

MAELSTROM

Smart technology for MARine Litter SusTainable
RemOval and Management

D9.5

Final Communication and Dissemination Report

03/2025

General Information

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1 Executive Summary

The present document is the **Final Communication and Dissemination Report** for the EU-funded project MAELSTROM – *Smart technology for MARine Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management*. This is **Deliverable 9.5** of Work Package 9 and aims to inform the European Commission and the MAELSTROM consortium about the communication and dissemination activities carried out during the project lifecycle over the past **48 months** (4 years).

Although communication and dissemination activities are closely related, we have chosen to address them as two separate sections for reporting purposes. In this context:

- **Communication** refers to efforts to strategically promote the project, its relevance, and its milestones to a wide range of audiences, including the media and the public, fostering two-way engagement.
- **Dissemination**, on the other hand, refers to activities aimed at promoting and facilitating the use of MAELSTROM's research and technological results among potential users and stakeholders in the research, industry, commercial, and policymaking sectors.

Thanks to the active participation of its 14 consortium members, the MAELSTROM project has successfully achieved its communication and dissemination goals, significantly contributing to the global conversation on marine litter management and circular economy. Over the past 4 years, the project has reached significant milestones, including 2 international awards, the development of 2 marine litter removal technologies, 1 AI-sorting robot, 1 marine litter tracking app and tested 3 different marine litter recycling processes. Academic engagement included 10 master's theses and 2 PhD dissertations. MAELSTROM participated at 2 UNEP International Negotiating Committees to develop an international legally binding instrument on plastic pollution, including in the marine environment (INC-3 and INC-4), it was invited to 73 conferences, and established partnerships with 30 international projects/networks. It organized 5 international side events, 4 demonstration events, 4 international stakeholder engagement workshops, and 4 ML thematic webinars. The consortium has moreover constituted the MAELSTROM Working Group which unites 27 members from 18 institutions across 8 countries. MAELSTROM made contributions to science-policy integration by publishing 7

scientific articles (with more in progress) and developing 2 position papers with policy recommendations alongside 1 legacy document. The project hosted 23 cleanup events across 3 countries, engaging over 800 people and removing more than 2 tons of marine litter. Additionally, it involved 500 school students in educational initiatives to promote environmental awareness. MAELSTROM generated 78 news articles, published 1,125 social media posts, and was featured on 5 European TV channels. Multimedia efforts included the production of 6 videos, 8 newsletters, 24 MAELDrops, 11 flash interviews, 2 trilingual booklets, and 10 press releases, all disseminated via the project's website and social media channels. The creation of three plastic recycled whales as powerful symbols of sustainability has enhanced MAELSTROM's outreach and engagement efforts.

MAELSTROM's communication and dissemination have engaged diverse audiences, from the public and media to key stakeholders in research, industry, policymaking, and education. The efforts outlined in this report have not only promoted the project's objectives and technological advancements but also fostered valuable collaborations, ensuring the lasting impact and continued relevance of the MAELSTROM outcomes for the international community.

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2 The MAELSTROM Project

MAELSTROM - *Smart technology for MARine Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management* is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex question of the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy. MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with fully-fledged circular economy and society-oriented solutions. In particular, the project:

- (i) sets out a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas.
- (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable, and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second-generation fuel, to identify, remove, and sort marine litter.
- (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems.
- (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation.
- (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of MAELSTROM solutions, also providing a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products.
- (vi) enhances social awareness on the issue of marine litter and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities.
- (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

3 The MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of the following partners

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	ALPHA Consult	ALPHA UK	Emiliano SPALTRO es@alphacons.eu
	Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research	CIIMAR	Isabel SOUSA-PINTO ispinto@ciimar.up.pt
	Servizi Tecnici	ST	Nicola FERRARI n.ferrari@stvenezia.com
	The Great Bubble Barrier	TGBB	Philip EHRHORN philip@thegreatbubblebarrier.com
	MAKEEN	MAKEEN	Anders BJORN ABJ@makeenenergy.com
	National Center for Scientific Research	CNRS	Marc GOUTTEFARDE marc.gouttefarde@lirmm.fr

Table 1 - MAELSTROM partners

4 Aim of the Deliverable

This document presents the **Final Communication and Dissemination Report** for the EU-funded project MAELSTROM. It is **Deliverable 9.5** of Work Package 9 and provides a comprehensive summary of the communication and dissemination activities carried out over the course of the project, highlighting key actions and outcomes from the past 48 months.

The report builds upon Deliverable 9.1: **Plan of Dissemination and Communication**, which was delivered in June 2021 and outlined the initial strategy and work plan for the project's communication and dissemination efforts. It details the progress made in promoting MAELSTROM's objectives and results, including participation in physical and online events, key publications, networking initiatives, and social media performance. Additionally, the document describes the adaptive strategies implemented to address evolving communication needs throughout the project, reflecting the dynamic nature of the consortium's activities.

Work Package 9 – Communication and Dissemination consisted of five tasks, as shown in Figure 1:

- Task 9.1: Communication and Dissemination Plans
- Task 9.2: Project Branding & Media
- Task 9.3: Support Capacity Building Actions
- Task 9.4: Support Stakeholder Engagement Processes
- Task 9.5: Support Project's Events

Figure 1 - Communication and Dissemination Tasks

5 Main Communication and Dissemination Outcomes

Effective communication and dissemination are essential components of any successful research and innovation project, ensuring that its findings and outcomes reach relevant stakeholders and generate meaningful impact. Within the MAELSTROM project, significant communication efforts were dedicated to sharing knowledge, promoting project's technological and scientific advancements, and fostering engagement across multiple audiences.

From public events and educational initiatives to scientific conferences, press articles, and stakeholder networking actions, the consortium effectively leveraged planned activities while also embracing new opportunities that arose during the project. All actions were guided by the framework established in the Plan for Communication and Dissemination which provided a strategic roadmap for reaching a broad spectrum of stakeholders, including researchers, industry professionals, policymakers, and the general public. By adopting an integrated approach, the communication and dissemination strategy aimed at:

- Increase **awareness** of MAELSTROM's relevance, goals, and milestones.
- Promote the **adoption** and utilization of its innovative technologies and research results.
- Build meaningful **collaborations** with key stakeholders at local, regional, and international levels.

Together, these efforts significantly enhanced the visibility and impact of MAELSTROM's outcomes, solidifying its contribution to tackling marine litter and promoting a circular economy paradigm.

MAIN OUTCOMES

MAELSTROM involved 14 partners from 8 EU countries, with a total funding of €6 million. Over the 48 months, MAELSTROM achieved significant milestones, including 2 international awards, the development of 2 marine litter removal technologies, 1 AI-sorting robot and 1 marine litter tracking app, tested 3 different marine litter recycling processes creating new valuable products out of it. Academic engagement included 10 master's theses and 2 PhD dissertations.

CLUSTERING & STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

MAELSTROM participated at 2 UNEP international negotiating committees, it was invited to 73 conferences, and established partnerships with 30 international projects/networks including the **Atlantic Strategy of the UN Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development** and the **EU Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters**, the **BlueMissionMed** Coordination and Support Action (CSA) among others. It organized 5 international side events, 4 demonstration events, 4 international stakeholder engagement workshops, and 4 ML thematic webinars. The consortium has moreover constituted the MAELSTROM Working Group which unites 27 members from 18 institutions across 8 countries (see also Deliverable 7.4). This collaborative group connects expertise from various EU-funded research projects to identify key research priorities for addressing marine litter across three primary pillars: Science-Society-Policy, Marine Litter Monitoring & Detection, and Marine Litter Removal & Recycling.

SCIENCE-POLICY

MAELSTROM made contributions to science-policy integration by publishing 7 scientific articles (with more in progress) and developing 2 position papers with policy recommendations alongside 1 legacy document.

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

The project hosted 23 cleanup events across 3 countries, engaging over 800 people and removing 2 tons of marine litter. Additionally, it involved 500 school students in educational initiatives to promote environmental awareness.

OUTREACH

To amplify its visibility, MAELSTROM generated 78 news articles, published 1,125 social media posts, and was featured on 5 European TV channels. Multimedia efforts included the production of 6 videos, 8 newsletters, 24 MaelDrops, 11 flash interviews, 2 trilingual booklets, and 10 press releases, all disseminated via the project's website and social media channels. The creation of **three plastic recycled whales** as powerful symbols of sustainability has enhanced MAELSTROM's outreach and engagement efforts. As a final outcome of the project, a dedicated documentary shooting for Euronews has been agreed by the Consortium for January 2025 focusing on the MAELSTROM cleaning technologies and environmental assessment.

6 Communication Strategy

MAELSTROM's communication actions were designed to promote the project's objectives and activities in a clear and accessible manner to a diverse range of stakeholders, including the wider civil society. In alignment with the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030, the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), these efforts focused on raising awareness about the impact of marine litter and plastic pollution, encouraging responsible behaviors, and showcasing innovative removal solutions.

While the **CIMA** Research Foundation, as the communication coordinator, led these activities, all project partners actively supported and engaged in the communication efforts. Strong collaborations were established with partner **VLPPF**, which led the communication efforts for the In-No-Plastic project, and **CIIMAR**, leading partner of the community and stakeholder engagement processes in Vila do Conde, Portugal. Both brought extensive experience in public awareness initiatives through cleanups, info-days, environmental awareness in schools and other community events. Additionally, connections with **CNR** past and ongoing projects on plastics, as well as partnerships with artists, art institutions and schools in Venice, were strongly supported by CIMA's Communication Department.

Key audiences included the citizens, young generations, local administrations and the private sector who were invited to reflect on the implications of plastic production and consumption, individual and institutional responsibility, and circular economy. These efforts were primarily carried out through public events and info days, alongside the publication of thematic interviews and graphically illustrated, bite-sized pieces of information on marine litter and plastic pollution, released on social media every to 2 months called MAELDrops.

Social media played a crucial role in MAELSTROM's communication efforts, utilizing five different channels and resulting in a total of 1,125 posts.

The project's visibility was further bolstered by interest from local and international journalists, including **The Guardian** and the **Horizon EU Magazine**, resulting in the publication of 78 international articles. **Euro News** has recently expressed interest in following the project's outcomes, contributing to its overall visibility even after its conclusion. We believe that MAELSTROM's communication efforts significantly

influenced how audiences perceived marine litter and inspired them to contribute to global efforts for sustainable oceans and societies.

6.1 Media & Branding | Task 9.2

Given the high communicative potential of the MAELSTROM project, initial efforts were dedicated to establishing a strong and visually appealing project brand. The MAELSTROM logo was carefully designed to reflect the core themes and natural elements associated with the project's objectives and activities. Through its dynamic lines, shapes, and colors, the logo evokes the environmental and marine settings at the heart of the project's work.

Designed with versatility in mind, the logo performs effectively across a wide range of applications - from traditional print media to digital platforms, including websites, apps, and promotional items such as T-shirts and branded gadgets. This adaptability ensures that MAELSTROM's visual identity remains consistent and impactful across all communication channels.

Figure 2 - MAELSTROM Logo visual elements

Given the number of planned events and invitations received by the consortium to participate in external initiatives, a multimedia package was developed and distributed to partners in the early months of 2021. This package was regularly updated throughout the project to meet the evolving needs of the consortium (e.g. updating partner logos). In 2022, a trilingual brochure was also produced, providing

detailed information about the project's objectives, technologies, and public events, such as clean-up activities. The brochure was made available in English, Italian, and Portuguese, reflecting the consortium's primary language (English) as well as the languages of the two pilot areas-Italy and Portugal-where MAELSTROM's technologies were implemented and where local stakeholder engagement was crucial. In 2024, the trilingual brochure was updated to include key outcomes achieved by the project, particularly highlighting the efficiency of the technologies developed and the environmental assessment processes undertaken and it was distributed during MAELSTROM's Final Event in Porto, Portugal.

Table 2 - Branding Materials

MAELSTROM Branding Materials	
EVENT'S KIT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logo • Leaflet and Brochure • PPT, Word and Poster templates • Roll-ups and flags • T-shirt and Bags
VIDEOS	<p>A total of six videos were produced as part of WP9:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MAELSTROM Intro – June 2021 • MAELSTROM App – July 2022 • Bubble Barrier @Portugal (short) – July 2022 • Bubble Barrier @Portugal (long) – November 2023 • Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform @Venice (short) – September 2022 • Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform @Venice (long) – September 2022 • AI Sorting Robot and Recycling Processes – November 2024 <p>Other videos, illustrating clean-up activities and sorting were co-developed with different partners such as the Municipality of Vila do Conde: https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-video/</p>
NEWSLETTERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter 1 – 06/2021 • Newsletter 2 – 12/2021 • Newsletter 3 – 06/2022 • Newsletter 4 – 12/2022 • Newsletter 5 – 06/2023 • Newsletter 6 – 12/2023 • Newsletter 7 – 06/2024 • Newsletter 8 – 12/2024 <p>https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-newsletters/ Please consult the Annex Section</p>

WEBSITE	http://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu
SOCIAL MEDIA	Facebook, LinkedIn, X, Instagram
MAELDrops	<p>Informative articles and postcards on key topics relating to marine litter, plastic pollution, circular economy and recycling innovations have been designed and published on both MAELSTROM website and on social media channels. A total of 34 MAELDrops were produced.</p> <p>https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maeldrops/ Please consult the Annex Section</p>
FLASH INTERVIEWS	<p>Series of short interviews/Q&As conducted with project partners regarding their contribution to the project's progress and its impact on marine litter management. A total of 10 interviews were produced.</p> <p>https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/flash-interviews/ Please consult the Annex Section</p>
WHALES INSTALLATIONS	Three models built and delivered, one in Portugal and two in Italy
PRESS OUTREACH	https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-press-review/

- Events Kit

The MAELSTROM events kit was designed to be versatile, catering to both formal events, such as conferences, and informal activities, like clean-ups. It included a variety of materials, such as internal and external roll-ups, brochures, flags, T-shirts, bags, and document templates (word and power point). These resources were made accessible to the consortium's partners through the dedicated MS Teams channel, the MAELSTROM Data Cloud repository, and the MAELSTROM website under the media kit section.

To minimize environmental impact, the printing of materials was limited to essential quantities and carried out only when digital alternatives were not feasible. Eco-friendly printing was strongly encouraged. In line with the project's sustainability goals, additional promotional gadgets were deemed unnecessary and were not produced.

Media Kit section: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstorm-media-kit/>

Figure 3 - Events materials

- Videos

As part of MAELSTROM's multimedia package, **six videos** were produced to illustrate the various stages of the project. The first video, which introduced the project, was created in 2021 and presented at the 1st International Workshop on the Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy, held in Venice during the International Boat Show. Since no "real" footage was available at that time, the video relied on an infographic approach to convey the project's objectives.

Five additional videos, featuring real project footage were also completed. The first of these focused on the MAELSTROM App, while the second announced the implementation of the Bubble Barrier in the Ave River, which was showcased during the UN Ocean Conference in Lisbon in June 2022. Two other comprehensive videos were produced to illustrate the implementation processes and launch events of MAELSTROM's Technologies - the Bubble Barrier in Vila do Conde and the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in Venice. Finally, a concluding video illustrating the AI-sorting Robot functionalities and the recycling processes and products explored within MAELSTROM was produced and presented at the final event in Porto, Portugal in 2024.

Local video production companies in Italy and Portugal were contracted to produce these videos, under the guidance of the CIMA Research Foundation, with logistical support from the partners responsible for the development and implementation of the technologies.

MAELSTROM

Video Section: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-newsletters/>

- **Newsletters**

Biannual newsletters were distributed every six months to the MAELSTROM Consortium and to interested subscribers. Each newsletter provided a summary of completed project activities, key milestones, and updates on ongoing work, as well as announcements for upcoming events and opportunities for engagement.

The newsletters were designed to keep stakeholders informed about the project's progress and to foster continued interest and collaboration. Individuals could subscribe to the MAELSTROM newsletter by completing a dedicated subscription form available on the project's website homepage.

In compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which came into effect in 2018, subscriber data was handled with the utmost care and privacy. Appropriate measures were taken to ensure data protection throughout the subscription and distribution process.

Newsletters Section: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-newsletters/>

Website

In addition to its active social media presence, the MAELSTROM website serves as the central hub for information on project activities, events, and key milestones. During the period from 1 January 2023 to 29 December 2024, the website has seen significant engagement, attracting an average of 4,064 new users per month. This demonstrates a consistent outreach, reflecting the growing interest in the project.

The majority of new users during this period hail from a diverse range of countries, with the highest numbers coming from the United States (1,149 users), Italy (506), Portugal (384), and the Netherlands (253). Among the most visited pages, the homepage stands out with a total of 4,436 visits, making it the most accessed entry point. Following closely is the page titled "What does MAELSTROM do?", which garnered 1,122 visits, indicating a strong interest in understanding the project's core objectives and activities. Another frequently visited page is the MAELSTROM

Outputs section, particularly the part dedicated to explaining the removal technologies, which attracted 865 visits. This suggests a keen interest in the technical aspects of the project, particularly its focus on innovative environmental solutions. Most visitors reached the website through direct searches, highlighting the effectiveness of the website's visibility and the growing awareness of MAELSTROM within its target audience. This trend suggests that the project is successfully building a dedicated and engaged following, with users actively seeking out information on its progress and outcomes.

Website: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/>

Figure 4 - MAELSTROM's website analytics

Social media

Social media accounts were established for the MAELSTROM project on **LinkedIn**, **Facebook**, **X**, **YouTube** and **Instagram**, recognizing the platforms' potential to reach diverse audiences and effectively engage them in the project's communication, dissemination and awareness objectives. These social media profiles served two primary purposes:

1. **Disseminating Scientific and Technological Outcomes:** aimed at sharing MAELSTROM's research findings, technological advancements, and milestones with stakeholders, including researchers, industry professionals, and policymakers. By leveraging these platforms, MAELSTROM ensured that its contributions to marine litter management and sustainable practices reached a wide audience, facilitating knowledge sharing and collaboration within the scientific community and beyond.
2. **Fostering Citizen Awareness:** Another key goal was to raise public consciousness about critical issues related to marine litter, single-use plastics, and the opportunities presented by a circular economy. Through engaging content, informative posts, and visually appealing graphics, the project sought to educate citizens on the impact of plastic pollution and encourage responsible behaviors that contributed to environmental sustainability. By cultivating a knowledgeable and active community, MAELSTROM aimed to inspire individuals to take part in local initiatives such as project cleanups and global efforts to combat marine litter.

Over the last four years MAELSTROM's social media channels have seen consistent growth, demonstrating a rise in both engagement and interest in the project, within diverse and global audiences.

Social media channel	Followers (n.)
LinkedIn	619
Facebook	271
X	266
Instagram	377

Facebook

The MAELSTROM Facebook account currently has 271 followers, with an average reach of 863 people over a 28-day period. The audience is fairly balanced, with 44% male followers and 56% female followers. The majority of the audience falls within the 25 to 54 age range and comes from mainly Italy and Portugal.

Figure 5 – Facebook analytics

Instagram

The MAELSTROM Instagram account has grown to 377 followers, with an average reach of 1,714 accounts over a 90-day period which indicates a significant level of engagement.

Figure 6 - Instagram analytics

X

The MAELSTROM X account has garnered 266 followers. Unfortunately, the platform's analytics features have been unavailable since 2022, preventing any further insights or detailed analysis of the account's growth and engagement metrics. As a result, we are unable to track current trends or assess the performance of our audience over time.

Figure 7 - MAELSTROM's X profile and followers

LinkedIn

Over the past four years, the MAELSTROM LinkedIn account has gained 619 followers, generating an average of 50,528 impressions and 1,603 reactions annually. This makes it the most successful account within our network, which is particularly positive given the platform's market-orientated focus, as well as the specialized technological and scientific nature of the MAELSTROM. The majority of visitors are from the research sector, with strong engagement from professionals in Portugal, Italy, Spain, and the Netherlands.

Visitor demographics

Job function

Visitor demographics

Location

Figure 8 - LinkedIn analytics

MAELDrops

To make complex topics such as marine litter, plastic pollution, circular economy, and recycling innovations accessible to a broad audience, the communication team developed an editorial project called **MAELDrops**. These were concise "information pills" accompanied by graphic illustrations, designed to simplify key concepts and share them in an engaging, visually appealing format. MAELDrops were posted approximately every 2 months.

The content for each MAELDrop was sourced from reputable scientific papers, reports from institutions such as the EU and UN, and other accredited websites. The primary aim of MAELDrops was to transform technical, scientific information into clear and accessible communication materials that resonate with a wide range of audiences. By doing so, the project sought to raise awareness on critical environmental issues and encourage active citizen engagement. ANNEX 2 provides an overview of all the MAELDrops produced.

Figure 9 - MAELDROP n. 24: Bioplastics, biodegradable and compostable plastics: second episode

Recycled Whale Installations

Three life-sized plastic sperm whale installations were created using recycled plastic provided by the Ecopolietilene Consortium ([link](#)), with whom the project established a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU).

The choice to represent sperm whales (*Physeter macrocephalus*) made from polyethylene as mascots for the MAELSTROM project steamed from their symbolic connection to the issue of marine pollution. Sperm whales, like many marine mammals, are endangered and particularly vulnerable to the threats posed by plastic waste in the oceans. Dozens of these creatures die from inflammation caused by indigestible plastic in their stomachs or from entanglement in ghost nets - abandoned plastic fishing gear.

Each year, over 640,000 tons of fishing nets, lines, pots, and traps - much of which is made from polyethylene - are discarded into the sea. Like other forms of plastic, polyethylene is non-biodegradable, takes centuries to decompose, and requires significant fossil fuel resources for its production. This makes it imperative to reduce its usage and maximize recycling efforts to mitigate its environmental impact.

As part of MAELSTROM's communication activities, the three life-sized whale sculptures were displayed in Portugal (1) and Italy (2). Whales were showcased at:

- Clean-up event in Porto, 2021
- Second International Workshop on the Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy held during the International Boat Show in Venice, June 2022.
- Anthropocene Exhibition to celebrate the 100 years of the Italian Research Council in Venice, 2023

The installations served as powerful visual representations of the marine litter problem and highlighted the need for innovative recycling solutions. The hosting partners, CNR-ISMAR and CIIMAR, will have the opportunity to continue using the whale installations for their environmental awareness activities, even after the conclusion of the project.

Figure 10 - MAELSTROM's recycled plastic sperm whale in Porto, during World Clean Up Day, 17/09/2021

Figure 11 - MAELSTROM's recycled plastic sperm whale in Venice at CNR-ISMAR headquarters, Italy.

Figure 12 - MAELSTROM's recycled plastic sperm whale in Venice at Palazzina Canonica, Italy.

Press Overview

MAELSTROM has gained significant media attention throughout its course, with a total of **83 interviews and articles published in local newspapers across Italy, Portugal, Spain, and Malta**, covering various project events and milestones. These articles are available for consultation on the MAELSTROM website, under the [Media – Press Review](#) section, providing a comprehensive overview of the project's visibility in local media. In addition to national coverage, the project was prominently featured in three respected international publications. **EU Horizon Magazine** dedicated two in-depth articles to MAELSTROM, highlighting its innovative approaches and significant contributions to tackling marine litter. The **Guardian** global newspaper also published an article showcasing the Bubble Barrier impacts.

Furthermore, MAELSTROM was included in the **CORDIS Synergy Info Pack**, further amplifying its reach within the EU Research and Innovation community.

MAELSTROM

- **CORDIS Synergy Info Pack: Restore our oceans and water**
https://ec.europa.eu/info/news/out-now-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-synergyinfo-pack-cordis-2022-feb-16_en
- **11/01/2022 - Meet Mr. Trash Wheel – and the other new devices that eat river plastic**
<https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2022/jan/11/meet-mr-trash-wheel-and-the-other-ingenious-tools-that-eat-river-plastic>
- **12/02/2022 - How robots and bubbles could soon help clean up underwater litter:**
<https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/horizon-magazine/how-robots-and-bubbles-could-soon-help-clean-underwater-litter>
- **09/02/2022 - Beach bots, sea ‘raptors’ and marine toolsets mobilized to get rid of marine litter:** <https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/horizon-magazine/beach-bots-sea-raptors-and-marine-toolsets-mobilised-get-rid-marine-litter>

7 Dissemination Strategy

Throughout the duration of the project the MAELSTROM team engaged in a diverse array of technical events, capacity-building initiatives, and scientific dissemination. These events served as crucial platforms for sharing the project's goals, technological progress, and preliminary results, fostering networking opportunities and building synergies among peers, researchers, and stakeholders across multiple levels.

While the CIMA communication team was not directly responsible for all of these activities, it played an important supporting role by providing technical communication expertise and materials. This collaboration was essential in ensuring that the project's findings were conveyed clearly and effectively, reinforcing the project's relevance within the broader research and innovation landscape. The involvement in such events allowed the MAELSTROM team to not only disseminate information but also to receive valuable feedback and insights from other experts in the field. This interaction contributed to refining the project's objectives and approaches while highlighting the importance of multi-stakeholder collaboration in addressing complex issues related to marine litter and plastic pollution. Dissemination efforts were conveyed into three tasks: i) support capacity building; ii) support stakeholder engagement; iii) support public events.

7.1 Support Capacity Building | Task 9.3

Capacity-building initiatives drive engagement and enhance collaboration among partners and stakeholders. They help build trust and facilitate open communication, enabling stakeholders to work together more efficiently and align their efforts toward common objectives.

The communication team's role in this task focused on: i) facilitating internal communication among partners; ii) engaging target audiences with MAELSTROM's technologies; iii) promoting the transfer of knowledge and expertise through a multimedia approach.

1. Supporting Internal Communication and Collaboration:

Given the importance of aligning efforts and sharing knowledge, the communication team made significant efforts to foster a participatory and supportive environment

among the consortium members, which was considered a key factor in the success of both the communication efforts and the project itself. To achieve this, the team organized regular communication meetings to keep partners informed about key milestones, upcoming events, and deliverables. These meetings played a crucial role in building a strong communication network within the consortium, enabling partners to exchange ideas, address challenges, and align their communication needs.

Additionally, the gatherings provided a platform for partners to request specific communication support or propose new ideas, ensuring that communication activities were well-coordinated, and contents clearly communicated to external stakeholders.

The decision to replace the one-off capacity-building workshop on communication - originally planned for the kick-off meeting, assuming it would take place in person - with regular monthly meetings proved to be highly beneficial. This shift facilitated consistent contact among the communication focal points, allowing for timely responses to their needs and suggestions. A total of **34 communication meetings** were organized, each focused on a specific topic, with all sessions encouraging open discussions and participatory brainstorming about communication strategies related to MAELSTROM activities. In addition to the regular monthly meetings, supplementary sessions were organized within smaller working groups when necessary (e.g., for partners involved in a specific event).

2. Engaging Targeted Audiences with the MAELSTROM Technologies:

One of the key capacity-building efforts supported by the communication team involved raising awareness about the MAELSTROM App, The Bubble Barrier, The Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform, the AI-Sorting Robot and the recycling processes. The team worked closely with project partners to organize demonstration sessions during international events, clean-up events and information days, where the **app's features and scale models** of the technologies were showcased to relevant users such as environmental organizations, volunteers, local stakeholders and marine litter practitioners. To support the process, the communication meeting produced **4 dedicated informative videos and a specific brochure section**.

Figure 13 - MAELSTROM's capacity-building activities for use of the MAELSTROM App with environmental associations in Venice

Figure 14- Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform presented by Damien Sallè from Tecnalia at the 2nd International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy, Venice, 1st June 2022

Figure 15 - Anne Marieke Eveleens from The Great Bubble Barrier demonstrates the Bubble Barrier system using a small-scale model at the United Nations Ocean Conference, Lisbon 28th June 2022

3. Promoting Knowledge Transfer

The communication team also supported capacity-building activities aimed at promoting knowledge transfer and fostering engagement with a wider network of stakeholders. By managing and disseminating communication materials such as newsletters, press releases, and informational brochures and videos, the team ensured that key project findings, best practices, and technical insights were shared with stakeholders, including local policy makers, industry experts, and academic partners. In addition to creating **materials for broader outreach**, the team also focused on developing **interactive educational tools**, like the MAELDrops infographics. These tools conveyed **complex information in an accessible manner** helping to build a deeper understanding of marine litter issues and the importance of circular economy approaches.

Moreover, the Consortium published 6 scientific papers, with 2 more already submitted and 15 more papers in preparation (see table below).

Published Papers	
Title	Year
Cyril Barrelet, Marc Chaumont, Gérard Subsol, Vincent Creuze, Marc Gouttefarde. From TrashCan to UNO: Deriving an Underwater Image Dataset To Get a More Consistent and Balanced Version. CVAUI 2022 – 5th Workshop on Computer Vision for Analysis of Underwater Imagery @ICPR, Jul 2022, Montreal, Canada. https://hal-lirmm.ccsd.cnrs.fr/lirmm-03815628/document	2022
Iglesias, M. Lupiac, L. R. Vieira, S.C. Antunes, J. Mira-Veiga, I. Sousa-Pinto, A. Lobo (2023): Socio-economic factors affecting the distribution of marine litter: The Portuguese case study. <i>Marine Pollution Bulletin</i> , 193, 115168. doi: 10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.115168 https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37329738/	2023
M. Gouttefarde, M. Rodriguez, C. Barrelet, P.-E. Hervé, V. Creuze, et al., The Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform: An Underwater Cable-Driven Parallel Robot for Marine Litter Removal. <i>Cable-Driven Parallel Robots</i> , S. Caro, T. Bruckmann and A. Pott eds., Springer, 2023 (Sixth International Conference on Cable-Driven Parallel Robots, CableCon 2023). https://hal-lirmm.ccsd.cnrs.fr/lirmm-04261099v1/document	2023
I. Iglesias, F.A. Buschman, G. Simone, F. Amorim, A. Bio, L.R. Vieira, H. Boisgontier, L. Zaggia, V. Moschino, F. Madricardo, I. Sousa-Pinto, S.C. Antunes (2024): Hydrodynamics of a highly stratified small estuary and the influence of nearby river plumes, <i>Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science</i> , Volume 304.	2024
M.M. Parascanu, J. Clavell Díaz, M. Rodriguez Mijangos, M. Isasa Sarralde, D. Salle, A. Alonso Galdames (2025): Life cycle assessment of an innovative seabed cleaning platform for marine litter removal in aquatic ecosystems, <i>Environmental Technology & Inno.</i> https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eti.2024.103971	2025
Gomes, I., Mira Veiga, J., Iglesias, I., Vieira, L., Kett, G., Sallé, D., Pessoa, A., Nerantzis, E. A., Zingariello, D., Betteto, G., Poletto, D., Moschino, V., & Madricardo, F. (2024). MAELSTROM Legacy Document. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14679311	2025

Submitted Papers	
Title	Year
L. R. Vieira, F. Madricardo, I. Gomes, A. Pessoa, J. Veiga, M. Bocci, G. F. Kett, I. Iglesias, S. C. Antunes, M. Ghezze, D. Poletto, V. Moschino, I. Sousa-Pinto. The need to align EC Directives to properly address Riverine-Marine Litter: A Contribution to EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”. <i>Submitted to Environmental Sciences Europe Journal</i>	2025
T. Cecchi, D. Poletto. ‘Ghost Boats’ in Venice: environmental and health concerns from their green chemical fingerprint and sustainable, blue, circular end-of-life-solutions.	2025
Papers in preparation	
Title	Year
Numerical modelling of the marine macro-litter hotspots on the seafloor of the Adriatic Sea - Ghezze et al. To be submitted to Marine Pollution Bulletin	2025
Seafloor macrolitter mapping and removal by an innovative robotic solution in the Venice Coastal Area - Mesghez et al. To be submitted to Remote Sensing	2025
Identification and characterization of marine litter items and distribution: case studies from the North-Western Adriatic Sea and North-Western Portuguese Coast and Estuaries - Moschino et al. To be submitted to Marine Pollution Bulletin	2025
Qualitative and quantitative assessment of microplastics pollution in waters and sediments of the Ave River estuary (Portugal) - Simone et al. To be submitted to Marine Pollution Bulletin	2025
Consideration of marine litter issues in marine planning: examples from some European countries and recommendations - Bocci et al. To be submitted to Marine Policy	2025
Consistent K-fold cross validation for image/video object detection, Cyril Barrelet, Marc Chaumont, Gérard Subsol, Vincent Creuze, and Marc Gouttefarde, IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, in revision.	2025
Understanding small shallow waters estuary hydrodynamics to forecast litter transport patterns - Benchama et al. To be submitted at Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science	2025
Ecological Evaluation of the Ave Estuary in the Face of Modern Environmental Challenges - S.C. Antunes, L.R. Vieira, I. Iglesias, S. Nogueira, G. Simone, G. de Castro, G.F. Kett, I. Sousa-Pinto. To be submitted to Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science	2025
From Source to Sink: Microplastic Transport and Distribution in the Ave River Estuary (NW Portugal) - L.R. Vieira et al. To be submitted to Science of Total Environment Journal	2025
From Policy to Action: Good Practices for Addressing Marine Litter through Collaboration and Innovation - L.R. Vieira et al. To be submitted to Environmental Sciences Europe Journal	2025
Tackling Marine Litter with Innovation: From Monitoring to Cutting-Edge Solutions - L.R. Vieira et al. To be submitted to Marine Pollution Bulletin Journal	2025
Knowledge Gaps in Marine Litter: Effective Strategies for Science & Society - G.F. Kett et al. To be submitted to Science of the Total Environment Journal	2025

Roadmap for Sustainable Management of Marine Litter in Europe - G.F. Kett et al. To be submitted to Journal of Environmental Management	2025
Potential impacts of removing operations of marine litter on fish and macro-zoobenthic communities- Moschino et al., To be submitted to Environmental Science and pollution research	2025
Mapping microplastic distribution and concentrations in the Venice coastal area (Italy) before and after macro-litter removal- Moschino et al., Environmental Science and pollution research	2025

7.2 Support Stakeholder Engagement Processes | Task 9.4

MAELSTROM actively sought to create synergies among multi-level actors within the marine litter sector. This included collaboration with similar and complementary EU projects, as well as partnerships with key public and private stakeholders such as municipalities in the pilot locations, waste management and recycling companies, academics, NGOs, artists, schools and local associations interested in connecting with and supporting the project.

Stakeholder engagement and networking activities were primarily led by the Portuguese partner CIIMAR for activities in Portugal, and by Venice Lagoon Plastic Free (VLPF) and CNR for activities in Italy. However, these efforts were closely aligned with the communication and dissemination activities, with CIIMAR, VLPF, CNR, and CIMA working in close synergy to ensure coordinated engagement. Below are some of the major achievements, which will be further detailed in CIIMAR's and CNR's reports.

→ Joint Strategy for Dissemination and Networking Activities on Marine Litter

The document was produced and delivered by 12/2021 by CIMA's team with guidance from CIIMAR under Work Package 7. The document received inputs from November's webinar discussions and presented recommendations for capitalizing efforts regarding marine litter dissemination and networking across multiple actors.

→ Stakeholder Engagement International Workshops in Venice, during the Venice International Boat Show

During the international workshops, the activities and efforts of various European projects were presented, each supporting the technological and cultural steps needed toward sustainable marine litter management in Italy and

across Europe (see deliverable 7.4 for further details). In addition, there was active engagement of stakeholders, fostering collaboration and knowledge-sharing among key actors, including policymakers, researchers, and local communities, to ensure the long-term success and implementation of these initiatives.

Figure 16 - Marine Litter International Workshops Editions

→ MAELSTROM Webinars

Four thematic webinars were organized by the MAELSTROM partners CIIMAR, CNR, VLPF and CIMA with the support and participation of other partners. All counted with the participation of several international stakeholders to whom the consortium has established an open dialogue for future collaborations.

- **Science and society:** working together to address the marine litter challenge
- **Building Capacity** in Detecting, Tracking and Modelling Marine Litter through European Open Science Cloud (#EOSC) Digital Services
- **Biodiversity and Marine Litter:** Co-detection and impacts
- **One Ocean One Health:** Current Perspectives on Marine Litter in Ecosystem and Human Health
- **Memorandums of Understanding**

- A Memorandum of Understanding was established with the Ecopolietilene Consortium (<https://ecopolietilene.it/>): an Italian group composed of manufacturers, distributors, and recyclers of polyethylene goods. The Ecopolietilene Consortium is an autonomous non-profit system recognized by the Italian Ministry of the Environment, Land and Sea Protection. The consortium has provided the recycled plastic material from which our life-size whale models were built.

→ Clustering and Networking

Figure 17 - MAELSTROM Networking

- The collaboration with our sister project In-No-Plastic translated into several synergies regarding communication activities, such as shared social media posts, shared press releases, and shared events.
- MAELSTROM attended a total of 73 conferences across Europe and internationally, actively engaging with a diverse range of stakeholders and experts in the field. Through these events, the project not only shared its findings and outcomes but also fostered valuable collaborations, establishing partnerships with 30 EU and international projects and organizations. These strategic alliances have helped to enhance the project's visibility, expand its

network, and strengthen its capacity to address complex environmental challenges on a broader scale, particularly in the realm of sustainable marine litter management.

MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic collaboration

MAELSTROM is meant to closely cooperate with its sister project In-No-Plastic, under the same call (ID: H2020-FNR-2020 - Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter). Both projects will contribute to the goal of the UN Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development aiming at “*a clean ocean where sources of pollution are identified and removed*”.

In this light, maximum cooperation between In-No-Plastic and MAELSTROM consortiums is and will continue to be pursued. This will be particularly relevant for stakeholder engagement, communication, and dissemination efforts. The benefits of having a common task force among the two teams are multiple:

- to create synergy between both projects towards disseminating a culture of awareness regarding the impact of marine litter on coastal ecosystems, within both projects' pilot geographical areas and beyond.
- to promote and give visibility to the experimentation of different innovative technological solutions for the removal and recycling of marine litter, within a sustainable circular economy approach.
- to promote the transfer and adoption of In-No-Plastic and MAELSTROM technologies by local administrators, showing their environmental and social benefits.
- to optimize resources, ideas, creativity, and efforts between both projects' communications teams.
- to widely highlight the multiple efforts being made towards a common goal - *to tackle marine litter* - with the full support of the European Union.

- **Sunset Beach Cleanups in Vila do Conde**

The communication team has played an active role in supporting the organization and providing visibility to the **annual Sunset Beach Cleanups** in collaboration with CIIMAR and the Vila do Conde Municipality, one of the key stakeholders in the project. These events have fostered an environment of trust and synergy among partners which were useful also for the implementation of the Bubble Barrier.

Figure 18 - Sunset Beach Cleanup in Vila do Conde, Portugal

→ Engaging Future Generations in the Fight Against Marine Litter

One of the most rewarding aspects of the MAELSTROM project has been its ability to connect with people across the globe, particularly younger generations, and raise awareness about the pressing issue of marine litter and environmental sustainability.

Over the past four years, the project has collaborated with schools, volunteers, and community groups to educate and inspire future leaders about the impact of marine litter on ecosystems.

For the MAELSTROM consortium, stepping beyond specialized scientific fields to make research accessible and engaging has been both a challenge and a necessity. This effort required not only simplifying complex scientific concepts but also finding ways to engage young people in meaningful ways that fostered curiosity, encouraged critical thinking, and motivated action. The goal was not just to share knowledge but to spark conversations and empower students to take responsibility for their role in protecting the environment.

The consortium's outreach efforts in schools in Venice and Vila do Conde were a key part of the project's civic education program, designed to raise awareness among students about marine litter and introduce them to the innovative technological solutions being developed by MAELSTROM's partners. These activities provided a platform for students to learn about the science behind marine pollution while also encouraging them to think about practical solutions.

As part of these educational initiatives, students were asked to reflect on their daily habits and identify disposable plastic products that could be replaced with more sustainable alternatives. Sharing their solutions with classmates created a collaborative learning environment where students could see how small changes could make a significant difference. Through these interactions, the consortium has gained valuable insights into how younger generations perceive environmental issues and the kinds of solutions they believe are most effective. This exchange of knowledge has enriched the project's overall understanding and reinforced the importance of making science more inclusive, interactive, and accessible.

Figure 19 - Seminar on microplastics at the Albert Einstein High School of Venice, February 2022

Figure 20 - Clean up activity in Pellestrina Beach with students from the Albert Einstein High School of Venice, May 2022

Figure 21 - Clean up activity in Vila do Conde with students from the Dr. Carlos Pinto Ferreira School District, May 2023

Figure 22 - Artistic Installation with collected marine litter by students from the Dr. Carlos Pinto Ferreira School District, May 2024

Figure 23 - Info day during the Sunset Beach Cleanup in Vila do Conde, Portugal, September 2024

7.3 Support Public Events | Task 9.5

MAELSTROM's communication team supported the consortium's attendance at public events, ensuring the project's visibility and enhancing its outreach efforts. From supporting event logistics to developing promotional materials, the team worked to ensure a strong and consistent presence at key conferences, workshops, and public events, highlighting the project's objectives and results and its contributions to sustainable marine litter management. Three highlights:

United Nations Ocean Conference held in Lisbon from 27th June to 1st July 2022

In this occasion the consortium had the exceptional opportunity to network and to present the project and its technologies. Considering the event was held in Portugal, a pilot country for the MAELSTROM project, emphasis was given to the Bubble Barrier system and to the MAELSTROM app, a universal tool to monitor the full marine litter collection-recycling process.

The project was represented physically by partners from CIIMAR, Venice Lagoon Plastic Free, and The Great Bubble Barrier, while CNR and CIIMAR partners joined the online High-Level Conference "*Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030*". Moreover, MAELSTROM had dedicated slots at two UN side events and a dedicated slot on CIIMAR's stands.

Figure 24 - MAELSTROM partners at the UN Ocean Conference Side Event, Matosinhos, June 25th, 2022

EU OCEAN DAYS

MAELSTROM participated in the EU Open Days, showcasing its work through a dedicated stand, a poster session, and the presentation of its two policy briefs. The stand provided a platform for engaging with a wide range of stakeholders, offering insights into the project's goals, activities, and outcomes. The poster presentation visually communicated key findings, while the policy briefs were shared with EU policymakers to highlight the project's suggestions to improve EU Regulations for sustainable marine litter management.

Figure 25 - MAELSTROM Partners at European Ocean Days, March 2024

UNEP International Negotiating Committees on Plastic Pollution – INC 3 and INC 4
 Fantina Madricardo, researcher at CNR-ISMAR and coordinator of the MAELSTROM project, participated in both the third and fourth sessions of the International Negotiating Committee (INC3 and INC4), as part of the Italian delegation as expert scientist in addressing plastic pollution. These strategic events, organized by the

United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), brought together a diverse range of stakeholders, including government officials, academic experts, civil society organizations, and private sector representatives.

The meetings underscored the growing recognition of the critical role that science plays in tackling plastic pollution. Scholars and researchers from across the globe were prominently involved, contributing their expertise and research findings to inform the ongoing negotiations and shape global strategies for combating plastic waste. Through her active participation, Fantina Madricardo further reinforced the project's commitment to contributing to international efforts to reduce plastic pollution and promote sustainable practices worldwide.

Figure 26 - International Negotiating Committee, Canada 2024: The European Union Delegation and the Italian Delegation.

Table 3 - MAELSTROM Events (Task 9.5)

	Title	Status	N. participants
Kick-off meeting	MAELSTROM Kick Off Meeting (online)	03-04-05/02/2021	All consortium members, an average of 2 per partner (28)
Dissemination Events	1 st International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy joint event with InNoPlastic H2020 project	03/06/2020	75
	2 nd International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy, joint event with InNoPlasticsH2020 project	06/2022	83
	3 rd International Workshop Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy, joint event with InNoPlastic H2020 project	06/2023	80
	4 th International Workshop Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy,	05/2024	73
	MAELSTROM Final Workshop & Conference – Porto, Portugal	11/2024	55
Clean ups & Info Days	Yearly clean ups (4 in total) & Info Day - Venice, Italy on World Ocean/World Environmental Day	05/06/2021	50
		02/06/2022	50
		06/2023 06/2024	
Clean ups & Info Days	Yearly clean ups (4 in total) & Info Day - Porto, Portugal on World Clean Up Day	09/2021	95
		09/2022	105
		09/2023 09/2024	100 110
Clean ups & Info Days	San Sebastian Clean Up, Spain	08/2022	30
	Gnejna Bay Cleanup, Malta	03/2024	50
Demonstration Workshops	Yearly side events (3 in total) – Venice, at the International Venice Boat Show dedicated to local stakeholders	06/2022	30
		06/2023 06/2024	
Demonstration Workshops	Side event – Porto, at the Business2Sea	11/2024	100
	Science and society: working together to address the marine litter challenge	18/11/2021	63
Demonstration Workshops	Building Capacity in Detecting, Tracking and Modelling Marine Litter through European Open Science Cloud (#EOSC) Digital Services	10/05/2022	26

Webinars	Biodiversity and Marine Litter: Co-detection and impacts	10/2022	20
	One Ocean One Health: Current Perspectives on Marine Litter in Ecosystem and Human Health	04/2023	40
Capacity Building Actions	Capacity Building on Communication & Stakeholder Engagement approaches. Target: MAELSTROM's partners/communication focal points	Replaced by monthly meetings	Communication Focal Points (average 14 per meeting)
	Marine litter monitoring using the MAELSTROM App - 2022	2022	60
	Marine litter monitoring using the MAELSTROM App - 2023	2023	80

8 MAELSTROM Legacy and Final Conclusions

MAELSTROM has been a successful journey, fuelled by the collaboration, expertise, and dedication of our international consortium partners. Their contributions were essential in achieving the project's goals and advancing our shared mission.

However, as with any ambitious undertaking, we faced challenges along the way. Some aspects of the project did not unfold as smoothly as expected, and we encountered areas that required adaptation and recalibration. These challenges, while difficult, provided invaluable lessons, helping us refine our approaches and ensuring continuous learning and growth throughout the project.

These insights have been captured in a **Legacy Document**, which reflects both our successes and setbacks. The purpose of the document is to share our experiences with other projects tackling marine litter, helping them avoid similar obstacles and improve their chances of success. We also hope that the lessons learned will inform European and national policies, contributing to more effective solutions for reducing marine litter and promoting long-term environmental sustainability. Specifically, the Legacy Document delves into:

- **Scientific Challenges**

Challenges in identifying pollution hotspots and understanding marine litter dynamics in pilot locations, ecological interactions and assessing short and long-term efficacy of MAELSTROM's removal technologies.

- **Technical Challenges**

Technical hurdles encountered during the design and development of marine litter removal technologies (es. integrating novelties/ specific features, ensuring durability in harsh marine environments, etc.); technical issues with identifying, collecting and recycling marine litter.

- **Logistical Challenges**

Logistical difficulties in deploying and operating MAELSTROM's technologies, including transportation to pilot areas, access to suitable test sites, coordination with local authorities and suppliers; management and transportation of marine litter to recycling and waste management companies. International logistics and subcontracting procedures.

- **Regulatory Challenges and Policy Gaps**

Regulatory complexities related to marine litter removal activities, including permits for testing experimental technologies, compliance with environmental regulations, and liability considerations. Policy gaps regarding riverine litter

and marine litter collecting and recycling procedures, and marine litter valorization.

- **Project Framework Challenges (Administrative and Financial)**

Project constraints including timeline, deliverables, reporting frameworks, budget limitations, cost overruns associated with research and development activities, etc.

- **Environmental Challenges**

Environmental factors that posed challenges to the effectiveness of marine litter removal technologies, such as specific hydrodynamic conditions, sediment characteristics, water turbidity or unpredictable weather conditions.

- **Stakeholder Engagement Challenges**

Challenges related to collaboration with stakeholders including differences in expertise, communication barriers, and conflicting priorities/expectations and awareness levels.

To streamline the partners' contributions, the legacy document has been structured according to the project's key phases: 1. Site Selection and Assessment; 2. Technology Design and Development; 3. Implementation; 4. Litter Collection, Sorting and Disposal; 5. Monitoring; 6. Transformation; 7. Market Entry and Uptake.

Each section addresses:

- What worked well.
- Challenges.
- What could have been improved.
- Opportunities and Suggestions (If relevant)

Link: https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/MAELSTROM_LEGACYREPORT.pdf

Figure 27 - MAELSTROM Legacy Document Cover, Published in November 2024

ANNEX 1 - Communication and dissemination procedures regarding third parties' involvement

The communication and dissemination guidelines regarding the involvement of Third Parties follow two different approaches depending on if referring to institutional/in-kind parties or to monetary/financing third parties.

A shared table regarding third parties' involvement was created on the MAELSTROM project channel on MS Teams where partners are expected to insert information and details regarding Parties willing to be involved in the project's activities. It was agreed that partners wishing to establish partnerships with third parties for activities happening within the MAELSTROM project shall inform the Project Manager (CNR-ISMAR) beforehand which, in case of possible ethical issues or conflict of interests will activate the Steering Committee to demand for a shared analysis and final decision.

Institutional and In-Kind Parties

Whenever requested and if considered to benefit a foreseen action and group of partners, every institutional/in-kind support will be fully acknowledged on communication materials. If requested, either by the third party or by the affiliated partner, third party's logos can be placed on MAELSTROM's communication materials (ex. Venice or Porto Municipalities logos), tagged on social media, and mentioned on press releases or in relevant project's events and activities. Approval will need to be previously given by the Project Manager/Consortium.

In the case that the institutional/in-kind support offered is considered to benefit only one partner, the communication process shall occur independently from MAELSTROM's communication group and shall be led by the affiliated partner responsible for the partnership/agreement. In this case, if the support received by the partner will be used for MAELSTROM-related activities, the project name and the European Union co-financing shall be mentioned, without creating a visual association (no logos together). In case the partner uses the support received for activities that do not relate to the MAELSTROM project, no mention to the project or the European Union shall be made.

Figure A1 - Communication procedures regarding institutional and in-kind third parties' involvement

Monetary/Financing Third Parties

Whenever requested, and if considered to benefit a group of partners, every monetary/financial support will be fully full acknowledged on communication materials. If requested, either by the third party or the affiliated partner, third party's logos can be placed on MAELSTROM's communication materials, tagged on social media and mentioned on press releases or in relevant project's events and activities. Approval will need to be previously given by the Project Manager/Consortium.

In the case monetary/financial support is considered to benefit only one partner, the communication process shall occur independently from MAELSTROM's communication group and shall be led by the affiliated partner responsible for the partnership/agreement. If the support received by the partner is to be used for MAELSTROM-related activities, the project name and the European Union co-financing percentages shall be mentioned, without creating a visual association (no logos together). Moreover, the partner benefiting from the monetary support shall clearly state the co-funding proportion being received, based on the total funding received by the European Union within the MAELSTROM project. In the case that the partner uses the support received for activities not related to the MAELSTROM project, no mention to the project or the European Union shall be made.

Figure A2 - Communication procedures regarding financial third parties' involvement

ANNEX 2 - MAELDROPS

MAELDrop #1 | The problem of marine litter | April 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-1-the-problem-of-marine-litter/>

*Day after day, coming together, raindrops fill the rivers and run into the sea. In the same way, we also want to create information drops which will fill our heads with thoughts, ideas and solutions related to marine litter and to MAELSTROM's goals: please welcome **MAELDrops!** How does marine litter damage the coastal ecosystems? Are all plastics the same? What can we do to limit this problem, and how does MAELSTROM aim to tackle it?*

So, let's get started, come along with us and be part of the move!

Seas and **oceans** play an important role for our planet. They influence the climate, support the life of many species and sustain fundamental human activities. However, the well-being of marine ecosystems is put at risk by several anthropogenic factors, including **litter**.

Litter, whether lost directly along the coastline or delivered to the sea by rivers, wind, or urban run-off, has an important ecological impact on marine life. As highlighted in a [report](#) published by the European Commission's JRC, litter can cause **direct damage**, for example by entangling or blocking the stomach/intestine of animals that accidentally ingest it. Moreover, the litter can cause **indirect damage**, for example by inducing a false sense of satiation, acting as vectors for toxic substances and compromising the animals' general ability to feed themselves.

Among marine litter, **plastics** are the most abundant. These are both large fragments and waste or very small particles resulting from the degradation and fragmentation of larger items. These are the [microplastics](#), smaller than 5 mm, which accumulate along the food web and, as a result, can even reach the food we consume.

What will MAELSTROM do to mitigate the litter issue? Our project will develop and test new environmentally sustainable technologies for removing litter accumulated on the seafloor or in the water column in coastal areas. MAELSTROM will then define and implement an integrated assessment approach (IAA) to evaluate the effectiveness of these technologies. This approach will support the Marine Strategy Framework Directive of European Union and assess the positive and/or negative impact of the MAELSTROM litter remediation actions on coastal marine ecosystems and local economies. The IAA will consider both macro and microlitter.

SEAS AND OCEANS play an **IMPORTANT ROLE FOR OUR PLANET** but they are put at risk by several anthropogenic factors including litter

PLASTICS are the most abundant including microplastics which accumulate along the food web and can **REACH THE FOOD WE CONSUME**

LITTER can cause both direct and indirect **DAMAGE TO MARINE LIFE** compromising animals general well-being

MAELSTROM aims to mitigate this issue by testing technologies for **LITTER REMOVAL FROM COASTAL ECOSYSTEMS** preventing its accumulation and degradation

MAELDrop #2 | How much litter is in the sea? | May 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-2-how-much-litter-is-in-the-sea/>

In [MAELDrop #1](#), we have introduced you to the problem of marine litter. But what kind of litter is marine litter? And in which quantities is it present in the oceans?

The United Nation Environment Programme [defines](#) marine litter as “any persistent, manufactured or processed solid material discarded, disposed of or abandoned in the marine and coastal environment”. As we reported, the majority of it is plastics. Assessing the amount of plastics in the sea is not easy, as estimates can give different results depending on the methodology used.

[According to the European Commission](#), **more than 150 million tons of plastic are accumulated in the oceans** and unfortunately, these quantities are increasing: between 4.6 and 12.7 million tons of plastic are added each year, and it could reach **29 million tons by 2040**.

These are impressive numbers, which should be considered even more worrisome considering that most marine litter consists of materials that degrade slowly. As a result, their continuous and increasing dispersion in the seas leads to a **progressive accumulation**. In this way the marine litter becomes pervasive in all the environments increasing the risks for all the food web and the habitats.

What will MAELSTROM do to mitigate the accumulation of marine litter? There are two activities in our project that will help reduce marine litter. On the one hand, we will test and implement two innovative technologies that will allow for the removal of litter from the seabed and from the superficial layers of the water column – we will present them to you soon! But we can't tackle the problem with technology alone – we need shared good practices and everyone's help to preserve our marine ecosystems. Being so, as part of the project we have organized info days and clean up campaigns where we will not be only collecting litter that has accumulated on the coast, but also creating awareness regarding marine litter impacts and spreading good behaviors to mitigate its impacts in coastal ecosystems and in our life!

More than
150 MILLION
TONS OF PLASTIC
are accumulated
in the oceans

These
QUANTITIES ARE
INCREASING.

Between **4.6** and **12.7 MILLION TONS**
of plastic are added each year

Since most marine litter consists of
MATERIALS THAT DEGRADE SLOWLY,
there is a **PROGRESSIVE**
ACCUMULATION in the seas

MAELSTROM will test and
implement two innovative
TECHNOLOGIES
FOR LITTER REMOVAL.

But we can't tackle the problem with
technology alone: discover
WHAT YOU CAN DO TO HELP US!

STAY TUNED...

MAELDrop #3 | Marine litter, from the sea back to the coast | June 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-3-marine-litter-from-the-sea-back-to-the-coast/>

In the last MAELDrops, we've told how much litter is found in the seas and oceans, and the damage it causes to ecosystems. But waste doesn't just stay in the water....

Carried by winds and rivers, or even abandoned directly in the sea, currents can concentrate waste, accumulating in large areas, as the famous Great Pacific Garbage Patch. But not all litter remains at sea. Ocean currents, in fact, often bring it back to shore ... and so we find it on our coasts and beaches. In addition to representing a possible **economic and landscape damage** (who likes to sunbathe surrounded by garbage?), here too litter can put at risk our ecosystems. According to a recent technical report by the European Union's JRC, a beach can be considered clean if less than 20 pieces of trash are found every 100 linear meters of coastline: this is a significant value, if we consider that between 2015 and 2016 many European beaches had on average 150 objects every 100 meters.

Understanding how much and what type of waste is found along the coasts is important to design effective strategies and policies aimed at reducing it. In this sense, **clean up campaigns are a tool of enormous importance**, because on the one hand they help to clean beaches and, on the other hand, they contribute to collect data on the marine litter. In addition, they represent a valuable opportunity to raise public awareness on the problem of marine litter.

What about MAELSTROM? We too believe in the importance of clean ups! The problem of marine litter, in fact, cannot be addressed only with science and technology: all citizens can commit to reduce it, both through small daily gestures and by participating in the clean-up events... Like the one that will be held in June 5th in Venice! Stay tuned to learn more, in the coming days we will provide all the information about the event, the first – but certainly not the last – of our project!

NOT ALL LITTER REMAINS AT SEA :

ocean currents often bring it back to shore ... and so we **FIND IT ON OUR COASTS AND BEACHES.**

CLEAN UP CAMPAIGNS

are a tool of enormous importance : **THEY HELP TO CLEAN BEACHES...**

...contribute **TO COLLECT DATA ON THE MARINE LITTER** and represent a valuable opportunity to raise **PUBLIC AWARENESS.**

WHAT ABOUT MAELSTROM?

We too believe in the importance of clean up campaign - as the one that will be held in **JUNE 5th IN VENICE :** stay tuned, in the coming days we will provide all the information about this **FIRST BUT CERTAINLY NOT THE LAST EVENT!**

MAELDrop #4 | Many types of plastics | July 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-4-many-types-of-plastics/>

In our MAELDrops, we have mentioned that most of the marine litter is plastic. But what exactly is plastic?

Plastics are a set of polymeric materials, made up of many equal and repeated units. There are diverse types of plastics, and each one has distinct characteristics according to the type of polymer from which it is made. Even in a simple bottle of water we can find two types of plastics: the bottle itself is usually made of polyethylene terephthalate (PET), which is light and resistant, whereas the cap is often made of polypropylene (PP), which is slightly harder and more heat resistant.

Plastics play an important role for human activities. Just think, for example, of how many medical devices, from disposable gloves to catheters, are made of plastic. However, if not responsibly managed and disposed, plastics can become a severe problem for ecosystems, with impacts on our own health.

One of the strategies to mitigate the problem, in addition to limiting production whenever possible, is to recycle and re-use plastic materials within in a circular economy perspective. To do so, it is necessary to consider the distinct types of plastics and choose appropriate recycling treatments accordingly.

What about MAELSTROM? From the marine litter collected by our technologies, plastics will be separated thanks to a robot based on an artificial intelligence system. In accordance with the European circular economy action plan, plastics will then be recycled through 3 innovative processes: additive and compounding, hot pressing, and low temperature pyrolysis, which will allow to recycle most of the plastic waste. Materials which will not be directed to recycling will be used for primary energy generation and second-generation fuel, and will power MAELSTROM's underwater cable-robot for marine waste collection... creating a self-sustaining cycle!

MAELSTROM

NOT ALL PLASTICS ARE THE SAME!

There are diverse types of plastics, with distinct **CHARACTERISTICS AND PROPERTIES**

COLLECTING AND RECYCLING PLASTICS ARE KEY

to limit its accumulation on ecosystems, but it requires **PROPER IDENTIFICATION AND SORTING**

MAELSTROM will use a
ROBOT BASED ON AI
TO SEPARATE PLASTICS
 from the waste collected in rivers'
 hotspots in Italy and Portugal

Based on single characteristics
 it will direct plastic waste to
**INNOVATIVE
 RECYCLING
 PROCESSES,**
 or when not compatible,
 it will use it to power
 MAELSTROM's technologies, creating
A SELF-SUSTAINING CYCLE!

MAELDrop #5 | Let's talk about polyethylene | November 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-5-lets-talk-about-polyethylene/>

Some time ago we mentioned the fact that there is not just one type of plastic, but many, each one of them with its own properties that influence their recycling feasibility. Among the several widespread plastics we use daily, today we will focus on **polyethylene**. Why?

Firstly, because polyethylene is a very versatile polymer, which can be molded into many different shapes and objects, both for everyday and industrial uses [1]. Some examples are: kitchen objects such as jugs or cutting boards, children's toys in parks, drainpipes, and many others, in a very long list. The second reason is that polyethylene is completely recyclable which, considering its wide diffusion, makes it an important type of plastic to consider in terms of circular economy!

It is for this reason that we have chosen recycled polyethylene as the material to make our MAELSTROM mascot whales! We have already introduced you one of the three sperm whales that will accompany us in the next years of work last September, during the Clean Up in Porto, organized by our partner CIIMAR. More two family members will follow soon!

The whales were made possible thanks to the support of the Italian consortium Ecopolietilene and will help us to disseminate knowledge on marine litter impacts on coastal ecosystems and on sharing good practices regarding innovative plastic removal and recycling technologies. In this way, we will join forces to protect habitat of our sperm whales and of the many other marine species put at risk by the accumulation of marine litter!

MAELDrop #6 | The nexus between plastic and climate change | December 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-6-the-nexus-between-plastic-and-climate-change/>

The United Nations conference on climate change, COP26, has just concluded, confirming the commitment to try to keep the increase in the average global temperature within 1.5 C at the end of the century. There is much to do to achieve this goal, and there are many fronts on which to act. Plastic production is among them.

In fact, as the UNEP report “From Pollution to Solution: a global assessment of marine litter and plastic pollution” published a few days before the start of COP26 highlights that plastic production led to the emission of 1.7 gigatonnes of CO₂ equivalent in 2015. The authors estimate, moreover, that this figure will increase by about 6.5 times by 2050, reaching an amount that is around 15% of the global carbon budget.

In addition to the risks that plastics poses to ecosystems and to human health, which we have discussed in MAELDrop 1, we must consider that plastics also pose a threat to climate crisis mitigation.

The report also warns that, by 2040, the volume of plastic in the sea could triple. Meanwhile, recycling rates remain below 10%, and unfortunately biodegradable plastics are unlikely to be a solution to the problem. These materials have long degradation times, during which they pose risks to ecosystems as it happens with non-biodegradable plastics. For this reason, the report concludes that synergistic interventions are needed to address the problem. These include circular economy approaches, but also initiatives aimed at changing consumer’s behaviors regarding single-use plastics.

What about MAELSTROM? Our mission is perfectly in line with the report’s conclusions: in fact, we develops solutions to face the problem of the plastic already accumulated in the coastal environment acting on the entire “life cycle” of marine litter: we aim at understanding where marine litter is concentrated, identify it by type, remove it, recycle it and insert it back into the market chain. Following a circular economy approach plastics will be given a new life while avoiding the production of new plastic and in this way protecting coastal ecosystems and our climate.

MAELSTROM

A new **UNEP REPORT**, published a few days before the start of COP26, highlights that in 2015 **PLASTIC PRODUCTION** led to the emission of **1.7 GIGATONNES OF CO₂ EQUIVALENT**

PLASTIC IS THEREFORE A THREAT not only to ecosystems and human health but also to **CLIMATE CRISIS MITIGATION**

Synergistic interventions are needed to address the problem. These include **CIRCULAR ECONOMY** approaches but also initiatives aimed at changing **CONSUMER'S BEHAVIOURS** regarding **SINGLE-USE PLASTICS**

MAELSTROM'S MISSION is in line with the report's conclusions: we act on the entire **"LIFE CYCLE" OF MARINE LITTER**, from **IDENTIFICATION** to **RECYCLING** and **MARKETIZING !**

MAELDrop #7 | How the COVID-19 pandemics increases plastic generation and dispersion | February 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-7-how-the-covid-19-pandemics-increases-plastic-generation-and-dispersion/>

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the importance of plastics, as most protective and medical devices are, at least partially, made of it. At the same time, however, it has exacerbated the problem of plastic pollution due to the increased production and dispersion of protective devices, single-use plastics and plastic packaging in natural ecosystems. Moreover, the need for personal protective equipment has in some cases led to the delay or withdraw of national legislations against single-use plastic.

The relationship between COVID-19 and plastic generation and dispersal was already intuited at the beginning of the pandemic. Scientists are now beginning to quantify it: according to a recent paper, as of August 2021, COVID-19 had led to the production of approximately 8.4 million tons of plastic globally; 25.9 thousand tons of which ended up in the sea. The research has also identified a dozen rivers that transported 79% of the COVID-19-generated plastic into the oceans.

These and future data are of foremost importance as they indicate critical points on which to act and to focus global efforts. In general, however, the authors conclude by reiterating the need already expressed by many experts: technologies to improve the collection, treatment and **recycling** of plastic are urgently needed.

This is exactly our goal at MAELSTROM! The innovative technologies being developed by our consortium will contribute to improve the plastic management cycle by identifying and removing it from rivers and the seabed. Moreover, the recently launched MAELSTROM app will help operators to track the entire process, from litter identification up to its recycling outcomes. Environmental assessments and monitoring activities happening at the same time alongside the project will enable the identification of accumulation hotspots and will assess the impact of MAELSTROM technologies.

MAELSTROM

COVID-19 has exacerbated the **PROBLEM OF PLASTIC IN MARINE ECOSYSTEMS**, increasing the **PRODUCTION** and **DISPERSION** of protective devices and packaging

Approximately **8.4 MILLION TONS** of **COVID-19 RELATED PLASTIC** were produced globally, of which **25.9 THOUSAND TONS ENDED UP IN THE SEA**

This highlights once more the **NEED TO PROMOTE TECHNOLOGIES** to improve marine litter **IDENTIFICATION, COLLECTION, TREATMENT** and **RECYCLING**

MAELSTROM TECHNOLOGIES will contribute to improving the waste management cycle, **REMOVING PLASTIC FROM RIVERS AND SEABED**

MAELDrop #8 | Studying marine litter from above with remote sensing | March 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-8/>

Understanding how much waste is present in the oceans, which trajectories it follows and where it accumulates is an essential step to understand its impacts on marine and coastal ecosystems and to set solutions to remove it. However, this is far from easy considering the vast ocean surface and the difficulty to physically access some areas. An important help in this sense comes from remote sensing technologies.

The European Space Agency (ESA) is funding 26 innovative projects to improve marine litter knowledge and monitoring through remote sensing. Projects cover different geographic areas and work on several fronts, including the development of new data processing, modelling and experimental techniques, mostly based on artificial intelligence.

MAELSTROM fully supports such initiatives. Even if our project works mainly “from the ground” we are convinced that the research activities supported by ESA will not only provide valuable information regarding litter accumulation hotspots on where to focus removal efforts, but they will also open the way to innovative ways to understand the quantities and dynamics of plastics in the environment and how they change in time.

Two of MAELSTROM partners are involved in those ESA projects: CNR-ISMAR participates on the TRACE project, exploring the possibility to detect marine litter from satellite data and forecast their trajectories using a coupled system of water current forecast and marine litter dispersal model. Deltares, on the other hand, is leading the “Plastic Monitor” project, focused on the detection of floating plastic litter that is transported downstream, in very polluted rivers, such as the Citarum river, in Indonesia.

MONITORING THE VAST OCEAN surface to **UNDERSTAND MARINE LITTER QUANTITIES AND DYNAMICS** is not easy

An **IMPORTANT HELP** comes from **ESA** which is funding **MARINE LITTER PROJECTS** THROUGH **REMOTE SENSING**

MAELSTROM fully supports such initiative, as it will open the way to better **IDENTIFY ACCUMULATION HOTSPOTS**

And to better understand the **QUANTITIES AND DYNAMICS OF MARINE LITTER** in the environment and **HOW IT CHANGES IN TIME**

MAELDrop #9 | Cetaceans, between yesterday's risks and today's risks | May 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-9-cetaceans-between-yesterdays-risks-and-todays-risks/>

Moby Dick classic novel presents a rich description of what was known about whaling and cetaceans at the time of author Herman Melville (1851); some of those descriptions may seem odd for a reader today! For example, Melville wrote that hunting sperm whales would not lead to the decline of their populations as species were considered to be immortal.

Unfortunately, the facts did not prove him right. In the XIX and XX centuries, when cetaceans were hunted mainly for their fat which would be transformed into oil (and that of sperm whales was particularly appreciated) and hunting techniques were refined, there was a sharp decline in cetacean populations. In order to protect those animals, in 1986, came into force the ban of the International Whale Commission (IWC), an intergovernmental body charged with the conservation of whales and the management of whaling. Some states, however, have continued whaling – no longer to obtain blubber from these cetaceans, but to trade their meat.

This activity is condemned by many quarters because it adds to the serious threats that cetaceans already face. A 2018 report signed by the Environmental International Agency and the Animal Welfare Institute states that human activities put cetaceans at risk both directly and indirectly, sometimes even acting synergistically: habitat degradation, chemical and noise pollution, unintentional entanglement in fishing gear result in a cumulative stress. Among those threats there is also, plastic pollution. According to the report plastic waste often traps animals or/is ingested. In addition, baleen whales – cetaceans equipped with baleen to filter water – are also exposed to the risks associated with the ingestion of microplastics and associated pollutants.

In short, the activities of human species have created and still create severe damage to cetaceans. For this reason, MAELSTROM has chosen a cetacean as the “mascot” of its activities... a real-size model of a sperm whale calf, made entirely of recycled plastic which will accompany the MAELSTROM team during info days and clean-up activities, raising awareness among citizens on the risks that threaten marine ecosystems. The recycled material was kindly donated by the Italian Ecopolyethylene Consortium. If you are in Venice or visiting the Salone Nautico come and visit us at CNR!

MAELSTROM

PAST WHALING ACTIVITIES led to a **STRONG DECLINE OF CETACEAN POPULATIONS.**

For this reason, **IT HAS BEEN BANNED** even if some States still practice it

Whaling adds to the already many **SERIOUS THREATS THAT CETACEANS FACE INCLUDING PLASTIC POLLUTION**

That's why MAELSTROM has chosen a **SPERM WHALE AS A PROJECT "MASCOT"**: it will accompany our teams on **RAISING AWARENESS OF THE RISKS** posed by plastics to coastal ecosystems

Come and **MEET OUR WHALE IN VENICE**, during our **NEXT WORKSHOP IN JUNE!**

VENICE
JUNE
2022

MAELDrop #10 | Marine litter, a vehicle of transport for invasive species | September 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-10-marine-litter-a-vehicle-of-transport-for-invasive-species/>

When thinking of marine litter impacts on ecosystems, we often think about the ingestion and entanglement of animals. However, marine litter poses other lesser-known risks to ecosystems, such as the spread of invasive alien species. These are organisms that reach areas of the planet other than those where they are native and successfully establish there. Invasive species can bring in new pathogens and compete with native species for resources. In many cases, invasive species pose a serious threat to the conservation of species at risk of extinction: an example is the Louisiana red crayfish (*Procambarus clarkia*), which competes with the Italian crayfish (*Austropotamobius pallipes*), classified as endangered by IUCN.

How can marine litter contribute to the spread of invasive species? Several studies point out that litter, including microplastics, act as transport platforms for species, even over great distances. Other elements, such as boats (e.g. ballast waters), can harbor allochthonous organisms, but it is more difficult to quantify (and thus keep track of) organisms carried by litter.

It seems clear, however, that the problem is not limited. A study shows that floating plastic has allowed the introduction of alien species even in the Antarctic Peninsula, where temperatures were thought to be too freezing for organisms to survive (it is also worth considering how global warming may reduce this constraint). The Mediterranean basin is well studied for marine invasive species: according to a JRC report, the more than 400 invasive species in the area arrived mainly from the Red Sea, via the Suez Canal, marine litter has been the vehicle for some of them.

In short, reducing the use of plastics, the main component of marine litter, and improving our litter management in general is crucial to protect aquatic ecosystems not always well-known ways! More needs to be done to inform citizens about all the implications of plastic consumerism and our MAELDrops aim at filling that gap!

The spread of
INVASIVE ALIEN SPECIES
is one of the **LESSER-KNOWN RISK**
posed by marine litter

We alien species are not from outer space... just from different areas of the planet!

Invasive species often
BRING PATHOGENS and
COMPETE WITH NATIVE SPECIES
for resources

We can be animals, plants, even microorganisms... and it is not always easy to distinguish us from native species!

Marine litter act as
TRANSPORT PLATFORMS
FOR INVASIVE SPECIES,
even over great distances

Not all of us manage to settle successfully in a new area. When we do it, we can become invasive!

MAELDROPS #10

Therefore,
REDUCING MARINE LITTER is crucial
TO PROTECT ECOSYSTEMS
in several ways!

Eradicating us is not easy: better to avoid letting us in!

MAELDROPS #10

MAELDrop #11 | Bioplastics, biodegradable and compostable plastics: first episode | October 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-11-bioplastics-biodegradable-and-compostable-plastics-first-episode/>

As broadly known, plastics represent the main component of marine litter. Moreover, the current global plastic production is responsible for the release of large amounts of CO₂ emissions, which are fueling climate crisis. Can then compostable, biodegradable and bioplastics be a sustainable alternative to traditional plastics?

“Alternative plastics” present several environmental advantages, but they also pose important issues that need to be addressed according to their types. The European Environment Agency refers to biodegradable plastics as being those materials which are capable of breaking down (biodegrading) under certain conditions and mediums; compostable plastics instead are those materials designed to biodegrade under the conditions of an industrial composting plant or industrial anaerobic digestion plant with a subsequent composting phase, or, at lower temperatures in the conditions of a well-managed home composter. On the other side, bioplastics are those made biomass sources (ex. food waste) as an alternative to petroleum. But beware, because not all bioplastics are biodegradable!

In fact, alternative plastics can take quite some time before fully degrade: a study conducted by researchers at the University of Plymouth showed that even plastics classified as compostable, while disappearing in water within three months, were still present in the soil after 27 months. Other materials tested, including a bag classified as biodegradable, remained intact in both water and soil after as much as 3 years! Anyway, times and efficiency of biodegradation depend on the kind of bioplastics and the environmental conditions.

This highlights one of the most important issues when talking about biodegradable, compostable and bioplastics: it is necessary to dispose them in the right way to ensure they can degrade without harming the environment.

The topic of bioplastics and compostable plastics is very broad, so we will talk more about it in the future. And remember: the best plastic will always be the one you don't use!

MAELSTROM

Can **COMPOSTABLE**
BIODEGRADABLE and
BIOPLASTICS be a
SOLUTION for **MARINE LITTER** and
GREENHOUSE EMISSIONS
related to plastic
production?

These materials have many
ADVANTAGES over
traditional plastics - but they also
pose **IMPORTANT ISSUES** that
need to be addressed

Plastics labelled as compostable or biodegradable can take **LONG PERIODS TO DEGRADE** in natural conditions. Therefore, it is important to follow a correct **DISPOSAL PROCEDURE**

MAELDROPS #11

But remember: the **BEST PLASTIC** will always be the **ONE YOU DON'T USE!**

MAELDROPS #11

MAELDrop 12 | Let's de-plastify the Holidays! | December 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-12-lets-de-plastify-the-holidays/>

December means that holidays are coming! How can we make our celebrations plastic-free or at least plastic-less? In this month's MAELDrop we have collected some suggestions for you!

One of the most characteristic aspects of this time of the year are presents. Our suggestion is to opt for gifts based on experiences instead of material objects: a cooking class, a theater yearly pass or a kayak weekend are all great opportunities to offer unforgettable moments to your loved ones. But if you need to go "material" look for eco-friendly options and objects that can be easily reused or recycled. Yes, unwrapping a gift is a wonderful experience! In this case consider using recycled or certified paper from sustainable sources, and avoid plastic ribbons, such as the traditional ones made of polypropylene.

Other wonderful moments of this time of the year are the big lunches and dinners with family and friends. During these occasions, we can still have the environment in mind by choosing washable or biodegradable crockery instead of disposable plastic plates and cups. The choice of food plays a vital role too: choose local food that can be transported in reusable or compostable bags and avoid global, packaged and high carbon footprint food.

Finally, decorations! There are plenty of alternatives to plastic and this also applies to Christmas tree lovers. Plastic trees have a strong environmental impact – just think about its production, transportation and disposal! In case you don't feel like having a real tree, which is a better choice than a plastic one, you can think of artistic alternatives: your next Christmas tree can be made of cardboard, books, pieces of wood or wine corks!

Have a look at the links below for further tips, inspiration and ideas for a plastic-free holidays and impress your friends and family without the plastic!

- <https://www.wwf.org.uk/top-tips-sustainable-christmas>
- <https://theconversation.com/how-to-have-yourself-a-plastic-free-christmas-108828>
- tree choice: <https://www.nature.org/en-us/what-we-do/our-priorities/protect-water-and-land/land-and-water-stories/real-vs-fake-christmas-tree/#:~:text=Real%20or%20Fake%3A%20Which%20Christmas,you're%20actual,y%20supporting%20forests>

How can we make
**OUR CELEBRATIONS
PLASTIC-FREE,**
or at least
PLASTIC-LESS

MAELDROPS #12

**PRESENTS: CHOOSE
EXPERIENCES**
and **ECO-FRIENDLY** objects.
BE AWARE OF PACKAGING too

MAELDROPS #12

For family meetings
AROUND THE TABLE:
GO LOCAL with **FOOD**
and opt for
**WASHABLE
CROCKERY**

MAELDROPS
#12

PLASTIC DECORATIONS:
find artistic alternatives using
NATURAL and **EVERYDAY
MATERIALS**. This year,
impress your friends and family
WITHOUT THE PLASTIC

MAELDROPS
#12

MAELDrop 13 | An international treaty against plastic | January 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-13-on-international-treaty-against-plastic/>

An international and legally binding instrument to tackle the problem of plastic pollution: this is the decision adopted in March last year by the United Nations Environment Assembly (UNEA). It is a historic decision, involving all member states in the fight against plastics within an holistic approach that comprehends the entire cycle: from the extraction of fossil fuels for plastic production, to its disposal – that, as we have repeatedly said in our MAELDrops, often linger for very long times in ecosystems, damaging them.

This choice sends a strong message about the importance of international collaboration to address a problem that, as we know, ignores geopolitical boundaries. Beyond transportation and trade, in fact, plastic waste travels all over the globe carried by ocean currents.

The first International Negotiating Committee was held between November 28 and December 2022: more than 2,300 delegates from 160 countries attended the event which marks the first step in the development of the treaty (the deadline for negotiations has been set for the end of 2024). It will be a challenging work, not least because, as some scientists point out, achieving the treaty will require accurate knowledge of where plastics come from, the trajectories they follow around the world, and according to which dynamics and responsibilities, requiring tremendous collaboration and good-will between science, policymakers, and citizenship.

As MAELSTROM, we strongly support the new treaty, wholeheartedly wishing the International Negotiating Committee and all the participating partners our best wishes. From our side we will keep contributing with our open data research and technological development to make the treaty effective on the shorter time possible!

March 2022: the United Nations Environment Assembly adopted a resolution to establish an **INTERNATIONAL AND LEGALLY BINDING TREATY TO TACKLE THE PLASTIC POLLUTION**

The treaty will address the **PROBLEM OF PLASTICS IN THEIR ENTIRE CYCLE:** from fossil fuels **EXTRACTION** for their **PRODUCTION** to their **DISPOSAL**

The first **INTERNATIONAL NEGOTIATING COMMITTEE** was held at the end of 2022, between November 28 and December 2, marking an **IMPORTANT FIRST STEP**

As MAELSTROM, we **STRONGLY SUPPORT** the new treaty, contributing to make it effective on **THE SHORTER TIME POSSIBLE** by **SHARING OPEN DATA** on our research and technological developments!

#LetsDoItWorld

MAELDrop #14 | A new pathology: plasticosis | March 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-14-a-new-pathology-plasticosis/>

We have long discussed on the harms that plastics can cause to animals: whales found with stomachs full of plastic, birds imprisoned in remnants of netting and waste that prevent them from flying, reduced ability to feed and to reproduce, among several other consequences.

However, documenting “invisible” and sub-lethal effects of plastic ingestion outside laboratories is often challenging, making it difficult to prove the correlation of plastic ingestion and negative impacts on animal health. At least until a recent study, conducted on flesh-footed shearwater, a medium-sized seabird.

The authors showed that ingestion of micro- and macroplastics in this species results in an overproduction of scar tissue (i.e., fibrosis) in the digestive tract, more specifically in the proventriculus, where digestion takes place [1]. The greater the amount of plastic ingested, the worse the fibrosis [2].

Researchers have named this phenomenon “plasticosis,” making it very clear how plastics can cause real pathologies – pathologies of the Anthropocene. In the shearwater, plasticosis can adversely affect the ability to absorb nutrients, the development of chicks, and make animals more vulnerable to infection. Moreover, although the research was conducted on only one species, it may actually affect others, and not just among birds.

Scientific evidence on the harms of plastics has long been too abundant to ignore. Action needs to be taken to substantially reduce pollution and to protect biodiversity. MAELSTROM deploys interdisciplinary expertise and new sustainable technologies to contribute to this goal, but a global challenge such as this, calls for a global collective effort. Stay with us; we will post regular updates on our work and suggestions on how you too can help!

MAELSTROM

We already know that
PLASTICS AFFECT ANIMAL well-being in many ways,
 but it can be challenging to study
INVISIBLE AND SUB-LETHAL EFFECTS

This phenomenon is called
PLASTICOSIS and could
 also **OCCUR IN OTHER SPECIES**
 with, yet to discover, several
 other negative impacts

A new study shows that
PLASTIC INGESTION
 causes **SCAR TISSUE FORMATION**
 in the seabird flesh-footed shearwater

The **EVIDENCE OF PLASTIC HARMS**
 can no longer be ignored!
 Action needs to be taken to substantially
REDUCE POLLUTION and
 to **PROTECT BIODIVERSITY**

JOIN
 THE
 CALL!

MAELDrop #15 | How old are microplastics in the sea? | June 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-15-how-old-are-microplastics-in-the-sea/>

How old are the microplastic fragments lying in our oceans? Knowing this can help us understand their origins and improve numerical models, used to determine the behavior of plastics in the oceans. However, we still lack a method to accurately determine the age of microplastics.

A recent study proposes an interesting approach to estimate microplastics age. It is based on the analysis of polyethylene, one of the most common plastics (see our MAELDrop 5!), which degrades through environmental exposure. “This degradation level can be measured using the change in the material’s molecular weight and something called the carbonyl index. Simply, when polyethylene degrades its carbonyl index increases and molecular weight decreases,” says in a release the first author of the research, Rie Okubo.

Researchers conducted a series of experiments to understand how different combinations of temperature and UV radiation affected the degradation of polyethylene in order to standardize the degradation times. Once the degradation times were established, researchers conducted tests on microplastic samples collected from the sea, in the western North Pacific Ocean, finding that nearshore microplastics ranged from 0 to 5 years old, whereas offshore samples ranged from 1 to 3 years old.

Delving into the dynamics of plastics in the oceans is a key step in understanding how to reduce their presence and establish the most effective management policies. In the meantime, remember that we can all do our part daily by choosing products with as little plastic as possible and disposing of it properly so that it is directed to recycling!

Knowing the **AGE OF MICROPLASTIC** can be a valuable aid to understand their origins and to **IMPROVE NUMERICAL MODELING...**

MAELDROPS #15

However, we were still lacking a method **FOR PRECISE AGE DETERMINATION!** A recent study proposes a **NEW METHODOLOGY**

MAELDROPS #15

Based on the analysis of polyethylene, one of the most common plastics, researchers investigated **POLYETHYLENE DEGRADATION TIMES** based on **TEMPERATURE** and **UV RADIATION FACTORS**

MAELDROPS #15

Besides studies on plastic dynamics and management policies, remember that **EACH ONE OF US CAN CONTRIBUTE TO ITS REDUCTION,**

CHOOSING PRODUCTS WITH LITTLE OR NO PLASTIC and DISPOSING OF IT PROPERLY!

MAELDROPS #15

MAELDrop #16 | Oceanic birds and plastic exposure, a global assessment | July 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-16-oceanic-birds-and-plastic-exposure-a-global-assessment/>

We have repeatedly talked about the risks that marine litter, particularly plastic litter, poses to animals. Unfortunately, new studies highlight even more of them.

A vast research study which brought together more than 200 authors from more than 160 institutes in various parts of the world presents the first global exposure assessment of seabirds (that is, species that live in the open sea), particularly petrel species to plastic litter. The researchers combined data on bird movements (analyzing data from 148 populations in 27 countries and Antarctica) with data on plastic distribution: the main conclusion is that plastic hotspots are the areas most frequented by birds.

What does this mean? It means that the risk of plastic exposure for these animals is particularly high, even if it varies by species, population, and breeding season. This is particularly concerning if we consider that pelagic seabirds are already among the world's most endangered species groups – and the very species classified as “threatened” are also those for which exposure to plastic litter is greatest.

Researchers conclude their study by pointing out some of the priorities for species conservation and research, highlighting the key role of international cooperation as plastic pollution knows no borders, and marine litter travels throughout the seas, ignoring national boundaries. Another key message from researchers is the need to drastically reduce the quantity of plastics released into the environment. At MAELSTROM we certainly have no fear of repeating ourselves if, once again, we recall the importance of cutting the consumption of single use plastic, and incentivizing a conscious and effective plastic management throughout its entire life cycle!

MAELSTROM

A new study highlights once again
**THE RISKS THAT PLASTICS
POSE TO ANIMALS.**

It is the result of an extensive
INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH that
**BROUGHT TOGETHER
SCIENTISTS** from more than
160 INSTITUTIONS

Results show that **PLASTIC
HOTSPOTS** in the sea

correspond to the areas
**MOST FREQUENTED BY
PELAGIC SEABIRDS:** it means that for
these species the risks associated
with plastics are particularly high

We say it again:

PLASTICS HAVE NO BORDERS!

A drastic **REDUCTION** in their use,
a proper **DISPOSAL** and
management combined with
international **COOPERATION**...

Are all critical elements if we are to
truly **PROTECT THE**

ENVIRONMENT we share
with other species – **FOR THEIR
AND OUR OWN WELLBEING!**

MAELDrop #17 | The approval of EU Nature Restoration Law | October 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-17-the-approval-of-eu-nature-restoration-law/>

After a break, our MAELDrops are back!

The summer brought us some really good news: in July the Nature Restoration Law was approved! The approval of this law represents a key step towards the EU Biodiversity Strategy and the EU Green Deal, by setting a binding legal framework for Member States to plan and achieve ecosystems' restoration targets.

The Nature Restoration Law sets as an overall target the restoration of at least 20% of the EU's land and marine areas by 2030 and ultimately all ecosystems in need of restoration by 2050. Specific marine targets include "the restoration of habitats in marine ecosystems".

It was not a foregone conclusion that the Nature Restoration Law would be passed!

That is why at MAELSTROM we are celebrating its approval: environmental degradation, habitat and biodiversity loss, climate change and pollution are proceeding unabated, and the consequences are visible, undeniable and... scary! It is no longer time to procrastinate decisions, instead, we need politicians to make clear and decisive choices, recognizing the interdependence of human and natural well-being!

Measures **WILL COVER** at least
20% of EU lands
and SEAS by 2030

In July, the **EU PARLIAMENT**
APPROVED the **NATURE**
RESTORATION LAW

The law sets binding targets for the
RECOVERY and **CONSERVATION**
of **EU ECOSYSTEMS**

Let's celebrate the approval: it is time
to **OFFICIALLY RECOGNIZE** the
INTERDEPENDENCE
OF HUMAN AND
NATURAL WELL-BEING!

MAELDrop #18 | The effects of plastics on human health | October 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-18-the-effects-of-plastics-on-human-health/>

In the last years research has increasingly highlighted the impacts of plastic pollution in ecosystems, especially marine ecosystems, but what about the effects on the human species?

#Plastics found in the oceans can reach our table, especially through the food web. According to several studies, humans ingest significant amounts of #microplastics on a daily basis: up to 5 grams per day, although estimates may vary. Microplastics can enter our bodies when we eat fish products in which it has accumulated but also through the breakdown of water bottles, by absorption of some cosmetic products and by air inhalation – just to mention some examples. Research over the years has shown the presence of microplastics in a variety of human tissues, including the placenta [1].

If it is truth that we increasingly know and understand more about the direct and indirect harms which plastics can cause to other species [2], things are less clear when it comes to our own. We know that plastic products are composed not only of the polymer that represents the actual plastic, but also of different types of chemicals that give it specific characteristics which can be toxic to living organisms, acting, for example, as endocrine disruptors (i.e., affecting the production of hormones). Recent studies have also shown how, due to their small size, microplastics can stress cell membranes, destabilizing them [3].

In short, as the World Health Organization reports [4], data are still scarce and there is much to be learned about the possible toxic effects of plastics on human health. However, its presence is ubiquitous, calling for more sustainable development models in which we can better use and manage plastics in our lives.

[1] <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0160412020322297>

[2] <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-14-a-new-pathology-plasticosis/>

[3] <https://www.pnas.org/doi/full/10.1073/pnas.2104610118>

[4] <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/362049/9789240054608-eng.pdf?sequence=1>

MAELSTROM

Research shows that **we accumulate** up to **5 GRAMS OF PLASTICS PER DAY IN OUR BODIES**, but little is still known regarding the **impacts of plastics on human health**.

MAELDROPS
#18

Recent studies point out that **chemicals and additives** contained in plastic products can be potentially **TOXIC FOR LIVING ORGANISMS**, for example as endocrine disruptors.

MAELDROPS
#18

And that **microplastics**, due to their small size, **COULD STRESS CELL MEMBRANES**, destabilizing them.

MAELDROPS
#18

More research is need but **PLASTICS ARE UBIQUITOUS**, calling for sustainable development models in which we can **better use and manage plastics in our lives!**

MAELDROPS
#18

MAELDrop #19 | Plastic pollution is also an environmental justice issue | November 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-19-plastic-pollution-is-also-an-environmental-justice-issue/>

The environment and animal wellbeing are the most well-known victims of plastic pollution. But there are others, lesser-known victims of plastics. In fact, the impact of plastic pollution disproportionately affects the planet's most vulnerable communities, exacerbating socioeconomic inequalities globally. These are the main conclusions of a report published in 2021 by UNEP and the NGO Azul, which is dedicated to supporting grassroots communities to conserve marine resources.

The report documents the unfair effects of plastic at every stage of its life cycle: from the extraction of raw materials, leading to the destruction of habitats and the contamination of water and soil, to the production process, which often exposes those living near the industries not only to toxic chemicals but also, indirectly, to pollutants from, for example, trucks, and, of course, to the disposal phase. Inadequate plastic disposal, for instance, alters marine ecosystems, contributing to acidification and impacting the food chain—a detriment to the environment and to communities that rely on fish as their main source of protein.

As the report reminds, all these effects are exacerbated by the increased production and consumption of plastic linked to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Plastic pollution is, in short, a real issue of environmental justice – one of the many. As Marce Gutiérrez-Graudiņš, co-author, of the report and founder and Executive Director of Azul, says: “Plastic pollution is a social justice issue. Current efforts to manage and decrease plastic pollution are inadequate to address the full scope of problems it entails. Disparate impacts on communities affected by plastic, at every point from production to waste, should make environmental justice a customary consideration within the marine conservation field.”

Plastic pollution is not only a problem for the environment and animal wellbeing.

It makes other less known victims!

It disproportionately affects the most **vulnerable communities**, not only through disposal but also throughout the entire plastics lifecycle

The effects have been exacerbated by the **increased plastic production and consumption** due to the **COVID-19 pandemic**

Plastic pollution is among the many **environmental justice issues** exacerbating **socioeconomic inequalities**, calling us to act!

MAELDrop #20 | The EU Plastics own resource | February 2024

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-20-the-eu-plastics-own-resource/>

Taxes and economic contributions may not be our favorite topics, but in this case, we're talking about contributions that have an exceptionally important goal. Imagine a world where every step you take to the supermarket or every package you receive at your doorstep doesn't just contribute to your daily life but also to a healthier planet. This is at the core of the "plastics own resource", introduced in the European Union in 2021. But what does it mean, and how can it be useful?

Here's how it works: Member States are required to make contributions based on the amount of non-recycled plastic packaging they produce. A "uniform call rate" (0.80 euro/kg) is applied to the weight of non-recycled plastic packaging waste. There's an important detail: the contribution is intelligently designed not to burden the less affluent EU countries excessively.

But how is this contribution calculated? It's quite straightforward, using data. Member States are obliged to provide information on how much plastic packaging is used and how much of it is actually recycled. This data is collected by Eurostat and made publicly available, promoting transparency.

This own resource doesn't dictate how Member States should utilize the funds generated by this contribution. Some of them have opted for (or plan to implement) a national "plastic tax." This means they can choose how to invest tax revenues so to have the maximum impact at the local level.

While the initiative has sparked some criticism and doubts (for instance, there are concerns it may lead to a shift towards even more environmentally impactful packaging materials), the "plastics own resource" is much more than just an economic contribution. Aligned with various other directives and initiatives like the EU Plastic Strategy and the Circular Economy Action Plan, it represents another step towards circular economy.

Ever wondered about the **“plastics own resource”** in the EU? This is a contribution on **non-recycled plastic packaging waste**, introduced in 2021

This measure leaves **Member States** the possibility to **define the most suitable policies** to **reduce plastic packaging waste pollution** at local level

Member States already **share recycling and packaging data**, which is used to **calculate the contribution**

The “plastics own resource” is not just a an economic contribution - it's **another step** towards **circular economy!**

MAELDrop #21 | The effects of plastics on human health, pt. 2 | April 2024

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-21-the-effects-of-plastics-on-human-health-pt-2/>

A while ago, in one of our MAELDrop, we talked about how little we still know about the effects that plastic – especially micro and nanoplastics (MNPs), which accumulate in tissues – has on human health.

Although studies still have some limitations, it has been possible to highlight some effects of plastics in terms of inflammation and oxidative damage, as well as possible mechanical stresses on cells. Much less clear is the clinical effect of this material within our bodies.

This year, a study revealed the presence of microplastics and nanoplastics in atherosclerotic carotid plaques for the first time. The researchers found MNPs in more than half of the patients who underwent surgery and were part of the study. Monitoring these patients over subsequent months, they observed that those with detectable MNPs faced a higher risk of cardiovascular events when compared with patients in whom MNPs were not detected. Additionally, these patients exhibited elevated levels of inflammatory molecules. This suggests a potential pathogenic mechanism of plastics: heightened inflammation renders the atherosclerotic plaques more susceptible to rupture, clot formation and potential complications such as heart attacks or embolisms. Subsequently, another study published shortly after echoed these findings.

However, attention: correlation is not causation. It has not been possible to demonstrate that the increased cardiovascular risk was directly correlated with the presence of plastic. Still, the correlation observed raises important questions to guide future studies: is plastic really a risk factor? In which quantities does it become dangerous? What other organs can be impacted by its presence and how? There are many open questions, yet one certainty remains: it is time to quickly change our approach regarding the production, use, and disposal of plastic.

MAELSTROM

In March 2024, a study highlighted for the first time the **presence of plastics** in **atherosclerotic plaques**

MAELDROPS
#21

Authors noticed that patients in whom **plastics had been detected** were also the ones most at risk of **cardiovascular problems**

MAELDROPS
#21

Correlation is not causation.
Still, these finding open important paths for investigating the still unknown **clinical effects of plastics**

MAELDROPS
#21

What we know for certain is that **we urgently need change** approach regarding the **production, use, and disposal of plastic**

MAELDROPS
#21

MAELDrop #22 | Enzymes for plastic degradation | June 2024

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-22-enzymes-for-plastic-degradation/>

There are numerous strategies to combat plastic pollution in marine and terrestrial environments, and all are essential. Efforts must be concentrated on material management, recycling, and removal. Particularly promising advancements come from biotechnology, which has recently achieved significant progress in developing enzyme-based solutions for plastic decomposition.

The most notable discovery involves an enzyme called PETase, identified in 2016 by a team of Japanese researchers in the bacterium *Ideonella sakaiensis*. PETase can degrade polyethylene terephthalate (PET), one of the most commonly used plastics for bottles and food containers. Scientists have engineered the enzyme to increase its efficiency and speed of plastic decomposition.

Over time, other organisms have also shown the ability to decompose plastic, including some invertebrates. Research has focused on improving their catalytic abilities and thermal stability. Among the main limitations to the application of these enzymes is that they are currently too slow to function at an industrial level and require physical-chemical conditions that may not be easily replicable on a large scale.

However, scientists recognize the great potential of these enzymes and enzymatic complexes in the fight against plastic pollution. Additionally, some studies suggest they could also help in the degradation of microplastics.

In recent years, biotechnology has made significant strides in developing solutions for **plastic decomposition** through the **use of enzymes**

The most notable discovery is an **enzyme that can degrade PET**, one of the **most used plastics** for bottles and food containers

This enzyme - **PETase** - has been **identified** in 2016 **in a bacterium**, but over time other organisms have also shown the ability to decompose plastic

Although there are some limitations, scientists recognize **the great potential of these enzymes** in the **fight against plastic pollution**

MAELDrop #23 | History of plastics | September 2024

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-23-history-of-plastics/>

Plastics are a heterogeneous group of materials, united by certain chemical characteristics. But do you know its history?

Strangely enough, ivory and billiards played a key role in the creation of plastics. In the late 19th century, billiards was very popular and a must-have for high society. Billiard balls were made of ivory, which was already becoming scarce at the time (though it took many more years before it was banned).

To replace ivory and other materials – like tortoiseshell and horn, used for making combs – the first plastics were developed. The very first was Parkesine, a semi-synthetic resin and its inventor, Alexander Parkes, won a bronze medal at the International Exhibition in London in 1862. A few years later, an even more successful material emerged: celluloid, made from nitrocellulose and patented in 1869 by John Hyatt.

However, these were still far from the “realm of synthetics” that characterizes plastics today. This path was opened by Bakelite, synthesized for the first time in 1907 and it was Leo Baekeland, who firstly reported the term “plastics” to name these materials.

Bakelite’s was widely used until the 1950s-60s for products like telephones, but over time, many other types of plastics emerged.

During and after the two World Wars, industrial production of many of the materials we use today began: cellophane, PVC, nylon, polyethylene. Between 1950 and 1970, plastic production increased twentyfold, and it has never stopped growing since. Indeed, it is expected to continue increasing, further revealing the heavy environmental consequences of what was once an enormous scientific advancement.

MAELSTROM

Did you know that ivory and billiards played a **key role in the creation of plastics?**
In fact, the first plastics were produced to **replace the ivory used for billiard balls**

The first plastics were **Parkesine and celluloid** developed in the late 19th century. However, they were still far from the **“realm of synthetics”** we know today

Bakelite, synthesized in 1907, was the **first “true” plastic**. Its success lasted a long time, but during and after the World Wars **many other types of plastics emerged**

Since 1950-70, **plastics production has never stopped growing**, revealing the **heavy environmental consequences of these materials**

MAELDrop #24 | Bioplastics, biodegradable and compostable plastics: second episode | October 2024

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-24-bioplastics-biodegradable-and-compostable-plastics-second-episode/>

Some time ago, we discussed biodegradable and compostable plastics, highlighting the challenges they present – even though they are often viewed as a more sustainable alternative to traditional plastics. Today, we want to explore how these materials are made.

Biodegradable and compostable plastics are usually made from renewable biological resources. One of the most commonly used materials is polylactic acid (PLA), derived from the starch of fermented plants (such as corn or sugarcane). Another common example is polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA), which are produced by certain bacteria during the fermentation. Starch blends, combining natural starch with plasticizers, are also used to create biodegradable plastics, often found in compostable bags or packaging films.

However, not all biodegradable plastics are necessarily biobased: some are fossil-based and created by adding chemical additives that promote degradation. An example of this is polycaprolactone (PCL), a synthetic polyester that is biodegradable and used in medical and industrial applications.

What are **biodegradable and compostable plastics** made of ?

Most are made from **renewable resources such as plants, starch, or microorganisms.**

Others are derived from **fossil sources, with chemical additives that promote degradation.**

Remember, **the impact of these materials depends on proper waste management !**

ANNEX 3 – Newsletters

Newsletter #1

<https://us6.campaign-archive.com/?u=29f791f69e98ddd6bbc588e28&id=35f9e8f70f>

[View this email in your browser](#)

July, 2021

MAELSTROM Newsletter #1

Welcome to MAELSTROM's project first newsletter! We are pleased to update you on the work we are carrying on, on our past and future events and all other news and milestones from the "MAELSTROM world". But, first of all... if you still don't know what MAELSTROM is about, let us introduce you the project!

What is MAELSTROM?

It is an EU-funded project designed to develop and test innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in coastal environments.

MAELSTROM will identify litter accumulation hotspots in the regions of Venice (Italy) and Porto (Portugal) and will implement two removal technologies – **a Bubble Barrier and an Underwater Cable Robot** designed to remove litter from the water column and from the sea/riverbed, respectively. Removal activities will be accompanied by environmental assessment, to understand the impact of marine litter in demo sites and that of the removal operations.

The removed litter will go through advanced recycling processes allowing for regenerated materials - such as polymers - to re-enter the industrial supply chains. At the end, feasibility studies regarding MAELSTROM's tested processes - from litter identification until its marketization - will bring together societal, economic and environmental indicators.

MAELSTROM will also contemplate science-policy interface, public awareness and societies' engagement regarding marine litter global challenge, through multiple events.

To know more, check our video [on YouTube](#) or [on our website!](#)

Our motto is:

Remove. Recycle. Give it a new use. Repeat

Will it be yours too?

Who are we?

MAELSTROM brings together 14 international partners from 8 EU countries:

MAELSTROM's events

MAELSTROM's Kickoff meeting

Three days of intense work to present goals and activities to be carried out in the next four years. One common aim: **to protect coastal ecosystems** by identifying, removing, recycling, and putting marine litter back in the market chain: discover more about our kick off meeting, held in February 2021!

[Learn More](#)

With In-No-Plastic, our first international event

The workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy: Challenges and Opportunities, held in Venice on June 3rd, was the first joint event of H2020 projects MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic. It was an **important moment to exchange knowledge** and updates on technologies being implemented for the removal and recycling of marine litter.

[Learn More](#)

Our first joint clean-up campaign in Venice

Strong citizens' participation and **three tons of collected waste**: great achievements on our first MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic joint clean up which took place in Venice during the World Environment Day, on June 5th.

[Learn More](#)

Next step: Porto's clean up event

Alongside the **World Cleanup Day** we will have our next beach clean up happening in September. The event will be organized by our partner CIIMAR and it will take place in Porto (Portugal). Stay tuned through our website and social media to have more details in the following weeks!

[Learn More](#)

MAELSTROM's technologies

The Great Bubble Barrier

Between the 12th and 16th of April, CIIMAR hosted The Great Bubble Barrier team in Northern Portugal, where several estuaries were analyzed towards the implementation of the **Bubble Barrier**. Both parties worked together to identify areas where a major impact can be achieved regarding marine litter removal actions.

Parallely, and in order to learn how the Bubble Barrier functions under different conditions, Deltares conducted some tests in Amsterdam. Bubble Barrier Amsterdam is active since 2019 in one of the main waterways of the Dutch capital preventing plastics from flowing into the North Sea. Deltares' researchers measured the flow velocity through two means: one permanent system at one location and one moving system using a drone. They then analysed the litter collected on a daily basis to see how the amount and composition of waste collected vary with wind and flow conditions.

Some of the litter collected included food wrappers and even a few laminated restaurant menus, for which the source can easily be traced back. The test was conducted with tangerines, a common way to measure floating objects. Using this common method to monitor floating objects, they determined what fraction of the

tangerines was collected by the Bubble Barrier. The majority was forced to the side of the canal into the catchment system.

Through those tests Deltares and The Great Bubble Barrier teams are able to better understand how the Bubble Barrier will work under different conditions, which will be used to design and deploy the Bubble Barrier in Portugal.

Underwater cable robot

In the past 6 months, an intense activity has been going on between the partners involved in the design of the **robotic system** to remove the marine litter from the seabed (Tecnalía, LIRMM, STVenezia, CNR ISMAR, VLPF).

Environmental conditions of the Venice lagoon and its surrounding coastal area were evaluated, including depth, tide, currents on the surface and seabed, among others. Paralelly, information regarding the marine litter and plastics items that are expected to be found on the seabed were also collected, discussing it directly within local consortium's partners CNR- ISMAR and VLPF, as well as with other external partners. Technical requirements regarding the sensors to be integrated in the robot (cameras, DVL, IMU, GPS, ADCP etc.), have also been defined so that the latter can be teleoperated from the surface and, in the future, be autonomously piloted by artificial intelligence and automatic control software.

Based on all these requirements, Tecnalía has created different designs of the cable-driven parallel robot mechatronics structure, as well as designs of the robot end-effector that will include a dredge as suction device and an underwater gripper for the grasping of larger items. The optimization of the designs is close to be concluded so that manufacture can start shortly!

MAELSTROM's milestones

Identification of litter hotspot in Venice. CNR-ISMAR has been engaged in the identification marine litter accumulation hotspots in the Venice Lagoon and coastal areas, to identify the most suitable locations to implement MAELSTROM's removal technologies.

MAELSTROM's first field monitoring for stranded marine litter. Held on the last week end of April, this was the first joint activity for MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic, and the **beginning** of a series of monitoring actions regarding waste stranded along the coasts of the Venice Lagoon. This first assessment was moreover useful to collect ideas and suggestions for the setup of MAELSTROM's marine litter tracking app.

MAELSTROM goes global. Think globally, act locally: the Environmental Education Center of Cairo Montenotte, in Liguria (Italy), **has engaged some local schools to collect plastic** which will be recycled and processed to be build MAELSTROM's gadgets!

MAELSTROM's networking

- [ITEM project](#)
- [EU Biovoices Project Conference](#)
- [BlueMed Conference](#)
- [Ecosistemas Marinhos e Economia Azul](#)
- [Chioggia Higher Education School & Fishermen Association](#)
- [European Maritime Day – Session BLUEINVEST](#)
- [NCR May Lecture – Netherlands Centre for River Studies](#)
- [EU Cluster Meeting on projects dealing with Marine Litter](#)
- [Quantia Eevent](#)
- [AreaAperta Primavera](#)
- [BleMed Hackathon 2021](#)

Co-funded by
the European Union

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Newsletter #2

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December, 2021

MAELSTROM Newsletter #2

Welcome to MAELSTROM's second newsletter! If you are new to MAELSTROM, note that it is an EU-funded project bringing together 14 partners from 8 European countries, designed to develop and test innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in coastal environments. Know more about the project [here!](#)

HOW IS IT GOING?

Environmental monitoring

Venice

In the last weeks, [CNR-ISMAR](#) started the environmental assessment in the Venice Lagoon by mapping hotspots of marine litter. CNR-ISMAR also tested different multibeam echosounder systems on the site to achieve the best results using the latest cutting-edge technology (Kongsberg, R2Sonic and Norbit). The maps will be the baseline of the next environmental assessment to be done before the robot implementation.

collected during the [LIFE-LEMA](#) project for analysis. Moreover, a large effort was done to define the complete robotic cell layout which is expected to be operational during the first semester of 2022 – on time to use the marine litter collected during the Venice summer clean-up on training the AI algorithm on real collected marine litter.

Main public events

In-No-Plastic/MAELSTROM workshop and Clean Up in Venice

The workshop *Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy: Challenges and Opportunities*, the first international event of MAELSTROM and our twin project *In-No-Plastic*, was held in Venice on June 3rd. This was an important moment of knowledge exchange and an opportunity to share updates on recent technologies for the removal and recycling of marine litter. The workshop was followed by a Lagoon clean-up on June 5th, within the World Environment Day.

[Learn More](#)

Porto Clean Up and info day on World Clean Up Day

On the World Clean-up Day, held on September 18th, [CIIMAR](#) and [CIMA Research Foundation](#) partners have organized a beach Clean-up at Castelo do Queijo (Porto). The event was associated with an info day to raise awareness about marine litter related impacts, and it counted with a special guest: our sperm whale! A real-size calf installation entirely made of recycled plastic, that was possible due to the precious help of the Italian Ecopolietilene consortium.

[Learn More](#)

... Last but not least

MAELSTROM FIRST WEBINAR WITHIN THE OCEAN DECADE

Within the United Nations Ocean Decade Laboratories, under the call "A Clean Ocean," the MAELSTROM team organized a satellite activity on *Inspiring Science and Society to tackle Marine Litter*. The event was held on November 18th, 2021, during a one-day online seminar and saw the participation of fifty participants in representation of multiple sectors from academia, private sector, environmental NGOs and Civil Society Organisations (CSOs). As for gender representation, 65% of the participants were women while 43% were men.

During the morning part of the webinar representatives of worldwide multi-scale marine litter initiatives presented the outcomes and the challenges experienced during their implementation efforts. On the afternoon, the webinar followed a participatory approach with discussions among panelists and participants on gaps and opportunities regarding marine litter within four clusters: 1) Civic Engagement,

Networking and Communication; ii) Stakeholder Coordination; iii) Governance; and iv) Funding

MAELSTROM APP

On December 11, a joint clean up event between MAELSTROM and the In-No-Plastics projects **closed the testing phase of the MAELSTROM app**. The App was designed to improve the marine litter collection and recycling processes based on more complete and accountable procedures. The App was developed by [GEES recycling](#), [ISDI](#) and [VLPF](#) partners. Read more [here!](#)

JOINT STRATEGY

As part of WP 7, the MAELSTROM team CIMA and CIIMAR have developed a Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions regarding Marine Litter (ML) mitigation initiatives within the European space. The strategy aims at contributing to the **coordination and integration of blue technology for plastic strategy-oriented efforts** by directly collecting the perspectives of ML practitioners and stakeholders on current gaps in the field. It furthermore aims at identifying effective approaches for multi-level stakeholder engagement, hopefully leading to more effective policies and actions regarding marine litter reduction, identification, removal, and recycling. The document will soon be online on MAELSTROM's website!

WHAT'S NEXT?

2022 public event

Next year will take us to Venice (Italy), Porto (Portugal) and San Sebastian (Spain) for more clean ups and info days: stay tuned on our website and social media for updates!

Next webinars

Not only public events: in 2022, we will organize two more webinars regarding marine litter and its challenges, so to increase networking actions across public, private, and societal actors also making use of our Forum: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/forums/forum/maelstrom-forum/>

WHERE HAVE WE BEEN?

June

- 01: [EU Cluster meeting in project dealing with Marine Litter](#)
- 08: [Quantia](#)
- 16: [Area Aperta](#)
- 17: [BlueMed Hackathon](#)

July

- 08: [EMRA2021 Marine Robotics](#)

September

- 12: [Quantia](#)
- 14: [BlueMed Unlocking the potential of Ports and Harbours in preventing and reducing the effects of Ma](#)
- 23: [Innovation Platform "Sustainable Sea and Ocean Solutions ISSS"](#)

October

- 26/27 [Ecomonda](#)

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Will it be yours too?

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Newsletter #3

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June, 2022

MAELSTROM Newsletter #3

Welcome to MAELSTROM's third newsletter! If you are new to MAELSTROM, note that it is an EU-funded project bringing together 14 partners from 8 European countries, designed to develop and test innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in coastal environments. Know more about the project [here!](#)

HOW IS IT GOING?

In February 2022, MAELSTROM's partners had a General Assembly and shared the main results of the first year of project. A quick update:

- **Characterization of major sources of marine litter in Venice and Vila do Conde.** MAELSTROM's leader [CNR-ISMAR](#) performed a systematic analysis and characterization of the marine litter sources in the northwestern Adriatic Sea and northwestern Portuguese coast and estuaries
- **Preliminary study assessment of the surface/water column Cleaning Device in the Netherlands.** Our partner [Deltares](#) carried out a one-week measurement campaign to understand how efficiently the Bubble Barrier is working in Amsterdam
- **Identification of the site for the installation of the Bubble Barrier.** Taking in consideration different aspects, [CIIMAR](#) and [The Great Bubble Barrier](#) identified the most suitable area of installation of the Bubble Barrier in Portugal
- **Integrated feasibility assessment report for the implementation of the MAELSTROM Bubble Barrier in Portugal.** Following the assessment of technical, practical, financial and environmental impacts, The Great Bubble Barrier has designed a suitable configuration of the Bubble Barrier and its solar panels, ensuring a maximized efficiency within the river's catchment system
- **Operationalisation of the MAELSTROM App.** Our partner [GEES](#) and [Venice Lagoon Plastic Free](#) have designed and developed complete hardware and software systems for marine litter identification, tracking and monitoring, following international standards of codification of marine litter items
- **Communication.** Our partner [CIMA](#) produced a Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions regarding marine litter mitigation, removal and recycling initiatives worldwide. Moreover, [CIMA](#) produced the MAELSTROM's Dissemination and Communication Plan; an interim report will be delivered by the end of June 2022

Find out more [here!](#)

MAELSTROM technologies

In June, our partners [Tecnalia](#) and CNRS-LIRMM have tested successfully the [Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform](#) that is soon to be installed in the Venice Lagoon.

While waiting for the transfer of the platform to Venice and in order to support its installation, CNR-ISMAR team collected videos and data, using a multibeam echo sounder and a miniROV, in the marine litter hotspots previously identified in the Venice Lagoon.

Understanding that MAELSTROM's technologies are too big to be transported, we have created two mini technologies to take with us to events and conferences! In the pictures below, the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform scale model (about 4% of the size of the real

platform) exposed during the [Venice Boat Show](#) and the Bubble Barrier scale model presented during the [UN Ocean Conference](#).

Main events

EU Green week

Within the EU Green Week 2022, MAELSTROM team organized [three events](#):

- May 31 - **meeting with local stakeholders**, to highlight the current marine litter management system in Venice in light of the recent approval of the Italian Salvamare regulation, which marks a turning point for the circular economy of marine litter in Italy. Activities and efforts of various European projects have been presented, each supporting the technological and cultural step needed towards sustainable marine litter management in Italy and across Europe.
- June 1 - **International workshop *Removal of Marine Litter and the Circular Economy – Challenges and Opportunities***, second edition of our annual workshop jointly organized with our twin project [In-No-Plastic](#). The workshop presented innovative and sustainable technologies for the removal and recycling of marine litter creating a chance for large industrial entities, start-ups, and NGOs to meet, exchange ideas, and to create synergies. The workshop was held at the Venice Boats Show and, at the CNR-ISMAR stand, we could also present our mascot, the calf sperm whale realized with recycled plastic kindly donated by the Italian Ecopolyethylene Consortium.
- June 2 – **Venice clean-up event**. In collaboration with In-No-Plastic, MAELSTROM organized a clean-up event in Venice and in the small islands at the lagoon outskirts. During the clean-up, the MAELSTROM App, now completely operational, has been widely used by MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic consortiums, local environmental associations, and volunteers. A total of 1734,36 Kg of litter was collected in just a couple of hours!

More information [here](#)!

Our calf sperm whale model at CNR-ISMAR headquarters during the Venice Boats Show. Another whale is exposed in Portugal, at CIIMAR's headquarters

MAELSTROM's webinars

On May 10, we held our second webinar untitled *Building Capacity in Detecting, Tracking and Modelling Marine Litter through European Open Science Cloud*, together with In-No-Plastic and [RELIANCE](#) projects.

The webinar, addressed to the scientific marine litter community, presented operational tools to produce collaborative scientific work on Marine Litter pollution using the EOSC digital services.

Flash news

UN Ocean Conference 2022

We have been honoured to participate at the [UN Ocean Conference 2022](#), which took place at the end of June in Lisbon! Besides participating at the Conference, MAELSTROM was also present at three side events:

- *Localizing Action for the Ocean: Local and Regional Governments Special Event* –June 25, Matosinhos
- *One Sustainable Ocean-Ocean Science & Business2Sea Side Even* - June 28, Lisbon
- *EU4OceanObs: Integrating Marine Litter Monitoring to Inform Action* - June 29, Cascais

Other interesting events took place during the first six months of 2022, providing a fantastic opportunity to highlight MAELSTROM and to connect and network with other colleagues internationally. Just to name a few:

- [Workshop EMFF Integration, Scaling Up and Cooperation with other EU Funding Instruments](#)
- [Expo Dubai - Land - City - Sea - Scape Intelligence Multidisciplinary and Systemic Approaches for the Rational Use of Resource and Sustainability](#)
- [GEOHABB 2022](#) – Marine Geological & Biological Mapping
- [EMRA 2022](#) - Workshop European Marine Robotics & Applications Workshop
- [AUTOMATION & ROBOTIC TALKS](#) (within BIEMH22 trade fair)

- **ERF2022 – European Robotics Forum** – Marine Robotics Workshop + Sustainable Robotics workshop

A study in the vertical distribution of litter in rivers

Rivers play an important role as ecosystems, supporting the lives of many species, and for human activities. Unfortunately, they also act as a road that allows litter to reach the sea. We still know relatively little, however, about how litter - and in particular plastic, the most represented in the sea - is distributed in the water column. Most studies, in fact, have focused on litter visible to the eye in the surface layers: but can we say there is as much of it in the depths?

A recent [paper](#) by Elise Blondel from Allseas and Frans Buschman from MAELSTROM's partner Deltares begins to answer this question. Their results show that the concentration of plastic near the riverbed is similar to that in the more superficial layers of the water column.

“This plastic adds to the plastics transport to the sea. Since the flux lower in the water column is substantial (at least for the investigated location, but it was also found in other Dutch locations), it should be taken into account”, says Dr. Buschman.

Read more [here!](#)

Don't miss our MAELDrops!

We are producing a set of MAELDrops, “pills” of information about marine litter, the danger it poses to ecosystems, and possible management strategies. Find them on social media channels by searching for [#MAELDrops](#) or read them directly on our website on the [news page!](#)

Our motto is:

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Will it be yours too?

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Newsletter #4

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December, 2022

MAELSTROM Newsletter #4

Welcome to MAELSTROM's third newsletter! If you are new to MAELSTROM, note that it is an EU-funded project bringing together 14 partners from 8 European countries, designed to develop and test innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in coastal environments. Know more about the project [here!](#)

HOW IS IT GOING?

Almost halfway into MAELSTROM!

We are now carrying out the third of a total of six phases: 1 – Localize; 2 – Characterize; 3 – Collect (we are here!); 4 – Sort; 5 – Transform; 6 – Marketize.

A lot still needs to be done to achieve our goals but end of the year newsletters are a good moment to celebrate our latest achievements. While we leave you to read, we take the chance to wish you a wonderful Holiday period and to thank you for being part of MAELSTROM with us! See you in 2023 with a renovated enthusiasm to beat plastic pollution!

HIGHLIGHTS

- **Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters 2030**

We are happy to share that **MAELSTROM** has joined the **European Commission's Charter** of the **Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters 2030**. MAELSTROM supports the Mission in several ways, by acting on the protection of aquatic ecosystems and on pollution prevention through its innovative marine litter removal and recycling technologies. The call is open to a wide audience of stakeholders and aims to give a clear signal of the importance of protecting inland waters and oceans by taking concrete actions. [Here](#) you can find more information on the Mission and how MAELSTROM supports it!

- **Seabed Cleaning Platform tested in Venice**

Important progresses were made on assembling our **Seabed Cleaning Platform based on Robotics**: the system was designed and produced by our partners [Tecnalia](#), [CNRS-LIRMM](#) and [ST](#) and tested in the Venice Lagoon during last September. We weren't the only ones being enthusiastic about it: also the President of the Veneto's Region, Mr. Luca Zaia, understood the usefulness of our Platform, as you can see in this [viral post](#), proving that local stakeholders can be actively engaged in common-good solutions.

Have a look at the video produced by our partner Tecnalia to understand how the Platform works [here](#).

- **How good is it?**

Cleaning operations in Venice were accompanied by our partner and project coordinator [CNR-ISMAR](#) which has conducted several **environmental monitoring actions** in the areas where the Seabed Cleaning Platform operated: the aim is to document the removal of marine litter in those areas confronting data from before and after the cleaning operations and to understand if and how the environment is changing after such actions. Find out more [here](#).

- **World Clean Up Day**

On September 17, as part of the [World Clean Up Day](#), we had our yearly multidisciplinary beach cleanup in the city of Vila do Conde (Portugal). The event was organized by our partners [CIIMAR](#) and [The Great Bubble Barrier](#), in collaboration with the [Centro de Monitorização e Interpretação Ambiental](#) (CMIA) and the [Câmara Municipal de Vila do Conde](#) and supported by of [Lipor](#) (Intermunicipal Waste Management Service of Greater Porto) and [Unifardas SA](#). See some pictures [here](#)!

- **Bubble Barrier @ Portugal**

We are looking forward to launching the first Bubble Barrier in Portugal! After some unexpected delays we are now finalizing the last technical issues to be ready to deploy this innovative litter removal system in Vila do Conde in 2023. Stay tuned for more information!

- **Earthshot Prize 2022**

By the way: our partner [The Great Bubble Barrier](#) was nominated as one of the finalists for the [Earthshot Prize 2022](#), the world's most prestigious and ambitious environmental prize, in the category *Revive our Oceans*! They haven't won the Prize, but they have not lost either...you can never lose when your mission is to protect the environment! Congratulations to all the nominees and a special high five to our Dutch partners!

- **MAELSTROM APP**

We had a chat with Giorgio Betteto, from our partner [GEES Recycling](#), and Martina Bocci, from our partner [Venice Lagoon Plastic Free](#), both in charge of the development of the MAELSTROM App, to learn more about its main features and how it can be of support for marine litter practitioners. [Here is the interview](#); and if you want to learn more about our App, have a look at our [new video](#)!

WHERE HAVE WE BEEN?

- [Pan-European digital assets supporting research communities – Benefits & Opportunities](#)
- [Innovazul 2nd International Meeting on Knowledge and the Blue Economy](#) - Open Innovation Session
- [Black Sea CONNECT Marine Litter Action Forum](#)
- [MARELESS Marine Litter and Circular Economy](#), by [Interreg Italy-Croatia Programme](#)
- [European Research and Innovation Days 2022](#) - session Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters: synergies and next steps

LAST BUT NOT LEAST: FOLLOW US AND DON'T MISS OUR #MAELDROPS!

This [month's MAELDrop](#) is about having a plastic-free Holidays with family and friends. Have a look at the suggestions that we have collected for you and follow us on social media to be always updated on the next MAELSTROM's milestones.

Our motto is:

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Will it be yours too?

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Newsletter #5

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June, 2023

MAELSTROM Newsletter #5

Welcome to MAELSTROM's fifth newsletter! If you are new to MAELSTROM, note that it is an EU-funded project bringing together 14 partners from 8 European countries, designed to develop and test innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in coastal environments. Know more about the project [here!](#)

HOW IS IT GOING?

Launch of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform

These last six months were extremely interesting for MAELSTROM! While activities keep being developed by all partners a special highlight goes to partners [Tecnalia](#), [CNRS-LIRMM](#) and [ST-Servizi Tecnici](#) which have finalized the testing phase of MAELSTROM's Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform - an innovative technological system for marine litter removal based on AI to sustainably remove litter from the seabed, without harming ecosystems. After being tested in Venice in September 2022, the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform was officially inaugurated on June the 9th, as part of the [European Green Week](#) and at the presence of Venice's councilor for the environment Massimiliano De Martin. Do you still remember how it works? If not, check [our video](#).

Click [here](#) to know more about the event.

Third International Workshop *Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economic: Challenges and Opportunities*

June was also the month for our Third International Workshop *Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economic: Challenges and Opportunities*, organized in collaboration with our twin project [In-No-Plastic](#) as a side event of the [Venice Boat Show](#). The meeting, which took place on June 1st at the headquarters of CNR-ISMAR, gathered representatives from academia, industry, and society to discuss the state of the art on knowledge and tools to monitor, remove and recycle marine litter, thus contributing to the achievement of the [EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters](#). However, as you know, we do not stop at meetings and workshops! The day after, thanks to our partner [Venice Lagoon Plastic Free](#), in collaboration with [WWF Plastic Smart Cities program](#), the [Italian Red Cross](#) and [Fare Verde](#) and [Poseidon](#) associations, we have organized a cleanup of the Venice canals and surrounding islands.

Cleanup activities are extremely important for MAELSTROM as they allow us engage citizens in the challenge of marine litter reduction and ecosystem protection. It never ceases to amaze us how much waste can be collected during these events: in just one morning our volunteers collected more than 1,300 kilograms of waste! The waste collected was identified and reported with the MAELSTROM App - developed according to the [EMODnet](#) categories- and sent to our partners [GEES](#) and [MAKEEN](#) for recycling.

Read more [here](#).

EU Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters – The Mediterranean Lighthouse in Action

Our project coordinator Fantina Madricardo from [CNR-ISMAR](#), and our colleagues Isabel Sousa Pinto and Luis Viera from [CIIMAR](#) participated at the *EU Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters* held in Palermo on May 30-1. They have represented MAELSTROM at the [Blue Mission Med](#) 1st Mediterranean Stakeholder Forum, under the Research & Education Table, in two sessions:

- Inspire and Inform: where they have showcased MAELSTROM's main achievements in [#research](#), [#oceanliteracy](#) and [#socialengagement](#).
- Blue Mission Med Stakeholder Forum: a session designed to identify key aspects towards implementing the Mission Lighthouse and to elaborate concrete actions (what and how) for each category.

MAELSTROM's WHALE - guest at CNR Anthropocene exhibit

Our third sperm whale, made of recycled polyethylene kindly provided by [Consorzio Ecopolietilene](#) is a special "guest" of *Anthropocene*, an exhibit celebrating the 100 years of the Italian Science Research Council (CNR). MAELSTROM's whale draws attention to the impacts of plastic pollution to marine ecosystems and it will be displayed at Palazzina Canonica, historical headquarters of [CNR-ISMAR](#) in Venice until July the 5th. If you happen to be in Venice during the next weeks, do not miss the opportunity to see the exhibit!

More info: <https://antropocene.cnr.it/>

World's Biggest Butt Pick Up - 1 million cigarette butts / Clean up in Vila do Conde

Between March and April, our team has dedicated specific efforts to the schools of Vila do Conde - our pilot location in Portugal. Our colleague Luis Vieira from [CIIMAR](#) gave some hours of training, during which he presented MAELSTROM's mission and goals, showing students the MAELSTROM App and a mini prototype of the Bubble Barrier, soon to be installed in the town's Ave River. On April 19th a joint clean up with students from Agrupamento de Escolas Dr Carlos Pinto Ferreira, in collaboration with CIIMAR and [CMIA](#) was organized at Ave's Estuarine Beach. During the cleanup students collected both macro- and microplastics and lots of cigarette butts! They have then decided to participate at the [World's Biggest Butt Pick Up - 1 million cigarette butts challenge](#), a national challenge launched by environmental activist The Trash Traveler. It was such a fun and enriching experience for all!

MAELSTROM's stakeholder meeting in Vila do Conde, Portugal

On April 4th, part of the MAELSTROM's Consortium has gathered in Portugal with national stakeholders from the [Vila do Conde Municipality](#), the Portuguese Secretary of State for Fisheries, the [Portuguese Environment Agency](#), the National Maritime Authority-Captaincy of Vila do Conde and [Docapesca](#) to share and discuss MAELSTROM's activities and goals for the region. The meeting, held at the Environmental Monitoring and Interpretation Center (CMIA) was an important occasion to collect and align stakeholders' needs and suggestions regarding the implementation of a [Bubble Barrier](#) in the Ave River.

Challenges, opportunities, and next steps for the installation of the system were widely discussed, ending with a unanimous and positive consensus for its local implementation and maximization.

MAELSTROM 5th General Assembly and Steering Committee

On February 15th and 16th, we had our 5th General Assembly and Steering Committee, hosted at [CNRS-LIRMM](#) headquarters in Montpellier. As we enter the second biennium of our project, we have spent those two days sharing lessons learned - what is working well, what is not? Which are the future challenges and opportunities for MAELSTROM's findings? There is a lot we can learn from each other and from difficulties and at MAELSTROM real sustainability starts with facing problems with an honest approach and working together to find solutions!

WHERE HAVE WE BEEN?

- [European Maritime Day](#) & Kick Off Meeting of the EU funded [WINBLUE Project - Empowering Women and Mainstreaming Gender Equality in the Blue Economy](#)
- [GeoHab International Symposium](#)
- CINEA Workshop [Synergies and Clustering between Maritime Projects](#)
- [14th European Robotics Forum](#)
- [AI for Good - What does it take for a robot to be sustainable? conference](#)
- First [EU Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters](#) Forum

- Air Centre Friday Networking online seminar [Marine Litter and Biodiversity: Co-Detection and Impacts](#)

WHAT'S NEXT?

Huge expectations for the next months as we will be implementing our second marine litter removal technology – a [Bubble Barrier](#), developed by our partner [The Great Bubble Barrier](#)! The Ave River in the Portuguese town of Vila do Conde was the place chosen to deploy this smart technology for plastic pollution. The system uses a bubble curtain to capture plastic pollution in rivers and, in the case of MAELSTROM, it will be co-powered by solar energy through our partner [Institute for Sustainable Energy - University of Malta](#). After some delays, a launch event is now foreseen to happen between September/October 2023. Our local partner [CIIMAR](#) is on the spot making sure all will happen smoothly, so fingers crossed and be tuned for more information soon!

Credit: courtesy of [The Great Bubble Barrier](#)

LAST BUT NOT LEAST: FOLLOW US AND DON'T MISS OUR #MAELDROPS AND FLASH INTERVIEWS!

This [month's MAELDrop](#) is a study to estimate the age of microplastics in the sea. Why is it important to know, and which innovative approach is under discussion? Follow us on social media to be always updated on our MAELDrops and MAELSTROM's main milestones!

We are also glad to announce that MAELSTROM's communication group has started a new editorial project called **MAELSTROM's flash interviews**. Alongside our MAELDROPS, they attempt to be an informative tool to deepen some aspects of partners' work which might not come across immediately. What is the link between robotics and sustainability? How are bathymetric maps useful to remove waste from the Venice Lagoon? What is the role, and which are the challenges for citizen's engagement in addressing marine litter?

MAELSTROM flash interviews are a series of short interviews with our partners, you can find them on social media but also on our website. Here the first two. Enjoy the reading!

- [MAELSTROM's flash interviews #1 | Talking about robotics and sustainability with Damien Sallé \(Tecnalia\)](#)
- [MAELSTROM's flash interviews #2 | Tackling litter in Venice Lagoon: Q&A with Fantina Madricardo](#)

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Newsletter #6

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December 2023

MAELSTROM Newsletter #6

Welcome to MAELSTROM's sixth newsletter! If you are new to MAELSTROM, note that it is an EU-funded project bringing together 14 partners from 8 European countries, designed to develop and test innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in coastal environments. Know more about the project [here!](#)

HOW IS IT GOING?

Launch event of the Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde – Portugal

Image credit: [The Great Bubble Barrier](#).

We have Bubbles!

After three years of intensive work, on November 25th, our Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde was officially launched in the city of Vila do Conde, in Portugal.

The Bubble Barrier is the second and last technology implemented by our project, following the [Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform launched in June, in Venice](#). The implementation of the Bubble Barrier has therefore been a milestone for the MAELSTROM team: it is already collecting plastics and other waste in the Ave River, preventing it to reach the sea and contributing to the [EU Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters](#).

The system was co-designed and implemented by our partners [The Great Bubble Barrier](#) and the [Institute for Sustainable Energy](#) of the University of Malta, under the supervision of the MAELSTROM coordinator, the Italian [CNR-ISMAR](#) and project partners [Deltares](#) and [CIIMAR](#). Moreover, the Bubble Barrier installation has counted with the key support and collaboration of the [Vila do Conde Municipality](#) – to whom we sincerely thank for its proactive approach regarding marine litter and plastic pollution – and from [CMIA Vila do Conde](#).

The inauguration ceremony was attended by the Portuguese State Secretary for the Sea, Dr. José Maria Costa, by the Vice-President of the [Portuguese Environmental Agency](#), Dr. José Pimenta Machado, by the Mayor of Vila do Conde, Dr. Vítor Manuel Moreira Costa, by the Port Captaincy Commander Monica Martins, by the Director of [Docapesca – Portos e Lotas, S.A.](#) Dr. Nuno Coelho and by [Lipor](#) CEO, Dr. Fernando Leite.

It was fantastic to see how our international collaboration-based project met the local support and commitment from the Portuguese Authorities, making it possible to install a permanent Bubble Barrier in the Ave River. In the next months, the MAELSTROM team (partners CIIMAR and Deltares) will be monitoring the type and quantity of waste collected and assessing the environmental impact of the Bubble Barrier in Ave's riverine ecosystem.

To know more about the Bubble Barrier, read the [dedicated page](#) and the [Flash Interview with The Great Bubble Barrier](#) on MAELSTROM's website and check the [video](#).

MAELSTROM receives the Atlantic Project Award 2023

MAELSTROM [has received](#) the Atlantic Project Award during the [10th Atlantic Stakeholder Platform Conference](#), under the category *Healthy Oceans and Resilient Coasts*, together with the [BlueMissionAA](#) project.

The Atlantic Project Awards feature outstanding initiatives, successful collaborations and achievements relevant to the implementation of the [Atlantic Action Plan 2.0](#). Under the category *Healthy Oceans and Resilient Coasts*, the award recognizes projects, initiatives and actions working for stronger coastal resilience and which reinforce the fight against marine pollution.

The award ceremony was held at the Porto Cruise Terminal in Oporto, Portugal and this year's conference was Atlantic Future: New synergies and innovations for a sustainable Ocean Economy.

Extremely grateful for such recognition!

MAELSTROM: Flagship project contributing to the EU Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters

MAELSTROM has been included in the [European Executive Research Agency's](#) (REA) factsheet as one of the project examples contributing to the implementation of the [EU Mission on Oceans and Waters!](#)

The five EU Missions were launched in 2021 by the Horizon Europe programme and aim at finding concrete solutions to some of our greatest challenges. In particular, the EU Mission on Ocean and Waters aims to tackle the challenges of pollution and biodiversity loss in oceans and waters through research and innovation, citizen engagement and blue investments – a key role in achieving climate neutrality and restoring nature.

Since 2014, REA has managed over 500 projects relevant to the Ocean and Waters Mission under the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe programmes.

Check REA's factsheet on the [EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters: European Research Executive Agency contributing to the Mission](#).

PUBLIC EVENTS

MAELSTROM Project Coordinator at the third session of the Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee

Fantina Madricardo, MAELSTROM coordinator, integrated the Italian Delegation participating at the Third Session of the Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee (INC-3) on Plastic Pollution, held at the [UN Environment Programme](#) headquarters in Nairobi from 13 to 19 November.

The aim of the INC is to develop an international legally binding instrument on plastic pollution which is to be based on a comprehensive approach that addresses the full life cycle of plastic, including its production, design and disposal. The INC began its work during the second half of 2022, with the ambition to complete the negotiations by the end of 2024.

MAELSTROM Workshop @ ECOMONDO

Our project coordinator Fantina Madricardo (CNR-ISMAR), with Claudia Pecoraro (DG-RTD, EU Science & Innovation) chaired the workshop *Sustainable Technologies for Marine Litter Removal and Recycling: the experience of the H2020 MAELSTROM project* during ECOMONDO's fair held on November 7th. MAELSTROM's partners attended the event and discussed the opportunities and the challenges faced while developing MAELSTROM's removal technologies – but also the role and the importance of stakeholder and citizen involvement in addressing plastic pollution.

The workshop was an opportunity to dialogue with many other experts from EU funded projects [Remedies](#), [Inspire Europe](#) and [Prep4Blue](#) which have illustrated their experiences in marine litter monitoring, removing and recycling, the lessons learnt, and the strategies put in place to overcome the challenges faced.

Sunset Beach Cleanup @ Vila do Conde

We have celebrated the [World Cleanup Day](#) and the [EU Beach Cleanup 2023](#) Campaign on September 16th, with a beach cleanup in Vila do Conde. The beach cleanup was followed by a stargazing session, guided by our colleagues from

[Counting Stars](#) – a group of astronomers and astrophotographers committed to reconnecting people with the wonders of the universe “over us”.

In just one hour, a total of 111 participants aged between 3 and 79 years collected 140 kg of marine litter: 29 kg of glass, 66kg of plastic and 45 kg of unsorted material, plus 1237 cigarette butts!

The Sunset Beach Cleanup was a joint action between MAELSTROM's partners ([CIIMAR](#) and [CIMA Research Foundation](#)), the [Municipality of Vila do Conde](#), [Counting Stars](#), and [Centro de Monitorização e Interpretação Ambiental](#) (CMIA). The event counted also with a vast support from national and local partners such as [Docapesca – Portos e Lotas, S.A.](#), [Águas do Norte](#) – Grupo Águas de Portugal, [FOCA](#) and [Unifardas SA](#).

We invite you to see [this video](#), kindly produced by the Municipality of Vila do Conde!

MAELSTROM contributes to the Traversing European Coastlines Expedition

We contributed to the [TREC Expedition](#) conducted by the [Fondation Tara Océan](#) and Tara Oceans Consortium through a dedicated session on marine litter and a beach cleanup for students.

Our partner [CIIMAR](#), together with the team from the [European Molecular Biology Laboratory](#), met at [CMIA](#) headquarters with students from local schools for an awareness session on marine litter impacts and a beach cleaning activity. Data collected was shared with the TREC researchers, contributing to a more detailed assessment of Vila do Conde coastal environment.

The TREC initiative consists of a European expedition to study coastal ecosystems and their response to the environment, from molecules to communities. It started in April 2023 and is expected to last until the end of June 2024. During that time, researchers will be gathering biological samples and environmental data along the European coastline at more than 120 land-sea transects.

Joint efforts in decentralized International Cooperation for Blue Economy

At the end of June, we [have joined forces](#) with projects [WINBLUE](#) (EMPFAP 2023–2025) and ISOSPAM (funded by [AICS](#) for Ecuador) to share know-how on the field of the blue economy and its impacts and opportunities to the development of local economies. When local communities are supported by the right know-how and by sustainable and inclusive approaches, positive benefits can arise from blue economy initiatives, while also reducing environmental pollution and preserving marine ecosystems.

MAELSTROM's partners [ISDI Ltd](#) and [VLPF](#), together with [Biochica Srl](#) of the WINBLUE project, organized gender-sensitive encounters with local entities and stakeholders – from Italy and Ecuador – from the educational, developmental and fishery sectors so to identify synergies among local needs and the proposed activities of each project.

PUBLICATIONS

A new method to monitor plastic concentration from the echo

Frans Buschman from our partner [Deltares](#) is among the authors of a [research paper](#) published on *Frontiers in Earth Science* in November. The work suggests a new, interesting approach to monitor plastics in rivers. Researchers have investigated the Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP), a tool already used for flow velocity studies, and demonstrated that the data obtained from the ADCP can be calibrated to obtain a correct estimate of the order of magnitude of plastic transportation in a river.

“In conclusion, this study tells us that the ADCP can be a valuable tool for estimating plastics transported in the water column of rivers. In particular, it has the advantage of being used for continuous and cross-sectional monitoring, helping us improve and determine the impact of current mitigation and cleaning efforts,” [says](#) Dr. Buschman.

WHERE HAVE WE BEEN?

- EUSAIR [Conference on the Protection of Waters and Seas from Plastics and Micro-plastics Pollution](#)
- [United Nations Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee on Plastic Pollution – Third Session](#)
- ECOMONDO 2023, workshop [Sustainable technologies for Marine litter removal and recycling: the experience of the H2O2O MAELSTROM project](#)
- [10th Atlantic Stakeholder Platform Conference](#)
- UNESCO Ocean Best Practices (OBPS) Workshop VII
- [Scienza in villa – Weekend edition 2023](#)
- [Portuguese Conference on Marine Litter and Microplastics, Circular Economy: Advancements and Solutions Panel](#)
- [Ciência Viva 2023 – Portuguese Science Summit](#)
- [2013 – 2023: 10 years of the Galway Statement](#)

WHAT'S NEXT?

Last but not least: follow us and don't miss our #MAELDrops and flash interviews!

Did you know that the risk of plastic exposure for seabirds is particularly high, according to the first global exposure assessment? Have you ever thought of plastic pollution has being a problem of environmental justice? Were you aware that the toxic effects of plastics on human health are still mostly unknown but research is moving forward on this field?

We have continued to explore these and other questions with our MAELDrops: you can find all of them [here!](#)

MAELSTROM's flash interviews are also on the rise: in the last months we have talked with our partners [CIIMAR](#), [The Great Bubble Barrier](#) and [Venice Lagoon Plastic Free](#) regarding their activities and inputs within the MAELSTROM project. More to come in 2024, keep being with us on that side!

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Newsletter #7

<https://us6.campaign-archive.com/?u=29f791f69e98ddd6bbc588e28&id=32a4074516>

July 2024

MAELSTROM Newsletter #7

Welcome to MAELSTROM's sixth newsletter! If you are new to MAELSTROM, note that it is an EU-funded project bringing together 14 partners from 8 European countries, designed to develop and test innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in coastal environments. Know more about the project [here!](#)

Hello MAELSTROM community! As we approach the conclusion of our four-year project, it's a moment to reflect on the many activities we have successfully completed and the achievements we can be proud of. While we near the end, there are still key tasks and goals to accomplish so keep following along with us, and in the meantime, enjoy the reading!

HOW IS IT GOING?

MAELSTROM receives the Sustainability Leadership Recognition in Robotics

While attending MAELSTROM's 7th Steering Committee and General Assembly in Malta (see below), we were pleasantly surprised by the Sustainability Leadership Recognition in Robotics, awarded by [euRobotics](#) during the [2024 European Robotics Forum](#).

Our partners [Tecnalia](#), [CNRS-LIRMM](#), and [Servizi Tecnici](#) were acknowledged for their outstanding efforts in creating MAELSTROM's [Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform](#), under the category Developing a Robot to Support Sustainability.

The Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform underwent successful testing in the Venice Lagoon, coordinated by [CNR-ISMAR](#), in both 2022 and 2023, with a public demonstration in the Gran Canal. During these tests, it managed to collect over 2 tons of waste, including tires, buoys, ropes, wrecks, and single use plastics. The Sustainability Leadership Recognition in Robotics comes just five months after [we received the Atlantic Award](#) in October 2023 in Porto, Portugal. More on MAELSTROM's Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform on [this video](#).

MAELSTROM 7th General Assembly and Steering Committee

On March 15th, the MAELSTROM team gathered in Malta for its 7th Steering Committee and General Assembly. We are grateful for the warm hospitality provided by the [The Malta Chamber](#), to whom we extend our deepest thanks. During the gathering, our team discussed the status of the project and laid out a comprehensive Plan of Action for the remaining months of project activities.

Beach clean-up at Gnejna Bay

On March 16th, in the occasion of our 7th General Assembly and Steering Committee Meeting, our consortium's partners [ISDI Group](#), [Venice Lagoon Plastic Free](#) and [Institute for Sustainable Energy – University of Malta](#), along with [Nature](#)

[Trust – FEE Malta](#), organized a [public beach clean-up and a beach litter monitoring session](#) at Gnejna Bay (Malta). The clean-up was an opportunity to use the latest version of the MAELSTROM App, developed by our partners [Gees Recycling srl](#) and Venice Lagoon Plastic Free, whose beach litter monitoring functionalities have been upgraded under the recently started EU [Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters](#) project [REMEDIES](#).

The event was the occasion to share the mission of Nature Trust Malta and MAELSTROM's goals and milestones under the EU Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters with the Maltese society. Alongside volunteers from the Nature Trust – FEE Malta and beachgoers who spontaneously joined us, we successfully gathered approximately 60kg of litter in just 1.5 hours. We wish to thank all the volunteers and those who enthusiastically joined us in this symbolic yet important action! Check [here](#) the video on the MAELSTROM App!

The 4th MAELSTROM Webinar

On March 20th, we had the 4th MAELSTROM webinar, titled One Ocean, One Health: Current Perspectives on Marine Litter in Ecosystem and Human Health, as part of the Atlantic & Arctic Lighthouse Weekly Hour.

The webinar, jointly organized with [BlueMissionAA](#) and our partner [CIIMAR](#) provided a platform to explore our current understanding of the impacts of marine litter, in particular plastic pollution, on both ecosystem and human health. It brought together leading academics from [CNR](#), [CIIMAR](#), [University of Plymouth](#), [Utrecht University](#), [ENAS](#)) to discuss novel research findings and developments in marine and human health research, and the innovative solutions that hold promise for a cleaner future.

PLASTIC FANTASTIC Hackathon

Our colleagues from [CIIMAR](#) and [Venice Lagoon Plastic Free](#) were among the experts and judges of the [PLASTIC FANTASTIC Hackathon](#), organized by the [REMEDIES](#) program, an international online Hackathon & acceleration program.

Starting in April 2024 with an international Bootcamp and Hackathon, the program will run until October 2024. During this period, environmental and business experts, water and environmental activists, and impact entrepreneurs will collaboratively work to further develop solutions for the detection, monitoring, collection, valorization, and prevention as well as the reuse of plastic litter. The four most impactful solutions will receive further support from a broad and diverse community of experts from [Impact Hub Athens](#).

4th International Workshop Marine Litter Monitoring, Removal and Circular Economy

Within the [Venice Boat Show 2024](#), the MAELSTROM team has co-organized, alongside the [Blue Mission Med](#), the Fourth International Workshop on [Marine Litter Monitoring, Removal, and Circular Economy](#). The event, held on May 30th, showcased and demonstrated selected transformative innovative solutions to tackle marine litter and microplastics pollution and was a partner event of the [European Green Week 2024](#).

Another aim of this event was to support the Mediterranean Sea Basin for the implementation of the EU [Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters](#) by fostering an innovation ecosystem and accelerating the implementation of solutions – technological, social, business, and governance – to swiftly advance towards the objectives of protecting and restoring the health of our ocean and waters. We would like to thank all the participants and speakers for their invaluable contributions and insights, and projects' representatives from [In-No-Plastic](#), [SEACLEAR 2.0](#), [Upstream](#), [REMEDIES](#), [Inspire](#) and [MarGnet](#).

The clean-up in Venice

The day after our International Workshop on Marine Litter Monitoring, Removal, and Circular Economy, as per MAELSTROM tradition, we co-organized a cleanup in Secca S. Alvise, in Venice. with our partners [Venice Lagoon Plastic Free](#) and [Gees Recycling srl](#).

This year's cleanup was a joint initiative that gathered three EU-funded projects working on marine litter and towards the EU [Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters](#): MAELSTROM, [REMEDIES](#), and [SEACLEAR 2.0](#).

The cleanup saw the collaboration of many volunteers from the [Poseidone OdV](#) and counted with the institutional support of local actors such as [Venice Boat Show](#), [Veritas](#), [Legambiente](#), and [WWF Italia Plastic Smart Cities](#). Around 3000 waste items were collected, mostly ceramics and plastics.

Sea it, art against marine litter

Sea it detail, by Francesca Busca

"Transforming the undesirable into desirable, shame into wonder, superfluous into essential to provoke real change." This is the aim of [Francesca Busca](#), an Italo-

English artist in residence at [CNR-ISMAR](#) and author of the [Art for Trash©](#) project and of the art exhibition *Sea it*, exposed at CNR-ISMAR headquarters for two weeks during the [Venice Boat Show 2024](#), held on May.

Sea it is a collaboration between Busca and the MAELSTROM project. The artist has used waste produced within CNR-ISMAR facilities, the [Acqua Alta platform](#), and the CNR's oceanographic vessel Gaia Blu. Through the concept of Eco-Artivism, Busca seeks to create links between marine environmental science and art, to promote social change. The public had the opportunity to witness the completion of Busca's work, an extraordinary site-specific installation.

MAELSTROM's scientific papers

Marine litter is a widely recognized problem, but it represents a complex topic that must be thoroughly understood to develop effective strategies to address it. A study authored by researchers from [CIIMAR](#) and [Deltares](#) investigated the characteristics of marine litter on the Portuguese coasts, linking this data with socio-economic variables of the Portuguese municipalities.

The work provided an updated and comprehensive framework that can support marine litter management strategies with a novel cluster technique that can be easily reproduced in other regions. We have written about it [here!](#)

Lead by CIIMAR, with the collaboration of MAELSTROM's partners from Deltares and [CNR-ISMAR](#), another study was published on Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science. Researchers analyzed the hydrodynamic patterns of the Ave River Estuary, through in situ measurement campaigns conducted between 2021 and 2023. The measurements revealed a highly stratified estuary with strong vertical salinity gradients and very low currents. The currents were mainly generated by tides and estuarine circulation during periods of low river flow and by river dominance during high river flows. Additionally, it was observed that coastal conditions, influenced by the plume of the nearby Douro Estuary, play a significant role in the circulation of the Ave Estuary. These results are essential for the implementation of new ecosystem-based management measures to contain plastic pollution and for effectively planning coastal management and risk assessment.

WHERE HAVE WE BEEN?

- Venice Sustainability Foundation, [Circular Venice: policy, practices, and innovation in comparison](#)
- European Commission, [European Ocean Days](#)
- Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters [Annual Forum](#)
- euRobotics, [European Robotics Forum](#) (ERF 2024)

- Faculty of Engineering, [Universidade do Porto](#), XIII Environmental Forum
- <https://www.ismar.cnr.it/Conference>
- [Virtual Early Career Ocean Professional \(VECOP\) Days](#)
- Veltha, [Loops webinar](#)
- [GEOHAB Annual Conference](#)
- UN Environment Programme, [International Negotiating Committee \(INC-4\)](#)
- [Workshop on EU-funded Marine Robotics and Applications \(EMRA 2024\)](#)
- Sustainable Blue economy Partnership, [Blue Economy – The key towards Mediterranean regional Sustainability](#) workshop

WHAT'S NEXT?

Our last six months will see us highly engaged in assessing the ecological impact and overall sustainability of The Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde and of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform (Venice). Furthermore, our team will be focused on the recycling processes of the collected marine litter, within a proper waste disposal chain following a circular economy approach.

Las but not least, the MAELSTROM team is committed to leave a legacy document regarding the challenges and the innovations put in place this amazing 4-year journey!

Last but not least: follow us and don't miss our #MAELDrops and flash interviews!

Did you know that scientists discovered enzymes able to degrade plastics? Can they really help us in the fight against plastic pollution? Discover it on our [last MAELDrop!](#)

Also, do not miss [MAELSTROM's Flash Interviews](#), in which our partners explain their work within our project.

Follow us on social media to be always updated on our MAELDrops and MAELSTROM's main milestones!

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Newsletter #8

ANNEX 4 – MAELSTROM FLASH INTERVIEWS

MAELSTROM's flash interviews #1 | Talking about robotics and sustainability with Damien Sallé (Tecnalia)

March 9, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstroms-flash-interviews-1-talking-about-robotics-and-sustainability-with-damien-salle-tecnalia/>

Robotics is increasingly a part of scientific research in many fields. While it can be a concrete and valuable support for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals of the Agenda 2030, it also raises questions about its own sustainability: just think about the production of the necessary materials and their management.

These issues were recently discussed at the *What does it take for a robot to be sustainable?* conference organized by AI for Good, which was addressed by Damien Sallé, Coordinator of Robotics & Automation at our partner Tecnalia and one of the creators of our Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform. We therefore inaugurate with him our series of flash interviews, brief insights into the different issues we are facing in our MAELSTROM project!

Robotics and artificial intelligence are gathering enormous research efforts and appear to be increasingly important for our future. How can robotics and AI help us to achieve sustainable development models?

Indeed, robotics and AI are important technologies. They are used in more applications and sectors every day, not only in the manufacturing plants, but also in agriculture, health, construction, energy, logistics, inspection and maintenance and many more. In Tecalia, for the past years, we are also developing a new line of applications targeting Environmental Sustainability and in particular the Circular Economy, because we also want to contribute to the fight against climate change. Robotics in this sector can help a lot to bring efficiency but also ensure quality, traceability and thus trust, which is a main barrier for a wider deployment of remanufactured or refurbished products.

We can see applications of robots in 4 main sectors:

- Removing the waste from the environment, like we do for the seabed marine litter in MAELSTROM
- Inspection and repair of equipment, using robots with vision to detect the defaults and additive manufacturing to repair them (works for plastics, metals or concrete components)
- Dismantling, disassembling and remanufacturing of equipment, to allow the re-use of some components or to remove as much pure material as possible before shredding and recycling. For example, we do that for electric car batteries or motors.
- Sorting the waste to increase the purity of the recycling processes, using robots with multispectral cameras and AI for example. It is already used in urban waste plants, and we develop solutions to expand it to construction waste, textile, batteries, RAEE etc.

Is there, conversely, any aspect of possible unsustainability coming from robotics and AI based technologies?

Well, robots are complex mechatronic machines. Therefore, they incorporate lots of metal, plastics, electronics, but also complex motors and gearboxes, complex sensors and many computers. More and more the AI runs not only on the robot embedded computer (edge) but also in the Cloud in powerful servers hosted in datacenters and communicating with the robot through internet. Most of the time they are electric machines, so mobile robots also need batteries. In some rare occasions where a very large autonomy is needed, they can be powered by a gasoline generator. So yes, these machines have an environmental impact that is negative to build and operate them. Just like any other machine, I would say.

What can be done to prevent future robotic and AI technologies from reinforcing or creating “new” problems?

Everything in life is about balance... so technology itself is neither positive nor negative. It's how and why we use it that counts! Sustainability has three domains: economic, social and environmental. In almost all cases, robots bring economic sustainability not only for the companies but also for the territories where they are deployed, because they allow a better competitive offer and allow maintaining a strong industrial ecosystem. They can also have an impact on the social domain when they are used to assist people with special needs in the workplace or help in ageing care for example. For environmental sustainability, we've already discussed some examples. Of course, selling useless robots for kids or geeks that end-up unused after a few days because they don't provide any real value, that is a very bad use of our

resources and quota of CO₂... But it is absolutely not restricted to robots and apply to all our electronic devices, cars, fashion and so on.

If we focus on the environmental impact, and this is a personal opinion, in order to minimize the impact of the climate change on the ecosystems and biodiversity (reducing CO₂ emissions) I don't see other options than adopting sobriety practices which basically requires to do less. It means moving from a "consume-as-much-as-we-can" way of life to a "consume-wisely-and-only-when-needed" philosophy... Then we can work on optimizing the use of our quota of CO₂ to Do better the products, the technologies, etc.

Given these premises, then, how can we minimize the environmental impact of robots?

Well, manufacturers could keep working on improving the intrinsic properties of robots, by using only recycled/recyclable materials, by optimizing their energy consumption, by optimizing their programming taking into account also energy parameters and so on. But more critically: starting by using them only for things that are really worth the extra environmental cost! And for this, you enter in the evaluation of the sustainability balance, having to compare impacts of different natures: how can we decide if it is sustainable or not a robot such as our in MAELSTROM, that requires CO₂ and materials for its manufacturing and operation, but have a positive impact on the environment because it removes pollutants? Well, there is a tool called Lifecycle Analysis (LCA) that lists all these positive and negative impacts throughout the whole lifecycle of the system, from its design to its recycling. It's not easy nor perfect, but it is good indicator. I really encourage you to start using these tools to make informed decisions!

MAELSTROM's flash interviews #2 | Tackling litter in Venice Lagoon: Q&A with Fantina Madricardo

May 2, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/tackling-litter-in-venice-lagoon-qa-with-fantina-madricardo/>

In June, the MAELSTROM project will inaugurate its Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in Venice, an innovative technology designed to recover litter from the seabed (or lagoon-bed!) without damaging the ecosystems in which it operates.

The context in which we tested and where we will inaugurate the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform is not trivial. The Venice Lagoon, in fact, is not only the largest lagoon in the Mediterranean but also gathers interests of different order, from naturalistic and ecological to economic and historical. What was it like, then, to set up the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in this specific context? We discuss this issue with Fantina Madricardo (CNR-ISMAR), coordinator of MAELSTROM.

Operating in the Venice Lagoon, even more with an ecologically friendly but sizeable and yet to be tested facility such as the Robotic Seabed Cleaning

Platform, is certainly not a simple process. What main factors did you have to consider?

First of all, it was necessary to identify the area both in the lagoon and at sea where the technology needed to be implemented to clean the environment, then we carried out a constant dialog with the local authorities in order to obtain their support and the needed permits to operate in the designated areas.

Much of the initial phases of MAELSTROM were devoted to studying the environment in which the technologies would work. In Venice, in particular, CNR-ISMAR carried out thorough litter assessment and mapping work: can you tell us the main results?

CNR-ISMAR started documented the presence of litter though high-resolution seafloor mapping, starting from a general survey carried out in 2013 of all the navigation channels of the lagoon, with specific repeated surveys in marine litter accumulation areas inside the Venice lagoon, close to the city of Venice. In the open sea, we mapped an abandoned aquaculture farm that will be the test site for the seabed cleaning platform at sea, following the indication and in full collaboration with the Venice Coast Guard. We found very high concentrations of litter in terms of number of items per sqkm, more in the lagoon than at sea. In the lagoon, we found mainly wrecks, tires, waste bags and litter related to the city, whereas at sea, we found mainly abandoned plastic ropes, nets and buoys related to fishing and aquaculture. To map the litter on the seafloor we used mainly high-resolution sonar (multibeam echosounder) and videos.

To conclude: did the preliminary investigations conducted prior to the installation of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform reveal any insights for future studies, or that made you think of other possible strategies to protect the Lagoon from litter?

Certainly, the maps of the litter distribution raise awareness in both citizen and local stakeholders about the presence of litter (otherwise invisible in the turbid waters) and the necessity to have a common strategy to clean the legacy of litter accumulated in the last decades in the Venice Lagoon.

MAELSTROM's flash interviews #3 | Marine litter and clean up activities with citizens. A Q&A with Davide Poletto (VLPF)

July 13, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstroms-flash-interviews-3-marine-litter-and-clean-up-activities-with-citizens-a-qa-with-davide-poletto-vlpf/>

We are all part of this planet, and we can and should all know and care for it. Even European policies now recognize the crucial role of citizen involvement when it comes to environmental issues and sustainable development: as members of society, consumers, voters... in every dimension of us, each one of us can play a relevant role in making change happen.

This also applies when it comes to marine litter and at MAELSTROM, we are convinced of the importance of raising awareness among civil society, seeing it as an active participant in the challenge of protecting the seas and oceans. For this reason, our project has foreseen regular info days and clean ups in Italy and Portugal (our pilot areas where our technologies will be implemented) which represent moments of dialog and interaction among science and society: our events are based on marine

literacy, data sharing, ocean education and, above all, participation! In Italy, clean ups take place in Venice, home of our coordinator CNR-ISMAR, and are organized by our partner Venice Lagoon Plastic Free (VLPF), in collaboration with various entities. We held one just recently, in June, which resulted in the collection of over 1,300 kilograms of waste in just one morning.

For our series of flash interviews, today we will delve into the topic of citizen participation and involvement and its importance on addressing environmental conservation challenges with Davide Poletto, director of VLPF.

When did Venice Lagoon Plastic Free start operating, and how did the idea come about?

Venice Lagoon Plastic Free (VLPF) was formally set out in the Spring of 2019. However, relevant board members were already active and engaged as practitioners and scientists in a broad array of sustainable development programs and projects. The idea came across after having engaged and mobilized multiple times local and international civil society organizations and citizens in marine litter clean up and monitoring sessions, also in cooperation with UNESCO. I am now the current director; I spent over one decade serving UNESCO in international scientific cooperation for sustainable development projects and programs. The idea of putting our activities in the world heritage site of “Venice and its lagoon” as a testing ground with a local and a global vision under a common roof was shared with colleagues and friends, who enthusiastically picked it up. VLPF was therefore set out and has made a good name herself. Since then, besides MAELSTROM, VLPF has been active in strategic lighthouse projects to *Restore our Ocean and waters* mission under the EU and in other independent and pioneer initiatives based on private donations and crowdfunding strategies such as the “Ghost Boat” program.

What is, in your opinion, the most important outcome of getting citizens involved in these types of activities (clean-ups)?

Clean-up and marine litter monitoring activities have several positive behavioral spillover effects by increasing awareness about the state of pollution of our shorelines and the level of dispersion of plastics in nature seas and waters. They can also contribute to providing helpful information to the local government and to the EU scientific database and network to fine-tune their marine litter prevention and remediation policies. Clean-up and marine litter monitoring activities bound us with our nature and biosphere, unleash and coalesce new energies to fight plastics pollution and advance towards the building of a new sustainable blue circular economy capable of operating with amending hands on this scourge, turning marine and waters wastes into new resources for our economies and services.

Observing how young generations are increasingly active about climate change, how would you classify the engagement of young generations in Venice regarding plastic pollution?

With a population below the threshold of 50.000 inhabitants in the historical city center in a downtrend and an average age of about 50 years in an uptrend, Venice is a

town facing social and demographic decay and impoverishment of its social tissue. We have a few organizations of youngsters active in the historical center on the matter. Still, because of the shrinking and ageing population, they suffer from representativeness and poorness in social extraction and diversity. Transient populations, particularly students, are active and on the global wave of climate change protests and awareness campaigns are sensitive on the matter, advocating for more courageous and drastic changes in our economic development patterns locally and internationally. The number of associations and their activities in general is high, although sometimes too fragmented and conflicting.

What do you think could be improved in these kinds of actions? Are there aspects that could be enhanced, with the appropriate resources?

We believe that the town should be more courageous in carrying out the best course of action for sustainability. After the COVID-19 lockdown, we still see the pollution of our lagoon and shorelines rising up dramatically, as also underlined by our beach litter and water microcontaminants monitoring analysis. Public boats and private transport services for the public (taxis etc.) are still running on diesel fuel. The bottom of our lagoon is disseminated of tires of scrapped cars that are improperly used by transport boats as fenders. Thousands of them have piled up, increasing in number each day. The MAELSTROM seabed cleaning platform can represent a way to reduce such downstream pollution, but the solution is normative. Fiberglass boats are scattered and left like ghosts in our lagoon. The ghost boats issue is an unsolved and escalating problem since proper disposal of small old boats and vessels unfit for navigation is unaddressed financially and regulatory. We need to create an economical chain capable of removing and segregating valuable materials – inox, aluminum, etc., and the final treatment of fiberglass, varnished woods, etc., through advanced recycling processes, free of charge for the citizens. Venice is part of the WWF Plastic Smart Cities initiative and has approved its implementation plan recently. We hope the above issues and many others that would be too long to mention will find an appropriate response in a reasonably short time span. Research institutes and NGOs cannot replace law and decision-makers. We can “only” inspire, catalyze, show new patterns and advocate for changes on scientific grounds and evidence.

MAELSTROM's flash interviews #4 | Discover the Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde

November 29, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstroms-flash-interviews-4-discover-the-bubble-barrier-vila-do-conde/>

Image credit: [The Great Bubble Barrier](#)

On Saturday, November 25th, in Vila do Conde, Portugal, the launch event of our Bubble Barrier took place: an innovative technology for removing waste from rivers to prevent its entry into the sea and, consequently, accumulation in the oceans. This was a crucial moment for our project (there are many [photographic testimonials](#) on our social channels!), following the implementation of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform [launched in June 2023 in Venice](#). For its success, we truly must thank all the participants, and especially the [Vila do Conde Municipality](#) for their availability and for demonstrating so much proactivity in combating the problem of marine ecosystem pollution.

The Bubble Barrier system is designed not to disrupt fish or maritime traffic. It is co-powered by solar panels, designed and produced by the MAELSTROM partner Institute for Sustainable Energy of the University of Malta, to ensure renewable energy. Furthermore, to ensure its sustainability, CIIMAR, another partner of our project, conducted various environmental assessments.

The Bubble Barrier was developed by our Dutch partner, The Great Bubble Barrier, so we ask them, for our *MAELSTROM's Flash Interviews*, to tell us how it works and explain some details!

What gave rise to the idea of a bubble barrier to stop litter in rivers? What was the inspiration for the development of this technology?

Three of the co-founders, Anne Marieke Eveleens, Francis Zoet and Saskia Studer, are lifelong sailors and friends who constantly came across plastic at sea on their sailing trips. When they were having a beer after one of their trips, they started mulling over ways to tackle plastic pollution. They dreamt of a solution that would target plastic but wouldn't hinder ship traffic or fish migration. The bubbles in their drinks eventually sparked their imagination, their concept and prototype were awarded and soon they started testing and developing their first prototypes further.

At the same time, Philip Ehrhorn was developing his own Bubble Barrier in Germany. During a course in Environmental Engineering, he visited a wastewater treatment plant where he saw bubbles being used to aerate the water basin. The plastics that were flushed down the toilet, were pushed to the side of the basin. So, he wondered: 'Why can't we use the power of bubbles to capture plastic in rivers?' Eventually, the four of them met. They decided to join forces and together, they co-founded The Great Bubble Barrier.

How long will the barrier be maintained in the Ave River?

The Bubble Barrier system in Vila do Conde will be operational from the end of 2023. The team of engineers from The Great Bubble Barrier are responsible for adjusting the system so that it is optimally calibrated for the highest plastic catch possible.

The Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde is the first project in an estuary. The results of the pilot will be evaluated after 1 year of operation. With this project, we aim to realise a standard design for more estuaries in the future.

The Bubble Barrier in Vila do Conde will be operational until at least the end of 2024, since the MAELSTROM project is executed within a limited time frame and aims to research long-term solutions, backed by research findings. The project focuses on research, which allows for 1 year of implementation, running and monitoring of the Bubble Barrier technology in this specific location.

The ultimate goal will always be to continuously capture and prevent marine litter, thus extending the Bubble Barrier project for a longer period of time in the Ave River.

The Municipality will receive a report made by an independent auditor on the impact of the Bubble Barrier. If it is positive, the system will most likely remain in the water.

Of course, the Bubble Barrier is not the only possible tool to fight plastic pollution. Acting in synergy, various existing and/or developing technologies, including the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform developed within MAELSTROM, can help. What specific characteristics might make the Bubble Barrier particularly suitable for a particular location? In other words, what characteristics of the river enable it to be successfully implemented?

The benefits of a Bubble Barrier are as follows:

- It covers the full width and depth of the river
- Ships can pass without obstruction
- It doesn't hinder the passage of fish or marine life
- The system can be operational 24/7

In addition, our Bubble Barrier system has been proven to catch 86% of debris –items ranging from 1mm to 1m in size.

Can you tell us something about the future prospects of your work? Is it possible (as well as desirable), for example, for the barrier to be implemented in other areas of the world?

The Great Bubble Barrier would like to see our Bubble Barrier technology implemented across the world. In the short term, we hope to implement more Bubble Barrier projects in Europe, and in the long term, we hope to implement projects in Asia and other continents across the globe.

MAELSTROM's flash interviews #5 | The environmental assessment of Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde: Q&A with Luis Vieira (CIIMAR)

December 7, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstroms-flash-interviews-5-maelstroms-flash-interviews-5-the-environmental-assessment-of-bubble-barrier-vila-do-conde-qa-with-luis-viera-ciimar/>

We have talked extensively about the recently implemented Bubble Barrier in Vila do Conde ([here](#) you can find our recent interview with the team from our partner, The Great Bubble Barrier, who developed it). However, the implementation of the system is only one part of the activities planned in our project: MAELSTROM aims to ensure the sustainability of its technologies, and thus, the project includes a thorough environmental assessment of their impact.

We discuss this with Luis Vieira from CIIMAR, the MAELSTROM partner responsible for the environmental assessment of the Bubble Barrier in the Ave River estuary.

What kind of environmental assessment will CIIMAR perform on the Bubble Barrier recently installed in the Ave River? What major elements will you focus on?

The CIIMAR team will be responsible for the environmental assessment of the Bubble Barrier on the Ave estuary. Conducting a thorough ecological assessment provides a comprehensive understanding of the estuarine ecosystem, its dynamics, and the potential impacts of litter, providing a foundation of knowledge essential for the effective implementation of a marine litter removal technology, also maximizing positive impacts and its efficiency. Several parameters were evaluated before the implementation of the Bubble Barrier. Macro-litter was quantified through visual monitoring during the ecosystem state assessment, whereas microplastic particles were evaluated in the water column. The presence of this debris was also co-monitored in key organisms, for example, zooplankton. The water quality and the ecosystem's ecological status were determined through standardized metrics, including the characterization of physical and chemical parameters, and analysis of biological and hydro-morphological elements.

With the Bubble Barrier now installed in the Ave estuary, this methodology will be replicated during the next months to evaluate its efficiency and impacts. CIIMAR team developed for the first time a hydrodynamic model for the Ave estuary. This model not only supports the technology implementation but will be also crucial to anticipate future scenarios and evaluate the Bubble Barrier efficiency.

Why it is important to develop this monitoring work in estuarine areas? Why implement a marine litter removal technology in an estuary?

Rivers act as pipelines to the ocean, channelling the waste that is dumped into their waters and conducted to the estuaries and, finally, to the oceans. Thus, acquired data on the estuarine ecosystems can contribute to a better understanding of the entry of litter into the ocean from terrestrial sources. Estuaries support a complex web of life, including a diverse range of aquatic species. Marine litter can pose a threat to this biodiversity through entanglement, ingestion, and habitat degradation. To increase the knowledge on the contamination impacts on wild populations by both anthropogenic macrolitter and microplastics, more biomonitoring studies on those areas are still and urgently needed to support appropriate management measures. In addition, these field works are being considered crucial in the scope of national and international regulations.

Addressing marine litter in estuaries is essential for preserving the ecological integrity, economic functions, and cultural significance of these critical coastal ecosystems. Implementing removal technologies in these areas represents a proactive and targeted approach to mitigating the impacts of marine litter at the source, contributing to the overall health and sustainability of estuarine environments. It also provides an opportunity for community engagement and education. Local communities often have a vested interest in the health of estuarine ecosystems, and involvement in litter removal initiatives can raise awareness and foster a sense of environmental stewardship.

You also work a lot on stakeholder and citizen engagement: can you explain the importance of these actions?

No matter how innovative these technological solutions are, the mission to tackle marine litter will only be successful if we involve all sectors of society in a joint effort to change.

The CIIMAR team has been responsible for facilitating the involvement of local stakeholders in the co-design and implementation of the Bubble Barrier in Vila do Conde. Starting with the inspiring work with the municipality of Vila do Conde, which has taken a proactive approach to tackling marine litter by partnering with the MAELSTROM team to co-design and implement a Bubble Barrier in the Ave River. This technology was developed by The Great Bubble Barrier, and it is co-powered through solar panels installed by the Institute for Sustainable Energy of the University of Malta.

We also coordinated the involvement of local, regional and national stakeholders such as Docapesca Portos e Lotas, S.A., the Portuguese Environmental Agency as well as the Vila do Conde Port Captaincy and the Vila do Conde – Environmental Monitoring and Interpretation Centre (CMIA), which were extremely important for the design and implementation of the system.

CIIMAR had also an important role in stakeholder engagement at both national and international levels. The team will continue to be committed to contributing to awareness-raising efforts through strategic networking at national, European and global levels, Science-Policy-Society interface activities and tools for citizen science. We developed an online interactive forum to encourage interactive thematic discussions. CIIMAR team also organized several international workshops, webinars and other online and presential events to inspire science and society to tackle marine litter.

We are proud of MAELSTROM's international dimension and recognition, with a particular emphasis on collaborative transdisciplinary actions that link science, industry and policy. Recently, the project was highlighted as an example by the European Commission, which awarded MAELSTROM the Atlantic Project Award in the Healthy Oceans and Resilient Coasts category.

Do engagement activities continue following the installation of the Bubble Barrier?

Citizen engagement initiatives have been crucial in mobilizing society to take proactive steps, raise awareness, contribute to data collection, influence policy, and foster a sense of shared responsibility for the health of the oceans. These initiatives followed the main MAELSTROM pillars, counting on vast support from national and local partners.

We believe that the first marine litter removal technology implemented in Portugal will inspire and mobilize society in the course of action for marine litter prevention and remediation policies, towards an effective and sustainable blue circular economy.

During the previous events, many of our participants asked for other initiatives, our team is already discussing the next project info days, capacity-building sessions on MAELSTROM's technologies, and out-of-the-box cleanups. These will be key moments for awareness promotion on marine litter causes and impacts, promotion of good practices, and responsible choices and behaviours for a truly sustainable society.

MAELSTROM's Flash interviews #6 | Pioneering sustainable energy solutions: Q&A with the Institute for Sustainable Energy-University of Malta

January 25th, 2024

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/pioneering-sustainable-energy-solutions-qa-with-the-institute-for-sustainable-energy-university-of-malta/>

In the pursuit of safeguarding our planet's oceans and addressing the pressing issue of marine pollution, MAELSTROM brings together research institutions dedicated to the development of cutting-edge solutions that not only clean our waterways but also harness renewable energy to power these eco-friendly technologies.

One such institution at the forefront of this initiative is our partner, the Institute for Sustainable Energy of the University of Malta. The core mission of their researchers revolves around facilitating the formulation of national energy strategies by conducting extensive research into new and renewable energy sources. They also focus on energy conservation methods and the adaptation of equipment tailored to local conditions.

Join us as we delve deeper into their role within the MAELSTROM project, exploring the fusion of marine environment conservation and sustainable energy solutions.

To introduce yourselves: what are the main activities carried out by the Institute for Sustainable Energy?

At our Institute, we aim to assist in the development of national energy plans through studies in the use of new and renewable energy sources and methods of energy conservation.

We organize and participate in teaching programmes and research projects in the field of energy technology. Our other objectives include disseminating appropriate methods and techniques relevant to our areas of interest and to design equipment adapted to local conditions. This is carried out mainly by:

- analysis studies on the use of energy
- determination of feasible measures to conserve energy
- applications of renewable sources of energy
- originating and participating in teaching and research projects
- collaborating with other universities, industries, and international bodies

How have they integrated into the MAELSTROM project? What are the key features of the panels designed for the Bubble Barrier?

For the MAELSTROM project, our main goal is to provide enough renewable energy to the compressor of the Bubble Barrier to cover at least 10% of its electricity requirements, while also showcasing the potential of installing floating solar panels together with the cleaning technology. We started by assessing the electricity requirements of the Bubble Barrier to determine the most feasible solution for the installation. After identifying the best locations, we designed a system that would provide the most electricity to the Bubble Barrier, while making sure the installation is safe and does not act as an eyesore to the public.

What were the main elements you had to consider in their design?

The main element we had to consider was 'How much space is available'. After being provided with a rooftop and an area on a floating dock that could be used to install solar panels, we had to design a system that maximized electricity generation. We had to decide between installing the solar panels in a south-facing direction, which would maximize their efficiency, or installing more panels by using an east-west orientation with a lower efficiency. After calculating the amount of electricity that can be generated in a year by both systems, the decision was made to install a larger 36.3 kWp east-west oriented photovoltaic system on the rooftop of the CMIA building in Vila do Conde and a 4.4 kWp system on the floating dock installed on the Ave river, near the catchment system of the Bubble Barrier.

What will be your main activities within MAELSTROM during this final year of the project?

During the final year of MAELSTROM, our main goal is to assess the environmental impact of the technologies installed in Vila do Conde, together with our partners from The Great Bubble Barrier. We will conduct a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for both the Bubble Barrier technology and the solar panels. We will also assess the environmental impact of the Bubble Barrier operating both with and without the solar panels. We will also remain available to the Municipality in Vila do Conde for any assistance they require with the solar panel installations, as well as any maintenance or repairs that need to be done during the year.

MAELSTROM Flash Interview #7 | Sustainability and innovation: Q&A with ISDI

February 20th, 2024

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstrom-flash-interview-7-sustainability-and-innovation-qa-with-isdi/>

MAELSTROM's partner ISDI Group is a consultancy company based in Malta that provides a wide range of professional services in the Mediterranean basin and overseas. Through a multifaceted approach encompassing collaboration with international consortia, consultancy services for private enterprises, and active participation in EU-funded projects, ISDI Group has carved a niche for itself in driving environmental sustainability, gender equality, and educational advancement in specialized tourism.

In this final year of our project, ISDI activities focus on advancing sustainable marine litter management practices. Through collaborations with innovative startups and academic institutions, ISDI aims to develop cutting-edge

biomaterial prototypes while spearheading clean-up initiatives to bolster community engagement and academic partnerships.

In this MAELSTROM's Flash Interview, we delve into ISDI's founding principles, its pivotal role within MAELSTROM, innovative approaches to recycling marine litter, and its strategic focus for the project's final year.

When was ISDI Group founded and what does it specialize in?

Founded in 2017 by a diverse team of partners, ISDI Group has become a pivotal force in sustainable global solutions, engaging with international consortia on EU-funded projects and offering consultancy to private companies on sustainability. Apart from MAELSTROM, ISDI Group actively contributes to the [WINBLUE project](#), focusing on empowering women in the business and research sectors and the [GEOTOURS GUIDES project](#). The latter aims to enhance the competencies of tour guides and travel agencies in geotourism, developing a unique training package to build geotourism brands and promote thematic tourism in the region. These projects underscore ISDI Group's dedication to environmental sustainability, gender equality, and educational advancement in specialized tourism, illustrating their broad impact across diverse sectors.

What have been your activities so far in the context of MAELSTROM?

Within the MAELSTROM project, the ISDI Group, in partnership with various stakeholders, has played a crucial role, notably co-organizing international workshops at the Venice Boat Show and actively participating in marine clean-up and monitoring initiatives. A key contribution from ISDI has been to the development and field testing of the MAELSTROM APP before its launch. Moreover, ISDI has been instrumental in advancing innovative circular economy solutions, implemented in later project phases. This holistic approach exemplifies ISDI's commitment to environmental sustainability, emphasizing the value of collaborative work in promoting circular economy practices and marine conservation.

How do you work on recycling, or in other words, what 'new life' do you offer to the recovered plastic?

ISDI Group, in strategic partnership with [VLPE](#) and [GEES](#), has taken a significant step towards repurposing marine litter by focusing on its potential to be transformed into valuable resources. This initiative involves a meticulous process of identifying and collecting data on possible applications for marine litter, with a special emphasis on blending it with other organic compounds currently classified as marine waste. This innovative approach aims to develop new, sustainable biomaterials through careful mixing, resulting in products that are both environmentally friendly and low impact. These materials are primarily targeted at the burgeoning fields of bio-construction and bio-architecture, representing a novel and sustainable application of recycled marine waste. By pioneering these

efforts, ISDI Group demonstrates a profound commitment to environmental sustainability, pushing the boundaries of traditional recycling to embrace circular economy principles and contribute to the development of green building solutions.

What will you focus on in this final year of the project?

In this final project year, ISDI Group is deepening its commitment to sustainable marine waste management by fostering systematic collaborations with innovative startups like Biochica, which specializes in the valorization of aquatic and marine ecosystem waste. This collaboration aims to develop a sustainable biomaterial prototype for green design and architecture, utilizing chitosan/chitin-based compounds from local Blue Crab. ISDI, alongside GEES, VLPF, and Biochica, will focus on blending marine litter with these bio-based compounds, enhancing the project's environmental impact.

Furthermore, the upcoming project meeting organized by ISDI in collaboration with the University of Malta and local NGOs, scheduled for March in Malta, will include a significant clean-up initiative. This effort not only showcases ISDI's dedication to practical environmental action but also strengthens community engagement and academic partnerships, reinforcing the project's holistic approach to sustainable development and marine conservation.

MAELSTROM's Flash Interview #8 | Forging Paths to Resilient Water Systems: Q&A with Deltares

April 2nd, 2024

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstroms-flash-interview-8-forging-paths-to-resilient-water-systems-qa-with-deltares/>

With a steadfast commitment to sustainability, MAELSTROM's partner Deltares strives to enhance the management and utilization of water resources, ensuring their security, quality, and quantity for both present and future generations. Embracing the challenge of climate resilience, Deltares envisions water systems that are not only ecologically and chemically healthy but also managed in a sustainable manner, fostering a legacy of thriving water ecosystems for all.

For our Flash Interview #8, we delve into Deltares' core objectives, its significant contributions within MAELSTROM, and its strategic plans for the project's final phase. Let us explore Deltares' journey, its pivotal role within MAELSTROM, and its vision for a future where water resources are safeguarded for the benefit of all.

Deltares is an institute involved in a wide range of activities; what is the main common thread that ties them together?

We work on innovative solutions in the field of water and our motto is: *Enabling Delta life*. One central topic is to contribute to more sustainable management and use of water resources, resulting in a secure quality and quantity of water resources for nature and people. We strive to achieve climate-resilient water systems that are ecologically and chemically healthy and managed sustainably so future generations will be able to use and enjoy them.

What kind of studies have you conducted as part of MAELSTROM, and how have they been applied in the project?

We evaluated the Bubble Barrier in Amsterdam and, together with The Great Bubble Barrier and other partners, assessed the possible locations and the design of the Portuguese pilot. With CIIMAR we worked out field observations to understand the flow in the Ave estuary. Since no data on river discharge are available, we set up and verified a hydrological model to obtain discharge estimations. We also helped develop a numerical model of the estuary, set up by CIIMAR. In addition to these, we looked at the likely sources of the types of plastic that occur in the environment in the two project areas.

Deltares has also contributed to the implementation of the Bubble Barrier in Portugal. Can you tell us more about it?

We helped coordinate the whole process of implementation of the Bubble Barrier pilot in Portugal, which was very complex – not only because of the environmental characteristics but because it falls under the governance of many different institutions. It was a long and complicated journey of engaging and articulating key authorities and obtaining the necessary permits. But once they realized the value of this pilot, they embraced the idea and the launch event was a success.

What are your planned activities for the final year of the project?

In this last but important stage of MAELSTROM, we will help assess the performance of the Bubble Barrier, now that it is in active operation. How does it work in different river discharge conditions, what proportion and type of debris does it collect and what is the impact on the estuary and surrounding area? This will provide evidence on whether is worth investing in these technologies and how these can be used to monitor the litter that ends up in rivers and would, otherwise, end up in the sea.

MAELSTROM's Flash Interview #9 | Transforming marine litter through pyrolysis: Q&A with MAKEEN

October 8th, 2024

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstroms-flash-interview-8-transforming-marine-litter-through-pyrolysis-qa-with-makeen/>

We continue our interviews with the partners of the MAELSTROM project to hear directly from them about their roles and the activities they are carrying out within the project. By leveraging their expertise in pyrolysis, MAKEEN is helping to convert plastic litter collected from European coasts into valuable resources.

In this interview with Lillian Christensen from MAKEEN, we explore its contributions to the project, focusing on their efforts to transform challenging waste streams into sustainable business opportunities, thereby supporting global efforts to reduce ocean pollution.

What is MAKEEN's role in the MAELSTROM project?

MAKEEN is a technology and equipment provider within pyrolysis, a process where materials, like plastic, are heated in the absence of oxygen, causing them to break down into simpler substances, such as gases, oils, and solid residues.

This process transforms the original material into useful products like pyrolysis oil – a raw material for making new items.

MAKEEN was therefore in MAELSTROM requested to perform pyrolysis on marine litter submitted from other partners, collected thanks to the implemented technologies and clean up activities, and presorted in the project. Moreover, MAKEEN had to assess the output materials from the pyrolysis process and consider business opportunities.

What does chemical recycling involve? Can it be done with any type of plastic?

Performing pyrolysis you process the plastic in an inert atmosphere and heat the material to a process where it goes to a gaseous form to decompose the material. At MAKEEN we condensate the material into a pyrolysis oil to be supplied to the petro-chemical industry and to be used in production of new plastic.

Pyrolysis can be performed on a variety of materials including plastics as the reactor, processing, and process parameters can be designed for the specific material or material mix for the setup to handle. Pyrolysis requires energy so therefore pyrolysis should only be applied when you as output will have useful, good quality materials. And since the output material quality and quantity is dependent of the input material composition and the process applied, not all plastic materials are suitable for pyrolysis. Some plastic types like PET and PVC (among the most widely used plastics, for example, in beverage bottles and various other products and construction materials, respectively), will give only a small yield and also tend to clog in the system and/or give out-of-spec pyrolysis oil and are therefore not preferable for the production of high-quality pyrolysis oil. Luckily, mechanical recycling of PET is already well implemented in many countries.

What will your main activities be in the final months of the project?

This final period of work will see MAKEEN engaged in finalizing the market assessment of the products from marine litter. All the results will be presented at the end of the project.

MAELSTROM Flash Interview #10 | Revitalizing marine litter: GEES' innovative recycling journey

October 31st, 2024

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstrom-flash-interview-9-revitalizing-marine-litter-gees-innovative-recycling-journey/>

We're excited to bring you a new addition to MAELSTROM's Flash Interviews series, diving deeper into the groundbreaking work of our partners. Today, we talk with Giorgio Betteto from our partner GEES which, within MAELSTROM, has the role of transforming recovered marine litter into new, valuable resources. Through innovative mechanical recycling and agglomeration, GEES is addressing a crucial environmental challenge by giving a second life to marine litter and abandoned boats, waste that typically cannot be recycled with conventional technologies.

In this interview, we delve into how GEES leverages its specialized processes to recycle materials that are notoriously hard to repurpose, such as multi-polymer fishing nets, floats, and aquaculture equipment. With their expertise, GEES also drives MAELSTROM efforts to enhance transparency and traceability in recycling through the MAELSTROM App and Portal, tools designed to

accurately identify and record waste components, supporting both operational insights and resource optimization. Join us as we explore the motivations, challenges, and successes of this innovative project with our Venice-based partner, GEES, whose work is reshaping our approach to marine waste and sustainable recycling.

What is GEES' role in the project, and how did the idea for the App come about?

Gees is responsible for transforming marine litter and abandoned boats—waste materials that cannot be recycled through traditional technologies—into new materials using our mechanical recycling/agglomeration process. The App and Portal were born from our experience in waste recycling operations, where identifying and documenting waste components is essential, even if only to understand what materials are being processed and what can be produced.

Gees also plays an important role in recycling. How does your process work? which materials are you able to recycle, and in what quantities?

We have processed several thousand kilograms of materials such as multi-polymer fishing nets, floats, aquaculture equipment, and abandoned boats. After separating out wood and metals (which are outside of our recycling authorization), the remaining materials are fully utilized in the production of panels. These panels come in two versions: “Magnum XL,” where the original components remain visible and identifiable due to the large particles, and “Maelstrom D’eco,” where further particle reduction allows for custom coloring and a refined appearance according to our standards.

What will your activities focus on during these final weeks of the project?

We aim to focus on promoting and commercially disseminating the products we’ve created, as they are extremely interesting, high-quality, and competitive.

MAELSTROM's Flash Interview #11 | Innovation goes hand in hand with sustainability

November 12th, 2024

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstroms-flash-interview-10-innovation-goes-hand-in-hand-with-sustainability/>

We continue our Flash Interviews with project partners. Today we speak with Elizabeth Nerantzis from ALPHA, whose role focuses on assessing the economic feasibility and social impact of the technological solutions proposed by MAELSTROM for marine litter removal: the Bubble Barrier implemented in Vila do Conde, Portugal, and the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform implemented in Venice, Italy.

Through a detailed Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA), ALPHA aims to demonstrate the added value of these solutions compared to traditional marine waste management methods, providing concrete data on costs, social benefits, and environmental advantages. These evaluations have allowed ALPHA to compare the operational and maintenance costs with existing technologies, highlighting the benefits in terms of plastic waste reduction and ecosystem preservation.

What is ALPHA's role in the project?

ALPHA plays a key role in assessing the economic and social viability of MAELSTROM's solutions, leading the work package focused on Economic Feasibility, Social and Economic Impact. This involves conducting a thorough Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA), especially for the MAELSTROM cleaning technologies—namely the Bubble Barrier and the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform—to highlight the added value of these innovations over existing solutions. Additionally, ALPHA is responsible for developing a roadmap for exploitation, guiding partners in effectively marketing, and commercializing these technologies. Our efforts focus on bridging the gap between innovative research and practical, sustainable applications that can make a real impact in waste management.

Can you give us a concrete example of your activities within MAELSTROM?

Certainly! One concrete example is our work on the Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) for MAELSTROM's cleaning technologies—the Bubble Barrier in the Ave River in Portugal and the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in the Venice Lagoon in Italy. Our team evaluates the full range of costs involved, from installation to maintenance and daily operations, and compares these with traditional waste-cleanup methods. For instance, we assess whether the Bubble Barrier offers a cost-effective way to trap riverine plastic waste without disturbing local ecosystems, or if the Robotic Platform can increase the efficiency of seabed cleaning in sensitive areas like the Venice Lagoon. By quantifying not only financial aspects but also social and environmental benefits, such as plastic waste reduction and ecosystem preservation, this CBA offers stakeholders a clear view of the long-term value and feasibility of these technologies.

What has kept you most engaged during this latest phase of work?

The most engaging aspect of this phase has been seeing MAELSTROM's technologies in action and collaborating with partners to map out realistic, effective commercialization strategies. It's inspiring to work on pioneering technologies that directly address marine litter pollution and could help preserve vulnerable ecosystems such as the Ave River and the Venice Lagoon. Being able to contribute to a project that combines economic viability with environmental sustainability—and has real potential to tackle the marine litter pollution issue and transform waste management across Europe—continues to energize our team each day.

ANNEX 5 – MAELSTROM PROJECT EVENTS

- MAELSTROM Kick off meeting, February 3-5, 2021, Online

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/eu-h2020-maelstrom-kicks-off-to-tackle-marine-litter-in-coastal-ecosystems/>

- 1st International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities – June 3, 2021, Venice, Italy | Joint event with InNoPlastic H2020 project | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/maelstrom-in-no-plastic-workshop/>

- Clean up Venice; Italy – International Environment Day within the EU Green Week, June 5, 2021 | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/maelstrom-in-no-plastic-workshop/>

- Porto Beach Clean-up, Portugal – World Clean Up Day, September 18, 2021 <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/beach-clean-up-2/>

- Webinar Science and society: Working together to address the marine litter challenge, November 18, 2021 | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/inspiring-science-and-society-to-tackle-marine-litter/>

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*Inspiring Science and Society
to tackle Marine Litter*

18.11.2021 • 09.30 – 16.00 CET

09.30 | Welcome
 Fantina Madricardo (CNR-Ismar)
 Isabel Sousa Pinto (CIIMAR)

09.45 | Keynote
 Thomais Vlachogianni (MIO-ECSDE)

10.00 - 12.15 | Linking targets to effectiveness in fighting
 marine litter pollution: global to local perspectives
 Moderators: Luis R. Vieira (CIIMAR) | Isabel Gomes (CIMA)

10.00 - 10.15 | Giorgio Bagordo | World Wildlife Fund (WWF)

10.15 - 10.30 | Fedra Francocci | BlueMed Initiative

10.30 - 10.45 | Break

10.45 - 11.00 | Pedro São Simão | The Portuguese Plastics Pact

11.00 - 11.15 | Czarina Constantino | WWF Philippines

11.15 - 11.30 | Maria Vicente | Open Science Hub - Portugal

11.30 - 11.45 | Gian Claudio Faussonne | The marGnet project

11.45 - 12.15 | Q&A with the audience

12.15 - 13.30 | Lunch Break

13.30 - 14.45 | Past, Present and Future Marine Litter Challenges
 Participatory SWOT Analysis
 Moderators: Davide Poletto (VLPF) | Luis R. Vieira (CIIMAR) | Isabel Gomes (CIMA)

14:45 - 15.00 | Break

15:00 - 16.00 | Round Table
 SWOT Analysis Discussion
 Contributions for transformative changes in the next decade
 Moderator: Thomais Vlachogianni (MIO-ECSDE)

REGISTRATION LINK:
www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/webinar-registration/

Co-funded by the European Union

organized by:

- Webinar Localize and Characterize: Building Capacity in Detecting, Tracking and Modelling Marine Litter through European Open Science Cloud (#EOSC) Digital Services, May 10, 2022

- Local Stakeholder meeting & Demonstration event - Venice| May 31, 2022 | Within the International Venice Boat Show | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/inspiring-science-and-society-to-tackle-marine-litter/>

- 2nd International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities – June 1, Venice, Italy | Joint event with InNoPlasticsH2020 project

Second International Workshop | 1 June 2022
Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy: Challenges and opportunities
 PARTNER EVENT OF THE EU GREEN WEEK
 CNR-ISMAR, Arsenale, Tesa 104 Castello 2737/F, 30122 - Venice (Italy)

Link online:
<https://cnronline.webex.com/cnronline/j.php?MTID=m7f138cc9a33e6851cbd0e3e778ab916d>

In cooperation with:

Co-funded by the European Union

- Clean up Venice – International Environment Day within the EU Green Week, June 2, 2022
<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/venice-clean-up-2022/>

IX EDIZIONE
INTERNATIONAL CLEAN-UP DAY
EU GREEN WEEK
2 GIUGNO 2022

 Co-funded by the European Union

- Vila do Conde Sunset Beach Cleanup, I Edition - September 17, 2022

- MAELSTROM WEBINAR – Biodiversity and Marine Litter: Co-detection and impacts, February 10, 2023

- 3rd International Workshop – Marine Litter Monitoring, Removal and Circular Economy: Challenges and Opportunities

The poster features a header with logos for MAELSTROM, InNoPlastic, CNR ISMAR, SINTEF, VENICE LAGOON, and ISDI GROUP. The main text reads: "Third International Workshop | 1 June 2023", "Marine Litter Monitoring, Removal and Circular Economy: Challenges and Opportunities", and "CNR-ISMAR, Arsenale, Tesa 104 Castello 2737/F, 30122 • Venice (Italy)". A QR code is provided for remote connection, with a URL: <https://us06web.zoom.us/j/8481522247?pwd=QWp1d2xqN1ZlWlRlbnYyZmR1bnRyMjRkdz09>. Below the text is a photograph of a beach with plastic litter. The footer includes logos for "In cooperation with" (SALONE NAUTICO VENEZIA, 10 & 20, REAM, NATERA 2019, Winblue, cimca) and "Co-funded by the European Union" (PLASTIC SMARTCITIES, WWF).

- Cleanup Venice – 2 June, 2023

CLEAN-UP DAY IN THE VENETIAN LAGOON

**MORE THAN A THOUSAND KILOS OF
LITTER COLLECTED**

- Launch Event/Live Demonstration of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in the Venice Lagoon, June 9, 2023

The poster features a dark blue background with the MAELSTROM logo at the top center, which includes a stylized sun and waves. Below the logo, the text reads 'MAELSTROM' and 'Smart technology for MARINE Litter SuStainable ReMOval and Management'. In the top right corner, there is a 'EU PARTNER GREEN WEEK EVENTS' logo. The main text in the center is 'PUBLIC EVENT' followed by 'Live demonstration of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in the Venice Lagoon' in orange. Below this, it says '9 JUNE 2023 | 5 pm' and 'PUNTA DELLA DOGANA - VENEZIA'. A central image shows an aerial view of a large white rectangular platform on the water with a smaller boat nearby. At the bottom, there is a row of logos for various partners including Deltares, L'Inchiesta, EIT Digital, ST, tecnalia, AlphaConsult, climar, ST, and MAKEEN. Below the logos is the website 'www.maelstrom-h2020.eu' and social media icons for Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, and YouTube. At the very bottom, it says 'Co-funded by the European Union' with the EU flag logo.

- Vila do Conde Sunset Beach Cleanup, II Edition - 23 September 2023

ACTNOW

MAELSTROM
 Smart technology for MAriNE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management

23
~~16~~ de Setembro - Vila do Conde

Sunset Beach Cleanup

Programa Inscrições →

17h00 - Receção dos Participantes e Briefing
17h30 - Início da Limpeza de Praia
19h00 - Pausa para Lanche
20h00 - Atividades "Lixo Marinho e Microplásticos"
21h00 - Passeio Cósmico
23h00 - Término do Evento

Ponto de encontro
 CMIA - Vila do Conde
 41°20'39.6"N, 8°44'44.0"W

Organização

Com o Apoio:

- Launch Event Bubble Barrier, 25 November 2023

The poster features a dark blue background with a subtle pattern of bubbles and a large, stylized white MAELSTROM logo at the top. Below the logo, the text reads: "MAELSTROM Smart technology for MARine Litter Sustainable RemOval and Management". The main title is "Evento de inauguração Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde", with "Bubble Barrier" in a larger, bold font. The date and time are "25 novembro 2023 10h30", and the location is "Junto ao CMIA Vila do Conde". At the bottom, there is a row of logos for the organizing institutions: Câmara Municipal Vila do Conde, DOCAPESCA, CIMAR, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Universidade de Aveiro, Universidade de Coimbra, Universidade de Évora, Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Alentejo, Universidade do Algarve, Universidade do Porto, Universidade de Lisboa, and the European Union.

MAELSTROM
Smart technology for MARine Litter Sustainable RemOval and Management

Evento de inauguração
Bubble Barrier
Vila do Conde

25 novembro 2023
10h30
Junto ao CMIA Vila do Conde

Logos at the bottom: Câmara Municipal Vila do Conde, DOCAPESCA, CIMAR, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Universidade de Aveiro, Universidade de Coimbra, Universidade de Évora, Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Alentejo, Universidade do Algarve, Universidade do Porto, Universidade de Lisboa, and Co-funded by the European Union.

- Gnejna Bay Beach Cleanup, Malta, 16th March 2024

MAELSTROM
Smart technology for Marine Litter Sustainable Removal and Management

Gnejna Bay Beach Cleanup

16th March 2024 | 10-13 | Gnejna Bay, Malta

www.maelstrom-h2020.eu

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Co-funded by
the European Union

- MAELSTROM WEBINAR: One Ocean, One Health: Current Perspectives on Marine Litter in Ecosystem and Human Health - March 20, 2024

BLUEMISSION AA
ATLANTIC & ARCTIC LIGHTHOUSE
WEEKLY HOUR S02E05

- 4th International Workshop – Marine Litter Monitoring, Removal and Circular Economy: Challenges and Opportunities

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

BLUE MISSION MED

EU MISSIONS

MAELSTROM

EU PARTNER GREEN EVENTS WEEK

4th International Workshop | 30 May 2024

Marine Litter Monitoring, Removal and Circular Economy: Solutions for the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters

Community of Actors back 2 back with the BlueMissionMed Italian HUB

📍 CNR-ISMAR, Arsenale, Tesa 104 Castello 2737/F, 30122 - Venice (Italy)

https://teams.microsoft.com/j/19%3ameeting_ZmFIN-GJYzMN2MzMS00NDU0LWwZDctNDU3MzZm1ZmlwNTQ5%40thread.v2/0?context=%7b%22Tid%22%3a%2234c64e9f-d27f-4edd-af0-1397f0c84f94%22%2c%22DId%22%3a%228287ebe4-8e6b-450c-96d8-01672fd3b453%22%7d

in cooperation with:

SALONE NAUTICO VENEZIA

CIMA

L&D GROUP

OCEAN

REMEDIES

Funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union

- Vila do Conde Sunset Beach Cleanup – III Edition, 21 September 2024

The poster features a blue sky background with a white horizon line. At the top, there are logos for 'WORLD CLEANUP DAY', the European Union flag with 'ACT NOW', and 'EUROPEAN CLIMATE PACT'. The MAELSTROM logo is centered, with the tagline 'Smart technology for MARINE Litter Sustainable Removal and Management'. Below this, the event details are listed: 'September 21st - Vila do Conde' and 'Sunset Beach Cleanup'. The 'Agenda' section lists activities from 16h00 to 23h00. A 'Registration' section includes a QR code and the meeting point location: 'CMIA - Vila do Conde' with coordinates '41°20'39.6"N, 8°44'44.0"W'. The 'Organization' section lists partners: 'ciimar', 'CÂMARA MUNICIPAL VILA DO CONDE', 'counting stars', 'centro de monitorização e interpretação ambiental vila do conde', and 'CIMIA'. A photograph shows two people in blue shirts and gloves collecting litter. The bottom section, 'Supported by:', lists various partners including PACTO, AELM, L'Università ta' Malta, AQUA WASTE, FOCA, UNIFARDAS, and DOCAPESCA, along with the European Union logo.

- MAELSTROM FINAL EVENT, Porto, Portugal 21-22 November 2024

- International Cleanup and Marine Litter Monitoring Day, 10 December 2024

ANNEX 5 – EXTERNAL EVENTS

2021

- ITEM project online workshop, 13/01/2021

- EU Biovoices Project Conference, 14/01/2021

https://www.biovoices-platform.eu/public/_viewFile/60130b29ddfbad073c50bbef

- Blue Med Final Conference, 22-23-24/02/2021

<http://www.bluedmed-initiative.eu/bluedmed-final-conference/>

One Mediterranean: practices, results and strategies for a common Sea
BlueMed CSA Final Conference
 22-24 February 2021, on-line, digital hub at CNR in Rome

The Mediterranean Sea is a crucial crossroad for the history, economy and culture of Europe, Middle East and North African countries. Many different interests depend on its resources, and the development of a coordinated plan for a shared, coherent and sustainable management is of paramount importance. Moreover, crucial issues like plastic pollution need to be tackled together by all Mediterranean countries, and pooling all relevant knowledge and people both from research and from the socio-political arena.

The BlueMed Initiative, launched in 2014, addresses these challenges, working on all the relevant levels, stimulating pan-Mediterranean network-building and coordinating thematic platforms. The co-building of a **shared Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda**, the subsequent **goals prioritisation** and the development of their **Implementation Plans**, as well as the outcomes of the **Pilot Initiative for a Healthy, Plastic-free Mediterranean Sea**, of the **Start Up Actions** and of the **Ambassadors' Programme** are the most mature achievements of the BlueMed work and will be presented during the conference.

- Ecosistemas Marinhos e Economia Azul, 23/04/2021

<https://ambienteportugal.pt/event/ecosistemas-marinhos-e-economia-azul>

- marGnet and MAELSTROM Demonstration activity: operation of a prototype for recycling of marine waste and the production of maritime fuel

- European Maritime Day - Session BLUINVEST, 21/05/2021

https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/events/2021-european-maritime-day-2021-05-20_en

- NCR May Lecture – Netherlands Centre for River Studies, 26/05/2021

<https://ncr-web.org/events/ncr-may-lecture/>

NCR May Lecture

26 May 2021 - 13:00

Netherlands
Centre for
River studies

NCR | May Lecture

Date 26 May, 2021 | 13:00 - 14:00

Lecturer Frans Buschman

Topic Transport and fate of plastic litter in rivers - how can monitoring be supported by modelling?

- EU Cluster Meeting on projects dealing with 'Marine Litter', 01/06/2021

<https://bioplasticseurope.eu/media/pages/news-events/horizon-2020-cluster-meeting-on-marine-litter/21c23f102f-1646989939/agenda.pdf>

02. Jun 2021

Horizon 2020 cluster meeting on marine litter

The European Research Agency has organised a cluster meeting with Horizon 2020 projects dealing with marine litter. BIO-PLASTICS EUROPE Coordinator Prof. Walter Leal and Lead Project Manager Dr. Jelena Barbir were present.

Abandoned, lost or discarded fishing gear accounts for 27% of beach litter in the EU

- Venice International Boat Show, 29/05/2021 - 6/06/2021

- Online seminar in the framework of the event "Arazzi del Mare", 8 /06/2021
- AreaAperta Primavera, 16/06/2021
- BlueMed Hackathon 2021, 17/06/2021

Do you care about **marine pollution**? Apply now!
Registrations open until May 10th 2021

blueMed
HACKATHON

Ideas and solutions for a Healthy Plastic Free Mediterranean Sea

Are you a passionate young MSc and PhD graduate in STEM disciplines,
a creative or a marine sciences young professional?

Join the BlueMed Hackathon
to contribute solving plastic pollution challenges!

Info and registrations:
<https://semed.eu/search?q=bluemed>
<http://www.bluemed-initiative.eu/bluemed-hackathon/>

Powered by

- EMRA2021 Robotics, 08/07/2021

- BlueMed - Unlocking the potential of Ports and Harbours in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter, 14/09/2021

Unlocking the potential of Ports and Harbours in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter

September 14, 2021, CNR ISMAR in Venice and online

This workshop looks at the most promising R&I solutions undertaken, as well as the policy instruments implemented, in the management and valorization of plastic litter in Ports/Harbours and their hinterland at Mediterranean level. The aim of the event is to identify gaps and bottlenecks to be overcome for an effective prevention and mitigation from the impact of marine litter across the whole basin.

Harbours and Marinas, that are among the heavily affected areas by the effects of marine litter, could play a strategic role in the remediation and prevention process from plastic pollution in the long term. Indeed, they act as catalysts for stakeholders across the plastic value chain by favoring the connection and collaboration among the shipping and fisheries sectors, encouraging the availability and adequacy of port reception facilities, as well as the conversion of waste – such as fishing gears – into valuable materials.

Photo by Nick Karvounis on Unsplash

- “Arazzi del Mare” organized by QUANTIA – ITALIA, 24/09/2021

- European Maritime Day: Innovation Platform "Sustainable Sea and Ocean Solutions ISSS", 23/09/2021

- IHOBE Comisión Basura Marina para el país vasco, 28/09/2021

https://www.ihobe.eus/agenda/urban-klima-2050-colaboracion-multisectorial-para-financiar-y-reducir-brecha-adaptacion-en-pais-vasco-2?fbclid=IwAR1eN9T4nLTIs8hUlVv3hPz8jjBD4YpUe1gyKqZCzuacujWllOzHm_448Q

- Scienza in Villa, 01/10/2021 – 03/10/2021

<https://www.scienzainvilla.com>

- ECOMONDO 2021 - Transforming plastic litter into new chemicals? Opportunities and challenges for innovative pyrolysis plants, 26/10/2021

<https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-12/ECOMONDO%20-%20Chemical%20recycling%20-%20summary%20report%20rev%20%282%29.pdf>

<p>10:00 - 13:00</p> <p>Sala Ravezzi 2 Hall Sud</p> <p>BLUE GROWTH Evento con la Commissione Europea</p>	<p>Transforming plastic litter into new chemicals? Opportunities and challenges for innovative pyrolysis plants - VERSIONE IN LINGUA INGLESE</p> <p>Lingua: inglese Traduzione simultanea: italiano</p> <p>Organized by: Ecomondo Scientific Technical Committee and CINEA (Sustainable Blue Economy Unit)</p> <p>The workshop will gather innovators, local and ports authorities, legislators and stakeholders, e.g. plastics association and fishers and vessels, to discuss the opportunities offered by pyrolysis plants to convert plastics waste into new chemicals. At the same time the technical and legislative barriers that hinder the exploitation of this kind of technologies will be addressed.</p> <p>The workshop will tackle plastics coming from different waste streams, and will specifically focus on the use of low temperature pyrolysis plants to treat marine litter.</p>
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- **ECOMONDO 2021 -The BlueMed Pilot healthy plastics-free Mediterranean Sea towards the 2030 targets: the strategy developed by the plastic producing and transforming operators of the area, 26/10/2021**

<https://www.ecomondo.com/eventi/ecomondo-2022/seminari-e-convegni/e20336286/the-blue-med-pilot-healthy-plastics-free-mediterranean-sea-and-the-eu-mission-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-by-2030.html>

Home / Eventi / Ecomondo 2022 / Programma Eventi

Ecomondo 2022

The BlueMed Pilot healthy plastics-free Mediterranean sea and the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030

 Venerdì 11 Novembre 2022

 10:00 - 13:00

 MEMO

 Sala Diotallevi 1 Hall Sud

 inglese

Organized by: Ecomondo Scientific Technical Committee & BlueMed GSOs, Federchimica-PlasticsEurope Italia, Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions (CPMR), National Research Council of Italy (CNR)

 Blue Economy

- **ECOMONDO 2021 - Connecting the system of Ports and Harbours to unlock the potential in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter across the Mediterranean Sea, 27/10/2021**

https://en.ecomondo.com/ecomondo/programma-eventi/pdf-calendario-eventi/2021/ecomondo-2021_eng_esteso_2010.pdf

14:30 - 17:30

Diotallevi 2 Room South Hall

BLUE GROWTH

Ecomondo Event

Connecting the system of Ports and Harbours to unlock the potential in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter across the Mediterranean - Ecomondo and Blue Sea Land Joint Event - VERSIONE IN LINGUA INGLESE

Language: English
Simultaneous translation: Italian

Organized by: Ecomondo Scientific Technical Committee, Blue Sea Land, Cluster BIG, Federpesca, CNR, BLUEMED GSOs

2022

- Workshop EMFF Integration, Scaling Up and Cooperation with other EU Funding Instruments, 03/02/2022

<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/maritimeforum/en/node/7000?fs=e&s=cl>

- EXPO Dubai: Multidisciplinary and systemic approaches for the rational use of resource and sustainability, 14/03/2022

<https://www.isofom.cnr.it/index.php/en/attivita/divulgazione/tutte-le-news/373-dubai-expo-2020-land-city-sea-scape-intelligence-multidisciplinary-and-systemic-approaches-for-the-rational-use-of-resource-and-sustainability>

- Jornadas do Mar: New Solutions for the Sustainable Removal and Management of Marine Litter, 26/03/2022
<https://www.jornadasdomar.com/schedule>

Programa Científico - Jornadas do Mar III

Sábado (26 de março)

14h00 "Novas Soluções para a Remoção e Gestão Sustentável do Lixo Marinho" | Local: A04.P1.11
- Dr. Luís Vieira

- XI Edition of the Environment Forum: "Removal and Sustainable Management of Marine Litter: Rethinking the Present, Designing the Future", 05/04/2022

AMBIENTE:
UM IMPULSO À INOVAÇÃO

PROGRAMA

09h Sessão de Abertura
Prof. Augusto Sousa | Vice-Presidente do Conselho Pedagógico
| Presidente Ordem dos Engenheiros Região Norte
Prof. Joana Dias | Diretora da Licenciatura e Mestrado em Engenharia do Ambiente
Carolina Lopo e Maria Carolina Duarte | Presidência da Comissão Organizadora

09h30 Impulso I Compartimentos Ambientais
Moderador: Prof. Cristina Vila
9h30: Dr. Luís Vieira | Remoção e Gestão Sustentável do Lixo Marinho: Repensar o Presente, Projetar o Futuro
9h50: Eng. Teresa Valente | TERRA MATER
10h10: Prof. Romualdo Salcedo | Projeto ACS

COFFEE BREAK

11h Impulso II Indústria em Portugal
Moderador: Prof. Mário Amorim Lopes
11h00: Eng. Ana Cruz | Sustentável por Natureza
11h20: Dr.ª Patrícia Vieira | Valérius 360
11h40: Eng. Miguel Cachão | *ReoWine* - Quando o CO₂ é a Solução

ALMOÇO

5 ABR
GRANDE AUDITÓRIO
DA FEUP

FÓRUM DO AMBIENTE
XI EDIÇÃO

Logos: FEUP, LEA, ALICE, SUMA, etc.

- GEOHAB 2022 – Marine Geological & Biological Mapping, 16-20/05/2022
<https://geohab.org/2022-program/>

- European Marine Robotics & Applications 2022 – Workshop, 16/06/2022
<https://noc-events.co.uk/emra-2022>

- AUTOMATION & ROBOTIC TALKS – within BIEMH22 trade fair, 17/06/2022
<https://biemh.bilbaoexhibitioncentre.com/en/conferences/automation-robotic-talks/>

- PLASTICA E CAMBIAMENTI CLIMATICI, UN MARE DA DIFENDERE, 22/06/2022
<https://www.cnr.it/it/nota-stampa/n-11193/plastica-e-cambiamenti-climatici-un-mare-da-difendere>

- UN Ocean Conference: Localizing Action for the Ocean: Local and Regional Governments Special Event

https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2022-04/Concept%20Note%202022%20UNOC%20Local%20and%20Regional%20Gov%20Forum_REVISED_7April_for%20website%20%281%29.pdf

- UN Ocean Conference: One Sustainable Ocean-Ocean Science & Business2Sea Side Event

<https://oceansciencebusiness2sea.b2match.io/>

- UN Ocean Conference: *EU4OceanObs: Integrating Marine Litter Monitoring to Inform Action* <https://www.eu4oceanobs.eu/marine-litter-monitoring-to-inform-action/>

- UN Ocean Conference: The Charter for the Mission “Restores our Ocean and Waters by 2030”

https://ec.europa.eu/info/events/charter-mission-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-2030-2022-jun-30_en

- ERF2022 – European Robotics Forum – Marine Robotics Workshop + Sustainable Robotics workshop

<https://erf2022.eu>

- 7th International Marine Debris Conference

<https://internationalmarinedebrisconference.org/index.php/7imdc-home-page/>

- European Research and Innovation Days

https://research-innovation-community.ec.europa.eu/events/5rBGp9lUhJt2lmxYEK45Qf/programme?fbclid=IwY2xjawHD6H9leHRuA2FlbQlxMAABHS-QAukCEQwSSGzer7fTrqJLLNu3OMj7rYSoiwik_qo7kmlZX4OQ-Q8Ghw_aem_zBksj_sPylEZh-iFvcU1qw

EUROPEAN RESEARCH & INNOVATION DAYS

29 SEPTEMBER 2022

16:00-16:45

Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters: synergies and next steps

#RiDaysEU

Join this session
Register now!

European Commission

- Marine Litter and Circular Economy Workshop
<https://programming14-20.italy-croatia.eu/web/marless>

Marine Litter and Circular Economy

Progetto MARLESS

MARine Litter cross-border awareNess and innovation actions

26 Ottobre 2022

- Black Sea CONNECT Marine Litter Action Forum
<http://connect2blacksea.org/marine-litter-action-forum/>

- Innovazul
<https://aquabt.com/event/innovazul-2nd-international-meeting-on-knowledge-and-the-blue-economy/>

- Pan-European digital assets supporting research communities – Benefits & Opportunities

https://eoscfuture.eu/eventsfuture/webinar-pan-european-digital-assets-supporting-research-communities-benefits-opportunities/?fbclid=IwY2xjawHD7dpleHRuA2FlbQIxMAABHXlM51yxqfyTrPRofM4R50qbpjaNiT-T2onVP6Byoys_8lmLgKsSWCMAew_aem_ZijBpLLJ8NGmfdY8hJqW

**PAN-EUROPEAN DIGITAL ASSETS
SUPPORTING RESEARCH COMMUNITIES**

Benefits & opportunities

**5-6 December 2022
Online**

Register now!

EOSC Future C-SCALE DICE EGI-ACE OpenAIRE NEXUS Reliance

The EOSC Future, C-SCALE, DICE, EGI-ACE, OpenAIRE-Nexus and RELIANCE projects are funded by the European Union Horizon Programme calls INFRAEOSC-03-2020 and INFRAEOSC-07-2020

2023

- CSA Blue Mission Med

<https://bluemissionmed.eu/bluemissionmed-kom-in-venice-italy/>

- 1st EU Mission Forum

https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/events/1st-annual-forum-eu-mission-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-2030-2023-02-17_en

- European Robotics Forum - Advancing the Un Sustainable Development Goals with Autonomous Robots

<https://erf2023.sdu.dk/timetable/event/phd-award-finalists-pitches-2/>

- CINEA Workshop "Synergies and Clustering between Maritime Projects"
https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/events/workshop-ocean-health-observation-2023-04-17_en

EUROPEAN CLIMATE, INFRASTRUCTURE AND ENVIRONMENT EXECUTIVE AGENCY (CINEA)

CINEA.D - Natural resources, climate, sustainable blue economy and clean energy
D.3 - Sustainable Blue Economy

Synergies and Clustering between Maritime Projects (EASME/EMFF/2020/3.1.12) – SI2.850620

“Workshop on Ocean Health & Observation”

- GEOHAB 2023

https://geohab.org/geohab-2023/?fbclid=IwY2xjawHD8MhleHRuA2FlbQlxMAABHYYNrtLe4hNhutUsBB2doKWjhFDij4VFkQuBoZwUznhJEanCB2pZrKvNOQ_aem_-47uBTE7s01Qq3uc-J-TbA

International Symposium 2023
 May 8-12 th - Reunion Island

- European Maritime Days

https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/events/european-maritime-day-2023-2023-05-24_en

- EU Mission “Restore our Oceans and Waters” – The Mediterranean Lighthouse in Action

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters_en

- Celebrating a decade of marine research cooperation along and across the Atlantic Ocean – Our Shared Resource

https://allatlanticocean.org/all-atlantic-forums/2023-galway/?fbclid=IwY2xjawHD8hVleHRuA2FlbQlXMAABHZomZXff1VsnxBCyTfzwZ97t0mmgfJd7_mwfHwhdxs8rF2sRc6keML-sNQ_aem_LLkYTrsUUI1pjF7ltNJx2w

2013 – 2023 | 10 YEARS OF THE GALWAY STATEMENT

Celebrating a decade of marine research cooperation along and across the Atlantic – **Our Shared Resource**

5-6 JULY 2023 | GALWAY, IRELAND

#AtlanticAll

BUILDING AN ALL ATLANTIC OCEAN COMMUNITY
Implementing the Belém Statement

BLUEMISSION 44
Building a coordinated hub to support the Mission implementation in the Atlantic and Arctic Basin

European Commission

Riadas na hÉireann
Government of Ireland

Foras na Mara
Marine Institute

OLLSCOIL NA GAILLIMHIRE
UNIVERSITY OF GALWAY

- Ciência Viva 2023

<https://www.cienciaviva.pt/semanact/2023/>

**CIÊNCIA
2023**

ENCONTRO COM A CIÊNCIA E A TECNOLOGIA EM PORTUGAL

**CIÊNCIA
E OCEANO
PARA
ALÉM DO
HORIZONTE**

5-7 JULHO 2023
AVEIRO
CAMPUS UNIVERSITÁRIO
DE SANTIAGO

- Third Portuguese Conference on Marine Litter and Microplastics
<https://www.mare-centre.pt/pt/3-conferencia-sobre-lixo-marinho-e-microplasticos>

#3CPLM #LIXOMARINHO #APLIXOMARINHO
#MICROPLASTICOS #PAVILHAODOCONHECIMENTO

**10 ANOS
POR UM MAR SEM LIXO**

**21 > 22 SETEMBRO 2023
PAVILHÃO DO CONHECIMENTO**

- Scienza in Villa 2023
<https://www.scienzainvilla.com/>

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SCIENZA IN VILLA

MONTEBELLUNA!

WEEKEND EDITION 2023

22-23 SETTEMBRE

INGRESSO GRATUITO

Scopri il programma di tutti gli incontri su www.scienzainvilla.com o sui nostri social

prenotazione non obbligatoria ma consigliata scrivendo a prenotazioni.siv@gmail.com

- Ocean Best Practices (OBPS) Workshop VII

<https://oceandecode.org/challenges/>

- ECOMONDO 2023

<https://www.mase.gov.it/pagina/ecomondo-2023>

- Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee (INC-3) on Plastic Pollution, Kenya
<https://www.unep.org/inc-plastic-pollution/session-3>

- Conference on the Protection of Waters and Seas from Plastics and Micro-plastics Pollution
<https://www.adriatic-ionian.eu/event/conference-on-the-protection-of-waters-and-seas-from-plastics-and-micro-plastics-pollution/>

2024

- Circular Venice: policy, practices, and innovation in comparison

https://vsf.foundation/en/eventi/circular-venice-policy-practice-and-innovation-compared/?fbclid=IwY2xjawHD-q9leHRuA2FlbQlxMAABHaxy-eN-Ow5SZd2T6h4GU-2RgmP6WLZZqTawNvbY-JnXNCCYGfyW6a_pPg_aem_aDmsyujnoUe19tqroBc1eQ

Circular Venice: policy, practice and innovation compared

29 January Orario 9:00 am - 1:30 pm

- EUROPEAN OCEAN DAYS

https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/theme/governance/european-ocean-days_en?fbclid=IwY2xjawHD-wpleHRuA2FlbQlxMAABHTf2So5pBLwrYpU9T00-uqQ3LdQw5yY6ZR2kwc0wagZgfvSOPpCKKct81Q_aem_Dtym1buV2AUVI9RO0Mt6WA

- EUROPEAN ROBOTICS FORUM 2024

<https://erf2024.eu/>

- UNITED NATIONS OCEAN DECADE CONFERENCE 2024

<https://oceandecade.org/events/2024-ocean-decade-conference/>

- 9th Our Ocean Conference
<https://www.ourocean2024.gov.gr/>

- Innovations on Plastic recycling
<https://www.linkedin.com/events/7183749730412216321/>

- GEOHAB 2024
<https://geohab.org/geohab-2024/>

- Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee (INC-4) on Plastic Pollution
<https://www.unep.org/inc-plastic-pollution/session-4>

- **ITALIAN BLUEMISSIONMED HUB IN ACTION** - Workshop on Marine Litter Monitoring, Removal, and Circular Economy

<https://bluemissionmed.eu/bluemissionmed-hubs/>

- **EUROPEAN FUNDED MARINE ROBOTICS AND APPLICATIONS - EMRA 2024**

https://emra-24.marinerobotics.eu/?fbclid=IwY2xjawHD_nlleHRuA2FlbQlxMAABHfQZorNLI3TZrQXVypOhbJXvk38YTmBTUmmUw7fDtBmLzFkh9IYeYFA7YQ_aem_FNvJJevl40iZi5rWk7Vrwg

- Blue Economy – The key towards Mediterranean regional Sustainability

https://bluepartnership.eu/sites/bluepartnership.eu/files/documents/2024-06/agenda_the_key_towards_mediterranean_regional_sustainability_updated_05.06.2024.pdf?fbclid=IwY2xjawHD_yJleHRuA2FlbQlxMAABHc-e_yYkH2i1FeGL7WFUYjWDW1R56sWclqjsG0yAQcDyHkcCzyFb_A7cuQ_aem_nfCDy4je7OGq_3aYmohSSQ

- Ciência 2024

<https://www.fct.pt/encontro-ciencia-2024-save-the-date/>

- UN MARE DI PLASTICA?

https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/o-sea-of-plastic/?fbclid=IwY2xjawHEAD1leHRuA2FlbQlxMAABHUJXGPLc8JsZFYi10NFV8oaQ0x_GYuxvDZSC8-KvLwltoneVzVsNpVhbMw_aem_VAozYm-fgzDZpuleZ1hMg

- TRASH TRAPPING IN EUROPE

https://www.eventbrite.co/e/trash-trapping-in-europe-tickets-999235830267?aff=oddtcreator&fbclid=IwY2xjawHEAKZleHRuA2FlbQlxMAABHc-e_yYkH2iIFeGL7WFUYjWDW1R56sWclqjsG0yAQcDyHkcCzyFb_A7cuQ_aem_nfCDy4je7OGq_3aYmohSSQ

- MICRO 2024

https://micro2024.sciencesconf.org/?fbclid=IwY2xjawHEAQJleHRuA2FlbQlxMAABHc-e_yYkH2iIFeGL7WFUYjWDW1R56sWclqjsG0yAQcDyHkcCzyFb_A7cuQ_aem_nfCDy4je7OGq_3aYmohSSQ

MICRO 2024
PLASTIC POLLUTION
FROM MACRO TO NANO
23-27 SEPTEMBER
LANZAROTE
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

- BLUE MISSION MED - Restoring Lampedusa Island

<https://bluemissionmed.eu/bluemissionmed-italian-hub-event-restoring-lampedusa-island-a-pilot-action-for-the-eu-mission-restore-our-ocean-and-waters/>

Regione Siciliana
ASSESSORATO DEL TERRITORIO E DELL'AMBIENTE
DIPARTIMENTO DELL'AMBIENTE

BLUE MISSION MED

RESTORE OUR OCEAN & WATERS BY 2030

Azione pilota per la EU Mission
"Restore our Ocean and Waters"
Workshop "Restoring Lampedusa Island"

La Missione UE "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030" mira a proteggere e ripristinare la salute del nostro oceano e delle nostre acque attraverso la ricerca e l'innovazione, il coinvolgimento dei cittadini e investimenti blu.

25 ottobre 2024
ore 10.30-16.00
Lampedusa

INFO: **091 7077807**
091 7077223
dra@regione.sicilia.it

Sala riunioni dell'Area Marina Protetta di Lampedusa
via Cameroni s.n.c. - Isola di Lampedusa (AG)

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Università degli Studi di Palermo
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- Business2Sea Forum Oceano 2024

<https://database.forumoceano.pt/en/business2sea-forum-do-mar-2/>

